

More than 400 global consensus and United Nations conventions that change the world's pattern and maintain world peace

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Global politicians, strategists, and the media should soberly realize that economic development does not necessarily bring civilization, and technology progress does not necessarily lead to civilization. On the contrary, they may foster widespread large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, trafficking in human beings or organ harvesting, and massacres. Looking back at history, people should be able to understand bloody

historical facts.

If anyone, whether a politician, lawyer or advocate, believes that lenient treatment should be given to such crimes, disregarding the suffering of the victims, and does not agree to impose severe punishment on the criminals and their nations, or does not agree to return the looted wealth, according to the principle of logical consistency, they should publicly disclose their full names, photos, addresses, as well as the amount and location of their wealth. At the same time, they must store all their assets in an unsafe place, and they and their families must experience the torture and suffering of 100 victims, taking turns for two days each, as determined by the victims themselves, with no responsibility borne by the victims. If you and your family can endure it, you can disagree with this agreement in your region. However, the premise is that you and your family must have no criminal record, and all sources of property must be legal and reasonable.

Would you like to experience the helplessness and suffering of victims in such harsh conditions? The world should also clearly realize that despicable and evil people always have more demands and seek more benefits than good people. Making concessions to the greed and evil actions of any country is a massive disaster for human society. Before thoroughly investigating these infuriating crimes, no country or company should undertake major economic or military cooperation with such greedy and evil criminal nations. Otherwise, it would be equivalent to providing support for their long-term criminal activities.

Today's rampant crimes in Myanmar, such as illegal detention, torture, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and massacres, as well as the difficulty in capturing criminals, is it not indicative of a semi-slave society? Knowing that most of Myanmar's politicians are involved in these crimes and yet unable to apprehend them, we are forced to cooperate with them. Isn't today's world an abnormal world, one that has lost its philosophy and moral ethics, far inferior to some ancient Chinese dynasties? The author believes that, in order to protect the safety of public life and property, maintain world peace and stability, it is essential to swiftly establish a global consensus and a United Nations convention to combat the crimes mentioned in this article, and to issue a declaration by the United Nations on combating crime. If the United Nations can still breathe independently, it should not wait like a noble waiting for the cries of the victims.

Table 3. Global consensus and United Nations conventions to combat large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, human disappearances, child trafficking, live organ removal, live burial, massacres, poor governance, and laziness in government for a new era characterized by kindness, order, stability, proactivity, empathy, and full of justice.

1	The factors that lead to large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, human trafficking, or organ harvesting crimes in a country are human beings, and politicians who are evil, selfish, greedy, despicable, narrow-minded, and have limited perspectives are more likely to create crime factories. From a philosophical and logical perspective, solving global problems requires understanding the main aspects of contradictions, and politicians in criminal countries have an undeniable responsibility for the crimes defined by this
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	consensus.
2	<p>Any person, organization, or government that commits and harbours crimes such as mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and looting of wealth constitutes a serious crime against humanity that poses a significant threat to global peace. Strict measures must be taken to prevent and punish such crimes. If the countries that are home to the criminals and provide the venues for the crimes, as well as the countries and organizations that protect the criminals, are not severely punished and do not compensate the victims and affected countries for their losses, any country or criminal may repeat the crimes defined by this consensus to plunder wealth, disrupt global peace, and lead humanity's desire for peace into a vicious cycle. Since 1900, all acts of large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, human trafficking, and organ harvesting must be thoroughly addressed and compensated. Only when past crimes were fully investigated, perpetrators and their countries severely punished, the potential for criminal intent suppressed and reformed, and victims and affected countries fairly compensated, could the world gradually become peaceful.</p>
3	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Criminals involved in this consensus are not eligible for parole. Anyone who personally participates in three or more cases of kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, or trafficking in human beings shall be sentenced to death. Anyone who participates in live organ removal or massacre shall be sentenced to death.</p>
4	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang</p>

	<p>rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>The criminal country must compensate for all losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country, and pay for all medical and living expenses of the victims. The criminal State must also pay punitive compensation for the losses suffered by the victims and the victim State. All fraudulently obtained property must be returned in full to the affected country and victims, and damaged property must be compensated at least double the amount of the loss.</p>
5	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Considering that in the process of fraud, criminals not only commit inhumane acts such as torture, organ harvesting, or burying victims alive, but also extort large sums of money, leading to the collapse of victims' families, the compensation standards outlined in this consensus must be implemented according to the compensation standards for 18 death and victim cases in the United States to prevent similar incidents from happening again and to maintain world peace. In the case of large-scale criminal offenses, the minimum compensation for each deceased victim or for each living organ extraction shall be 100 million dollars; for the injured, the minimum compensation shall be 5 million dollars per person. The fines for organ recipients shall be at least \$5</p>

	million per organ per person.
6	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 400 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 200 or more within three years, or with 50 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>The criminal nation is required to publicly disclose detailed information about all suspects and masterminds behind all criminals within its borders, including detailed information about their immediate family members and all descendants, within 15 days of the occurrence of this incident. Any individual who defrauds money shall have all their assets confiscated, including their family's assets, in order to fully recover the victims' properties and ensure complete compensation for the losses.</p>
7	<p>Any criminal organization from any country that carries out large-scale fraud, kidnappings, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres against civilians in other countries (countries that provide criminal venues), with a cumulative number of victims reaching 800 or more within five years, or with a cumulative number of victims reaching 300 or more within three years, or with 100 or more kidnappings, torture incidents, gang rapes, human trafficking cases, or organ harvesting incidents, and 10 or more killings within one year, shall be considered as committing a large-scale crime. Once a country (country that provide criminal venues) is found to tolerate such crimes, protect the perpetrators, or fail to effectively combat such crimes within 72 hours of their occurrence, and the main perpetrators are not apprehended, the crimes shall be punished according to the scale of the massacre, and the victimized country may demand punitive compensation to compensate for the losses suffered by the victims and the victimized country. The military, police or any personnel of the victimized country may enter the territory of the criminal country at any time and take any necessary actions to combat the criminals.</p> <p>Within the next 100 years, all criminals and their descendants must have traceability whenever they leave any city or region, and must report to the law</p>

	<p>enforcement agencies of the victim countries. All assets of the immediate family members and all descendants of the offender must be permanently disclosed.</p>
8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The criminal nation must compensate the victims' property losses in the victim country. The calculation of the monetary interest rate for property losses must be based on a compensation rate of 50-80% of Warren Buffett's annual compound real return of 20.44% from 1957 to 2022. If punitive damages are to be awarded, the rate of compensation should be higher. Any act of deceiving or coercing gambling is considered illegal plunder of wealth. Any act of deceiving or coercing tipping is considered illegal plunder of wealth.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>If a criminal State lacks sufficient funds to fully compensate the victim State or victims in cash, with the agreement of the victim State or victims, part of the compensation from the criminal State can be in the form of land, with the maximum compensation not exceeding 50% of its territory based on land area. However, this land must be legally owned by the country without controversy, and should be used to offset 20-80% of the compensation amount. Land should not be contaminated and compensated land must be continuous. If the criminal State is adjacent to the victim State, then a portion of the adjacent land should be partitioned directly and compensated to the victim State. If the land is not adjacent to the affected country, then it must border another country or be located along the coast. If the land is coastal, then the criminal country must compensate the victimized country with nearby islands and corresponding waters. All rights to land and its corresponding waters belong to the affected</p>

	<p>State and become part of its territory and waters. The criminal State must evacuate all residents of the compensatory land at the expense of the criminal State. All living facilities must be maintained and not destroyed. If resettlement causes difficulties, up to 10% of the female population in the area may be allowed to remain.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
10	<p>Politicians, military personnel, police, intelligence personnel, or public officials involved in or protecting the implementation of large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, and human trafficking must be sentenced to a minimum of 6 to 60 years of imprisonment or death without parole. Dietary standards in prisons can only be based on the minimum standard of living set by middle-income countries in Africa for survival. The offender must serve their sentence in the victim country, and the prison where the offender serves must be a national prison in the victim country or a prison built and managed by the victims. These criminal individuals, their family members, or their descendants are not allowed to engage in the government, military, police, intelligence, judicial, biological, chemical, medical, media, or financial industries, nor can they hold any government positions. They are permanently banned from running for any parliament, presidency, or any government office. They are permanently barred from running for or holding leadership positions in any non-governmental organization. Individuals currently employed in the aforementioned fields must resign within 48 hours. All personal properties or assets under the control of these individuals must be fully compensated to the victim country and victims. Such individuals, their descendants and family members must report all currency assets held in bank accounts to the relevant institutions in the victim country and to the United Nations within 48 hours of receiving the account.</p> <p>For the next 100 years, the annual consumption level of their descendants and family members must not exceed the national average level.</p>
11	<p>Since the beginning of the last century, the number of law students worldwide has increased several times. However, there has been a significant increase in serious crimes against humanity such as kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking or organ harvesting, and subsequent massacres. Judicial institutions have never modified laws to enforce efficient and rapid crackdowns on these crimes. The current judicial system is far less effective than China's ancient system and does not provide adequate protection for citizens' personal safety. Instead, lawyers receive the highest income level, and judicial institutions have completely failed to fulfill their obligations and responsibilities to suppress and reduce crime. They have also not demonstrated the capacity to curb and reduce crime. Consequently, all judicial personnel responsible for formulating the above-mentioned legal provisions should no longer be allowed to formulate any legislative ideologys. Legal rights and procedures for defending criminals and</p>

	<p>criminal nations involved in these large-scale crimes should be abolished. Any lawyer should not be allowed to defend these criminal States and criminals, and their defense should be regarded as committing serious and equivalent crimes against humanity. Any secondary attacks by the victim against the above-mentioned criminals should not be considered as excessive defence, but should instead be commended.</p>
12	<p>Given the serious and long-standing mass criminality in Myanmar, the United Nations, as the global organization responsible for global affairs, has completely failed to coordinate swift action to suppress and combat this crime. This failure has allowed Thailand to become a conduit for the trafficking of kidnapped persons from Myanmar. Salaries of officials in the UN Nations justice system and those in charge of Asian affairs must be reduced by at least 30%. The annual fees paid by China to the UN must be reduced by at least 15-30% until all Chinese victims in Myanmar have been fully assisted, all criminals have been severely punished, and all perpetrators and protectors involved in large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and slaughter have been severely punished. Only after all victims have received adequate compensation, as specified in this article, can the previously deducted amounts be restored.</p>
13	<p>All criminals and their patrons who commit large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and indiscriminate killing, have hoarded enormous amounts of wealth. In criminal states like Myanmar, they not only relentlessly extract the properties of the victims, pushing their families into severe debt, but also unceasingly force victims to scam others to amass wealth for them. They continuously rape and gang-rape their victims, akin to subjugating sex slaves. They coerce kidnapped females into pregnancy and childbirth and extract the victims' breast milk for the wealthy in Myanmar to consume, and produce luxury skincare products. They turn the newborns of these victims into sources for illegal organ harvesting. Concurrently, they are also making more and more victims into living organ donors. After organ extraction, they bury the victims alive or slaughter them.</p> <p>Therefore, any resident or national of the criminal country Myanmar, and any suspected criminal and their family members (including direct family members) must publicly and permanently disclose any property they hold in any country. Anyone who has resided in Myanmar for over a month, or who holds dual citizenship with Myanmar (excluding staff of embassies of other countries in Myanmar), must permanently publicly disclose all their personal and family assets to everyone globally. Every bank around the globe must publicize all assets and detailed listings and accounts of Burmese people, their family members, and those holding Myanmar nationality or dual nationality with Myanmar, including a detailed record of asset growth or decrease over the past 30 years, to help curb fraud and the transfer of fraudulent funds. All account details must be publicly available on the internet for anyone to review. Any</p>

	<p>assets suspected to be illegal by law enforcement officials from the United Nations, the United States, China, or the affected countries must be clarified within 48 hours. In addition, everyone in other countries where similar large-scale cases have occurred and their families, regardless of whether their spouses are Burmese, must publicly disclose all their property and bank assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
14	<p>The disclosure of assets by officials is a sign of societal progress, while the anonymity provided by cryptocurrencies encourages the safe transfer of illegal funds by criminals. A global consensus must be reached to permanently ban the use of cryptocurrencies by all residents of criminal states such as Myanmar, any individuals under suspicion of criminal activity, their family members (including direct relatives), nationals, persons with dual Myanmar nationality, and anyone within Myanmar's territory. Anyone who has made transfers or payments in excess of \$5,000 using cryptocurrencies in the past must provide the name and details of the person involved in the transfer.</p>
15	<p>Any criminal or suspect who has committed a crime in conjunction with a resident of the criminal state of Myanmar must permanently disclose all personal and family property in any country (including direct family members). Every bank worldwide must publicize all assets, detailed listings, and accounts held by the offender or suspect, along with a record of the increase or decrease in assets over the past 30 years. All details must be displayed on the internet and accessible for anyone to view.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
16	<p>Reward system: The victim country should first transfer the compensation received from the offender and the offending country to the victims. The compensation received by the victim country will then be proportionally distributed as rewards to global peace warriors who assist in upholding justice, as well as to all other countries and the United Nations that make claims against the offending country. The remaining 50% will be rewarded to the global leading countries that support and lead the claim, for example, if the leading country is the United States, then the reward will be given to the United States. If the criminal country compensates the victims and the affected country in the form of permanent land transfer, 0.7-1% of the annual fiscal income generated by the region over the next 30 years will be awarded as a bonus to the lead claimant. if the United States is the country leading the claim, then the bonus will be awarded to the United States. Other problems in dealing with the crimes of the offending country have also led to the permanent transfer of land to the affected country, and the same provisions for rewarding the leading country as mentioned above apply.</p>

	Only by adequately rewarding countries that lead the fight against malignant criminal nations, can the world sustain peace.
17	<p>In Chinese history, there has never been such a large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, organ harvesting, and massacre of civilians by criminals within another country's jurisdiction during peacetime. This is a major regression in human ethics and law. Despite a significant increase in the number of government officials worldwide, the number of graduates and doctors in political science, philosophy, management, and law far exceeds that of ancient China. In ancient China, once such large-scale crimes occurred, officials would either be dismissed or executed if they failed to resolve the situation within a specific time frame, allowing more capable officials to govern the country and the world. Today, the United Nations, to some extent, resembles a salaried organization that fails to demonstrate any strong emergency response and coordination capabilities in combating criminals and their host countries. Therefore, it is necessary to establish the necessary punitive measures for officials.</p> <p>Any city, county or region in any country with a population of one million or less, if it experiences 6 cases of missing or abducted children, 6 cases of adult kidnapping, human trafficking, 30 cases of torture, 20 cases of rape or gang rape, 3 cases of organ harvesting within a year, the officials in charge of the city, county or region's security work as well as the officials directly responsible must be dismissed. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least three levels. For more populous counties, cities, or regions, penalty rules are calculated proportionally based on their population. If the number of victims in any of the categories exceeds three times the aforementioned quantities, county, city, or regional chiefs, security chiefs, and the head of the police department must be dismissed. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least five levels, and their legal responsibilities must be pursued. Cases that are promptly stopped are not included in punitive statistics.</p>
18	In ancient China, unless there were special considerations, all criminals had to be publicly displayed during their detention and transportation. They had to march in the streets to make the public fully aware of their appearance in order to deter criminals, increase public awareness of precautions, and deter those who were considering committing crimes but had not yet done so. Clearly, the current relevant legal provisions are completely misguided and must be corrected, returning to the correct practices of the past. Any criminal must show their face during escort, trial, or public activities, and must not wear any head covering or mask, to publicly display his or her crimes. This deters existing and future criminals, facilitates public recognition of offenders, and also enhances the public's sense of justice.
19	In the course of a crime, if a perpetrator, criminal organization or criminal State destroys any evidence, the seriousness of the crime will no longer be determined by the evidence provided by the perpetrator but by the victim State and the victims themselves. Any record provided by the criminal or criminal

	country about large-scale massacres must be considered from the starting point of the plan, or it will be considered destruction of evidence. Anyone who directly or indirectly orders the destruction of evidence, and those who carry it out, can be subjected to severe punishment, and must be severely punished for crimes against humanity.
20	Any righteous organization has the right to combat, in any manner, the criminal members, criminal organizations, and their protectors within countries that commit large-scale crimes like Myanmar and protectors of massive crimes. Any country or individual has the freedom to provide any kind of weaponry or equipment until the criminals and their organizations are eliminated.
21	All Burmese politicians or military officers and members of their families or descendants who have contributed to Myanmar's grave criminal situation by disregarding the Panglong Agreement are prohibited from engaging in government, military, police, intelligence, judicial, media, or financial industries, and cannot hold government positions. They are permanently banned from running for any parliamentary, presidential or government office. They are also permanently prohibited from running for or holding any leadership positions in any non-governmental organization.
22	Any criminal state as defined by this agreement will be stripped of its voting rights in international judicial institutions for 100 years.
23	Any criminal state as defined by this agreement will lose its voting rights in any international organization, including the United Nations, for 100 years.
24	Any criminals or their descendants who are involved in the crimes stipulated in this agreement will be permanently barred from holding positions such as Chief Justice, Deputy Chief Justice, Supreme Court Jury, Prosecutor General, Deputy Prosecutor General, members of the Public Prosecutor Committee, Chief Prosecutor, Prosecutor, and Senior Prosecutor of the Supreme Court.
25	Any criminal or their descendants who are involved in the crimes stipulated in this agreement will be forever prohibited from holding any formal or informal position in any international judicial institution or in the United Nations.
26	Prior to signing a compensation agreement with the victimized country and paying all agreed compensation in accordance with the agreement, no country, institution or enterprise may engage in investment activities in the criminal State. They must not violate ethical principles by constructing any infrastructure for the criminal nation, including roads, railways, or ports, without considering the still-grieving victims.
27	After the signing of this consensus, or following the formation of a governmental consensus by the United Nations or after a declaration by the United Nations, any country where large-scale crimes such as fraud, kidnapping, torture and forced organ harvesting, and human trafficking have been committed since 1950 and have yet to be held accountable, must sign the first compensation agreement with the victim country and the victims within six months, and it must be implemented immediately. If the compensation plan does not begin to be implemented, all investment or construction of

	infrastructure in the criminal State by the countries that have signed this consensus must be immediately and completely halted.
28	Any country that refuses to sign this agreement should be considered as intending to instigate or protect future large-scale fraudulent behavior, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, torture, forced organ harvesting, and human trafficking.
25	Criminals from the offending country and their descendants, or their companies, should be completely and permanently barred from controlling any company in any countries outside their own through investment or economic activities.
26	A comprehensive and permanent ban should be enforced on criminals, their descendants, their companies, subsidiaries or their overseas counterparts from the offending country from leasing or purchasing land in any country.
27	There should be a complete and permanent prohibition on the criminal nation or its citizens, descendants, companies, affiliates, or overseas fellows from buying land in any country that exceeds 1% of the country's total territory.
28	Trials should be conducted in the victimized countries for criminals and criminal nations. The trials should not be held in the criminal countries. The jury system from the United States should be used, composed of ordinary citizens from the victim countries' territories. There are three specific requirements: First, the jury must be ordinary civilians from the county-level areas of the affected countries. Second, these civilians should not have received higher education. Third, they must hold the nationality of the victim country and have never changed their nationality. In addition, jury members should be between the ages of 18 and 75, with no age limit for victims. The jury shall consist of 60 persons, with any final punishment measures beyond the compensation and penalties prescribed in this consensus decided by the jury. Multiple prosecutions can be held by multiple victimized countries against the criminal nation and the criminals.
29	In criminal countries where large-scale crimes have occurred, the legal age for marriage must be at least 22 years old for men and at least 20 years old for women in order for them to get married and have children.
30	Any citizen of the criminal nation with a large-scale crime, or their descendants, or the descendants of their companies, or the descendants of any family business with assets or market value exceeding \$100 million, must sell their surplus assets within 15 working days, with priority given to selling to citizens who hold only the nationality of the given country.
31	All rewards and bonuses obtained in the activities of combating the large-scale crimes described in this consensus are exempt from personal income tax and inheritance tax.
32	Once a country or individual is involved in the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, any institution or financial institution must disclose within five working days the funds or assets held by the criminal country, offender or criminal organization, as well as the corresponding list. Any bank, financial institution, individual, or organization that assists the offender or the criminal

	<p>country or relatives of the offender in hiding assets in violation of this consensus, should be fined five times the value of the hidden assets and all personal and family assets of the criminal individual should be confiscated. It only allows to retain the minimum living allowance of that country. Violators and their descendants should be permanently prohibited from engaging in any financial, governmental, legal, police, security, military, or related work.</p>
33	<p>All those who plan, command, implement, and protect the large-scale crimes mentioned in this consensus, either as a criminal nation or as an offender, must stand trial in the victim's country. If a criminal destroys evidence of a crime or conceals the truth of a crime, no evidence of innocence, mitigation, or leniency provided by the criminal themselves or their defense attorney should be considered or accepted. Courts and juries may not believe any statement given by the offender on behalf of themselves or their group for their own interest. These criminals cannot have any defense attorneys and all evidence must be based on evidence provided by the victims or others. No country or region can harbor these types of criminals against humanity. The offender's country of origin or hiding place must hand them over to the victim's country within two weeks. Otherwise, the victim's country or any other country can target and attack the hidden offender, including military strikes.</p>
34	<p>If the offender is confirmed to be hiding in a sheltering country, the costs incurred will be borne by that country. If that country refuses to bear the costs, the United Nations has the right to freeze any assets of that country or its citizens globally. If the offender has destroyed any evidence of the crime or has concealed the facts of the crime, any evidence provided by the offender or defense attorney for acquittal, mitigation, or leniency will not be considered or accepted. If a lawyer mitigates his/her crimes, but it is proven otherwise, it indicates that the lawyer has lost the basic human rights standards, moral bottom line, and legal bottom line. The attorney and the criminal must at least be sentenced to the same level of crime, if it is the death penalty, the lawyer must be sentenced to death. Courts and juries may not believe any statement made by the offender or his/her interested party for the defense that is beneficial to the offender or his/her group. These offenders cannot be referred to as suspects before trial. Any bribery that results in lenient sentencing or the offender being acquitted will double the offender's liability. Any accountability system is not limited or restricted by time.</p>
35	<p>Any criminal State that fails to adequately compensate victims and their families, as well as the victim country, will be considered barbaric and uncivilized. Countries that have not signed agreements to fully compensate victims and their families, and countries persecuted in genocide, as recognized by victims, will be regarded as barbarous and uncivilized. No country, company, institution, or individual shall build roads, railways, or ports for such a criminal state.</p>
36	<p>Since 1900, any criminal State that has perpetrated any one of the crimes of massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, or harvesting</p>

	<p>live organs against the public of another country, cannot serve as a permanent member of the UN or of any regional organization for the next thousand years. Any politician from any country who proposes such a country will automatically be regarded as evil and without a moral bottom line.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
37	<p>Since 1900, according to this global consensus, any country, its descendants, or overseas descendants of those with citizenship who participated in mass killings, cannot own global media with the potential to influence other countries. If they currently hold these rights, the media control rights of other countries must be sold to other ethnic groups in that country, with priority given to ethnic groups of victims of mass killings. This transaction must be completed within three months. This provision should form a consensus among the governments of various countries and become part of the UN Declaration.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
40	<p>Provisions for the defense, trial, conviction, identification and compensation of offenders committing massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, or harvesting live organs should be incorporated into the criminal laws of each country according to this global consensus. Each UN contracting country should amend their national or regional laws within six months after formally forming a government consensus.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
41	<p>If the number of victims exceeds 50,000, at any time, the victim country can station troops in the offending State, with all costs incurred by the troop-contributing State borne by the offending State. This offending country must provide available specialized ports and airports, equipped with 10,000 to 100,000 troops. If there are multiple victim countries, troops are allocated according to the number of victims in each country. The location of the stationed troops is designated by the country of the victims. If the stationed troops are threatened, they can take any action. Any actions of the stationed troops are not</p>

	<p>bound by the laws of the criminal country, but only by the laws of the victim country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
42	<p>All personal and family property of the criminals involved in this consensus, as well as the property of relatives or illegitimate children sponsored by the criminals, must be confiscated and compensated to the victims.</p>
43	<p>Any medical personnel involved in forced organ harvesting and illegal use, once found participating in such illegal activities, their professional qualifications shall be immediately terminated, and their descendants shall forever be forbidden from engaging in the medical profession, becoming civil servants, government officials, judicial professionals, or military personnel.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
44	<p>Even if the offender involved in this consensus is deceased, all of his or her personal and family assets must be confiscated and compensated to the victims, whether transferred to their relatives, spouses, descendants, illegitimate children, or lovers.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
45	<p>If a county or region with a population of up to 5 million people experiences a case of missing children or adults, human trafficking, organ harvesting, or death, and at least 100,000 people believe the outcome is unjust and the public widely suspects the investigative process or results of the police, and the police themselves cannot resolve the issue, as long as three countries among the top 50 in global GDP raise objections, the police of the country where the incident occurred should invite law enforcement personnel from those three countries to participate in the investigation within three days. Each country will send four representatives, and all expenses will be borne by the country where the incident occurred. The third country and the victim's family members will have access to all case materials.</p> <p>If a county or region experiences cases of missing or abducted children or adults, organ harvesting, or death, and the public widely suspects the investigation process or outcome of the police, and the police themselves are unable to resolve it, with at least 50,000 people believing that the outcome of the case is unjust, as long as three countries in the top 50 in the world GDP rankings raise objections, the law enforcement authorities of the country where the incident occurred should invite three law enforcement personnel from each of the three countries to participate in the investigation of the case within three days. The costs will be borne by the country where the incident occurred, and both the third country and the families involved should have access to all case-</p>

	<p>related information.</p> <p>The country where the incident occurred must provide all conveniences to allow police officers from three countries to arrive in that country within the next three days. The country where the incident occurred must take all measures to protect the health and safety of relevant personnel.</p>
46	<p>Anyone who uses internet media or self-media to whitewash criminals or criminal groups or criminal countries engaged in telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, torture, organ harvesting, human trafficking, or massacre, and misleads or deceives the public, if found, after being pointed out twice or warned twice, continues the aforementioned acts, will be treated as participating in all the aforementioned criminal activities along with the whitewashed criminals. Judicial institutions must calculate and punish the crimes committed by them cumulatively.</p>
47	<p>Any county or region with a population of 5-10 million, including Myanmar, that experiences 5 cases of child abduction or trafficking, 300 cases of telecommunication fraud, 8 cases of kidnapping, disappearance or trafficking in persons, torture, gang rape, or illegal harvesting of organs within a year. The person responsible, the head of security, and the police chief of that county or region must be removed from their posts. After dismissal, their official position must be demoted by at least three levels, and officials must be held legally accountable. For counties or regions with larger populations, punishment rules shall be calculated proportionally. Cases that are promptly stopped are not included in punitive statistics.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
48	<p>Any county or region with a population of 1-5 million in any country, including Myanmar, within 2 years, if there are at least 12 cases of abduction or trafficking of children, 300 cases of telecommunication fraud, 12 cases of population kidnapping, disappearance, or trafficking, 5 cases of organ harvesting, where at least 80% of the major criminals cannot be captured, the main responsible person, the main person in charge of security work, and the police chief of the county or region must be removed from their positions. After dismissal, their official positions must be demoted by at least three levels, and the legal responsibilities of the officials must be pursued. For counties or regions with larger populations, sentencing rules shall be calculated proportionally.</p>
49	<p>If belated justice is considered justice, then what about evil? In fact, what we are largely lacking is not belated justice, but justice in the present moment. What is justice in the present moment? Justifiable self-defense is justice in the present moment. If justice cannot be served in the present, it lacks courage and true justice. If justice always arrives late, how can justice in the present be tolerated? Where do we begin to ensure security for individuals, children, women, and families, peace in the world, and continuous global harmony?</p> <p>What we lack most today is justice in the present, and yet, we are required</p>

	<p>to pay an excessive cost, even at the expense of the victims' lives. The entire society ignores the devastating harm inflicted on victims and their families by those who implement and establish the legal system, yet they do not take any responsibility or face any punishment. The legal system itself is severely lagging behind in its response to heinous crimes. In Myanmar, there are large-scale incidents of kidnapping, rape, gang rape, torture, organ harvesting, and massacre occurring every year. Where is justice from the International Court of Justice in The Hague? Where are the judges who uphold justice in the International Court of Justice? How long have they been asleep? Do they still receive salaries? In ancient China, judges who did not perform their duties were imprisoned or executed. You are law enforcement officers, and you should have a better understanding of the law than ordinary people. Shouldn't you be the first to be punished?</p> <p>Therefore, any urgent defenses and further action against the criminals involved in this consensus are justified. This includes any urgent action taken by those who show bravery in the face of righteousness. These actions should be commended and considered innocent. Regardless of the age of the offender, as long as they commit crimes, they are criminals. Even if they are still minors, they are still criminals, and their guardians are equally guilty. All the provisions of this consensus can be applied to punish their crimes. No judiciary in any country can deem the defensive actions of those involved in this consensus as guilty. Otherwise, if such law enforcement judgments occur, the relevant law enforcement personnel and lawyers can no longer engage in any law enforcement work. Criminals are the minority, and only by cracking down on and eliminating minority criminals can the security of the vast majority of good people be ensured.</p>
50	<p>In any country, should a telecommunication fraud hub emerge and is not dismantled within a month after being established, legal responsibility must be pursued against the leaders of that region and the judicial bodies. Those at the management level of the aforementioned institutions must be relieved of their posts immediately. The individuals concerned and their descendants shall be prohibited from holding any public service or government position, as well as from joining the military, the police, the security forces or similar organizations, whether on a permanent or temporary basis, and they shall be barred from working in the financial and economic sectors.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
51	<p>It is prohibited for any country or region that has ever been involved in crimes related to large-scale public consensus to operate offline or online gambling businesses or gambling venues. Violators should be sentenced to at least ten years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become</p>

	powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.
52	<p>Any country that refuses to sign this Consensus or Convention will be considered as a country attempting to commit or protect massive fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, or organ harvesting crimes, and plunder the wealth of victims.</p> <p>Any country opposing the core terms of this consensus or convention will be considered a country that disrupts the international moral order and crimes against humanity.</p> <p>Any politician opposing the core terms of this agreement or convention will be considered a politician who disrupts the international moral order and is against humanity.</p> <p>Any politician who opposes the core provisions of the agreement or convention that prevent the country from signing should force himself, his wife, son and daughter to experience the torture inflicted by all criminals in Myanmar for six months.</p>
53	<p>The offending nation must categorize and submit all factual evidences of crimes to the victim nation and to the United Nations, so that the victim nation can adopt theories and methods of metrological political party ethics, metrological administrative or governmental ethics, metrological judicial ethics, and metrological war ethics for a quantitative ethical assessment of the examples of the ruling party, government, judicial institutions, and military of the offending nation in the process of committing and protecting crimes.</p>
54	<p>Anyone applying for a public service role or running for office as a legislator , president or prime minister must possess good will, high moral character, a spirit of dedication, a sense of justice, and empathy and compassion. Those who have participated in the crimes mentioned in this consensus are not eligible to apply for or run for these positions.</p> <p>Any candidate for a civil service position must have at least five years of experience working at the grass-roots level. Graduates of elementary, secondary or tertiary education institutions, regardless of their level of academic qualifications, cannot directly apply for public service positions upon graduation. They must have at least five years or more of grassroots work experience.</p> <p>Anyone running for a legislative position must not only have five years or more of grassroots work experience, but must also have at least one year of front-line work experience in agriculture, manufacturing, or mining. Individuals vying for the office of President or Prime Minister, in addition to meeting the criteria for legislative candidates, must have served for at least five years in at least two positions at the level of governor, mayor, or minister at the city, state, or national level. Even if a candidate is a prodigy, they must still have at least five years or more of grassroots public service experience, at least one year of front-line work experience in agriculture, manufacturing, or mining, and have worked in at least three different positions with a minimum of one year in each position, and have distinguished records of accomplishment in their field of work.</p>

	<p>In particular, the basic premise for the recruitment of patent examiners by the National Intellectual Property Administration is that the candidate must have at least 6-10 years of professional practical work experience, and have logical identity thinking.</p>
55	<p>In the countries of the offenders involved in this consensus or convention, anyone running for a legislative position or the role of the President, Prime Minister, Speaker of the Senate, Speaker of the House of Representatives, or Governor, after being elected, if within 1-3 months of taking office, their main concepts of governance or solutions to major issues do not mostly align with the measures, goals or slogans proposed during their election campaign, and this inconsistency provokes public protest, they will be automatically dismissed from the position as soon as evidences are provided. The dismissed individual must leave the position within two days and ensure a smooth transition.</p> <p>Similarly, anyone who is elected as a legislator, the President, Prime Minister, Speaker of the Senate, Speaker of the House of Representatives, or Governor, if within the first year of their tenure their main governing concepts or solutions to major issues are not mostly consistent with what they proposed during their campaign, as long as someone can provide proof, the legislator, prime minister, or president will automatically lose their position. Those dismissed must leave their posts within three days and ensure a smooth transition.</p> <p>In order to prevent those who are incompetent yet eager to seize power from taking control of national or local governments, anyone who, for the aforementioned reasons, causes significant damage to the assets of the State or the public, such as the President, Prime Minister, Speaker of the Senate, Speaker of the House of Representatives, or Governor, shall bear not only moral responsibility, but shall also forfeit all personal assets to the State. They will only be allowed to maintain a basic living allowance sufficient for five years, calculated on the basis of the country's average standard.</p>
56	<p>In countries with a population exceeding 30 million, which have carried out or protected large-scale telecommunication fraud, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, torture, live organ harvesting, massacres, and other crimes, the number of their military and police personnel, including self-defense forces, is prohibited from exceeding 100,000. In countries with a population of less than 30 million, the number of personnel in the aforementioned institutions is prohibited from exceeding 80,000.</p>
57	<p>Any state-owned or private construction company engaged in building houses may not establish multiple firms; it can only own one company. All contracts must be signed under that company's name, and it is forbidden to set up a separate company for each real estate project. All contract projects are subject to lifelong accountability.</p> <p>In all residential, commercial, or industrial buildings constructed of concrete by the company, the names of the persons responsible for construction, development, and construction must be permanently marked in an appropriate location on the concrete walls of the building. If an individual is running or</p>

	<p>stomping in a room with closed doors and windows in the building, no noise should be heard in the rooms below; failure to meet this standard considers the building unqualified. The company and the developers must not only compensate the purchasers, but also take on legal responsibility. The main individuals responsible should face a minimum prison sentence of 8 to 15 years.</p> <p>The area of all houses can only be calculated on the basis of the usable area; it is forbidden to calculate their value and market them using the built-up area.</p> <p>Real estate companies are only allowed to take out loans through the parent company; it is forbidden to obtain loans through any subsidiaries or branches. If loans have already been taken out through subsidiaries or branches, all such loans must be accounted for under the parent company in terms of financial handling. Any financial audit conducted on the company must adhere to the above principle, otherwise the audit firm shall bear full responsibility.</p> <p>This clause must be implemented in all countries of the world.</p>
58	The government of the country must organize military and police forces to destroy the graves and tombstones of all evil war criminals and criminals from World War II within half a month, leaving no trace.
59	The country must select 2% of its civil servants who are of high moral character and possess certain professional abilities from the cohort about to retire each year, to continue serving in the civil service positions. They are to continue working until the age of 68 or 70, provided that the individual voluntarily chooses to defer retirement age.
60	Life is about quality and health, not necessarily length. Prevention leads to health, as does the choice of appropriate treatment methods in the early stages of illness. The vast majority of organ transplants can be avoided. The country must legislate to prohibit organ transplants and any harvesting of human organs.
61	If any act of reporting a crime is verified by the judicial authorities to constitute false testimony, even if the wronged party does not sue the false accuser, the relevant government departments must prosecute the offender within six months of the judicial authority's determination. Court proceedings must be public, and at least twenty unrelated media must be allowed to attend the entire process. Except for leaving one year's worth of basic living expenses, all personal property of the person providing false testimony will be confiscated by the State treasury. The State will additionally award 15% of the value of confiscated property to the person who was wrongfully accused within one year. If a just person provides evidence proving the act of false reporting, the State will award them 10% of the value of the confiscated property within one year. Anyone who encourages others to make false reports will have one-third of their personal property confiscated to the state treasury. All reviewers, judicial personnel, and lawyers on both sides must disclose their personal and family assets, including those of illegitimate children. The personal and family assets of the false witness and his accomplices, as well as the assets of illegitimate children, must be fully disclosed.
62	No government official can make mistakes without facing consequences, as this

	<p>would hinder the fair promotion and reward of well-meaning, talented, just, empathetic, and compassionate government staff. This includes all public servants and staff of government agencies, such as the National Intellectual Property Administration. Those who do not comply with laws, industry standards, the laws of logic, misuse their authority, or violate administrative ethics must face disqualification if they receive five complaints in any consecutive three-year period. They should not be re-employed in similar positions for eight years, and should not be promoted if transferred to other positions. Those who cause significant damage through their actions should be dismissed within three months.</p> <p>Any time a complaint is substantiated, it must be announced within a month to all personnel within the entire national government system, the judiciary, and regulatory bodies, disclosing statistics of all substantiated complaints regarding non-compliance with the above-mentioned rules, logic, and administrative ethics within that system.</p>
63	<p>All sports agents, especially those in the soccer industry where there have been significant instances of bribery causing public and fan outrage, must publicly disclose their personal and family assets. Sports agents are obligated to disclose all their assets, including those of their families. For every athlete transfer, the direction of commission payments, especially funds to third or fourth parties, must be clearly explained and permanently displayed on the sports government website of their home country. If a club or sports organization is responsible for transferring the commission, both the transferring and receiving parties must declare whether there are multiple beneficiaries of the commission and make the flow of funds public. Any fraudulent behavior will result in all commissions being forfeited to the State treasury, accompanied by a fine of five times the amount. If the athlete is aware of the situation and still proceeds with the transaction, any profits gained by the athlete as a result will be forfeited to the national treasury, and a fine equal to three times the amount of the profit will be imposed. Anyone who commits perjury will have their entire personal property confiscated and turned over to the state treasury.</p>
64	<p>All vehicles transporting agricultural products in bulk, including all vegetables, fruits, sweet potatoes, or purple potatoes, etc., shall pass through any highway toll-free. No organization or individual may charge a fee for any reason. Anyone who insists on conducting a full inspection of all goods, or demands unboxing or unloading for inspection before allowing passage, provided that no prior checkpoint has done so, and it turns out that the vehicle is indeed carrying agricultural products, the inspection personnel involved at that toll booth must be fired within 24 hours, and the person in charge of their unit must be demoted. All personnel at that highway toll booth (including fired individuals) and those in their supervising units must publicly disclose all personal and family assets within one week. For each day of delay, they must be fined according to the city's late tax payment model. Should the transporter suffer any loss, such as a delay in reaching the destination or damage to the packaging of agricultural</p>

	<p>products, the highway toll booth must compensate the driver and the owner of the goods twice the amount of the loss. This clause must be implemented in all countries of the world.</p>
65	<p>When any government agency in a country develops policies, the initiators, drafters, revisers, and responsible parties must be clearly identified and sign their names. In cases of severe violations of public morals, serious breaches of natural laws, or when major losses occur, the above-mentioned individuals must be held accountable. They must be demoted before they can be employed again, and half of their personal and family assets must be compensated to their nation. The highest-ranking official who signs off on the policy must assume 50% of the responsibility. Their individual and family wealth must be made public. Those who have made mistakes, if they have undergone experience and training and have demonstrated outstanding work performance, should be allowed to advance three ranks in their position.</p>
66	<p>In order to prevent officials lacking competence from causing losses to the nation, the investments of any state-owned enterprise in any country, unless secrecy is required, should be disclosed to the public after the investment is made; otherwise, they must be permanently disclosed to the public before the investment. This disclosure must include the names of the proposer, initiator, and executor, as well as the individuals responsible for each specific part of the project. In the event of significant losses, the above-mentioned individuals must bear responsibility. They must be demoted in order to continue their service, and half of their personal and family assets must be compensated to the state to which they belong. The highest-ranking official who signs off on the investment must bear 70% of the responsibility. Their individual and family wealth must be made public. Those who have made mistakes, if they have undergone experience and training and have demonstrated outstanding work performance, should be allowed to advance three ranks in their position.</p>
67	<p>Imposing taxes on basic family housing leads to a situation where families without money can only become homeless, which is in conflict with the universally acknowledged rights to freedom and human rights; it constitutes an act of intellectual fraud and plunder of property. All countries must exempt basic family housing from property taxes in order to ensure the global realization of universal values.</p>
68	<p>No charitable foundation or trust fund can be used for tax evasion, including evasion of personal income tax and estate tax. The administrative costs of any charitable foundation cannot exceed 4%. For every 1% exceeded, the benefit manager and beneficiaries must face a penalty of three times the excess amount. Individual and family wealth must be made public. In any country implementing this provision, the personal income tax and corporate income tax rates cannot exceed 25%, and the estate tax rate must not be higher than 33%. The global minimum threshold for estate tax should be at least \$ 8 million, and all countries around the world must impose a tax rate for change of nationality.</p>

69	<p>Farmers must not be prohibited from breeding their own poultry, pigs, cattle, and sheep for any reason. Slaughtering and selling small numbers of livestock raised by farmers must not be prohibited, unless the animals are sick. Anyone who enacts legislation to prohibit this must publicly disclose all personal assets and family wealth, as well as the assets of their immediate family members! Investigate retroactively for 30 years. The above terms apply to any country.</p> <p>The United Nations, together with the World Health Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, should consider this strategy as one of the approaches to tackle the challenging issue of reducing the current global rural poverty, increasing the availability of healthy ecological food and increasing farmers' incomes.</p>
70	<p>No one may, for any reason whatsoever, violate the millennia-old traditions of Asia, the customs of European residents and farmers, prohibiting farmers from burning grass and wood for heating and cooking, and maintaining daily life. Anyone who enacts legislation to prohibit this must publicly disclose all personal assets, family wealth, and assets of their immediate family members! Investigate retroactively for 30 years. Those who have already enacted such legislation must not be allowed to engage in legislative work in the future unless they have lived in the homes of firewood farmers in Europe and Asia for more than a year. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
71	<p>Fraudulent practices of counterfeit meat products are often seen in modern society, such as passing off horse meat or other meats like beef, using artificial synthetic meat as fresh meat, or labeling chicken as pork. There are even cases where low-quality minced meat is sold as normal fresh meat, or meat with viruses is ground up and sold as normal meat. It is suggested that the United Nations develop a relevant convention for the control of such criminal conduct: First, once verified, severe penalties will be imposed. Offenders will be fined five times the value of product fraud, banned from the industry for 20 years, and required to disclose all personal and family assets.</p> <p>Second, the names, photos, and specific details of the falsification of offenders will be publicly displayed on government websites for 10 years, and this information may not be deleted during this period.</p> <p>Third, first-time offenders will be criminally detained; repeat offenders will have all their personal property confiscated.</p> <p>Fourth, if the value of illegal meat exceeds 1 million, a prison sentence of 2-6 years will be imposed; fifth, offenders must be subject to travel restrictions, report to the police station when leaving their place of residence, and being prohibited from flying or taking high-speed trains.</p> <p>Sixth, the offender will be blacklisted for life, and all family members and relatives will be banned from entering the civil service system for life.</p> <p>Seventh, anyone who reports the fraudulent sale of other types of meat as meat or meat of inferior quality, once verified, will be rewarded with 25% of the offender's confiscated property. Eighth, the offender and all family members will be banned from entering public universities for 100 years.</p>

	<p>Ninth, anyone who grinds meat with viruses and sells it as normal meat, their family members and relatives will be banned from enjoying compulsory education and medical insurance services for 100 years.</p> <p>Tenth, any country or region where such incidents occur must inform every citizen of the provisions of this Convention through various fast communication or dissemination methods, at least once a week.</p>
72	<p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>Any financial institution or individual that lends money to enterprises and individuals at an annual interest rate exceeding 5% shall ensure that all expenses incurred in the loan process, including fees paid to third parties, do not result in an effective annual interest rate exceeding 5%. If exceeded, such charges cannot be considered legal, but rather as illegal income. Moreover, a penalty based on the loan amount shall be imposed, with confiscation of 20-30% of the principal. If the cumulative costs correspond to an effective annual interest rate exceeding 7%, the offender must face criminal charges and be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison. The above terms apply to any country.</p> <p>Usury, under the guise of high interest rates, erodes social stability like a plague, bringing misfortune to people's livelihoods. It not only devours the wealth of borrowers, but also pushes vulnerable individuals to desperation, leading to the breakup of families and the destruction of futures. Under the burden of excessive debt, victims often fall into the abyss of illegality, increasing crime rates and endangering public safety. It strays from the purpose of legitimate financial services, undermines normal economic order, and harms the interests of the disadvantaged majority. The United Nations should formulate a convention urging governments worldwide to crack down vigorously on usurious practices, protect citizens from their harm and maintain social harmony and stability. Advocating legal lending practices ensures the fair and orderly flow of wealth, bringing well-being to people.</p>
73	<p>In 2019, the average profit margin of small businesses in the United States was 7% -10%, and only 40% of small businesses were profitable.</p> <p>Anyone who adds talcum powder, alum, any illegal chemical additives, or excessive additives to flour or rice flour products shall be fined an amount five times the fraudulent value by the regulatory authorities. Similar to meat fraudsters, they will have their personal and family assets publicly disclosed, be prohibited from working in the industry for 20 years, and their name, photo, and details of fraudulence publicly displayed on a government website for 20 years, which must not be removed for any reason. If the fraudulent amount exceeds \$1 million, they must also be listed as controlled individuals when it comes to travel. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
74	<p>Any intermediary company, especially those in e-commerce, providing intermediary services for the products and commercial activities of other companies, can only charge a maximum of 20% of the transaction amount as intermediary fees or commissions within the first 18 months of its</p>

	<p>establishment, or if the sales volume of intermediary products is less than 20 million US dollars. Once either of these two milestones is exceeded, the intermediary or e-commerce company may only charge up to 15% in intermediary fees. If this limit is exceeded, it is considered illegal, and regulatory authorities must fine the violator ten times the amount illegally charged. If a company changes its name, but retains 30% of its workforce from the previous entity, it shall be regarded as the same company by the regulatory bodies, which must then impose harsher penalties. Companies not meeting the above criteria shall not be permitted to list on any exchange.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
75	<p>Any intermediary company, especially e-commerce platforms, that provides mediation services for the goods and commercial activities of other companies must adhere to certain employment and contracting standards after the company has been established for 18 months or after its sales revenue exceeds \$20 million. Employees who are hired or work under contract for such a company are prohibited from being employed through third-party dispatching if their cumulative working time exceeds three months in a six-month period, four months in a twelve-month period, or six months in a twenty-four-month period. In such cases, the company must enter into a direct employment contract with the employee, from whom the salary must be paid directly by the company. The company is also required to pay for the employee's pension insurance and health insurance at the same standard as its other employees. If these conditions are not met, the government must impose a fine on the company amounting to five times the total salary and bonuses paid to the illegally employed worker. If the offence is repeated, the person in charge of the company shall be subject to criminal punishment, with a sentence of two to three years' imprisonment. Companies that do not meet the above criteria should not be allowed to list on any stock exchange.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
76	<p>When any company is listed on a stock exchange, if the company has not been profitable for two consecutive years, any stock account with account funds less than \$100,000 is not allowed to trade the company's stock. Only after the company has been profitable for two consecutive years can the top 30 shareholders who hold the company's shares start selling their shares in the company. Otherwise, the top 30 shareholders who hold the company's shares, as well as any of their affiliated shareholders, are prohibited from cashing out by selling their shares in the company. Any fraudulent profit-driven trading will result in the confiscation of all income from the transactions by the offending shareholder and any of its affiliated shareholders, and the offenders will be subject to a penalty of three times the amount. The government must impose a prison sentence of 10-20 years on the perpetrators of such fraud.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
77	<p>After any company is listed on the stock exchange, fabricating profits or sales revenue and causing fluctuations in stock prices, the forgers will have all the</p>

	<p>income involved confiscated and face a fine of three times the amount. Both the forgers and the company must reimburse traders for all losses incurred, and the company will be delisted within 3 months. Forgers will be sentenced to 20-30 years in prison.</p> <p>Any company that fabricates profits or sales revenue to get listed on the stock exchange will have all revenues generated through such fraud confiscated, and both the forgers and the company are required to compensate the traders for all losses. The company will be delisted within 3 months. Forgers faces 20-30 years in prison.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
78	<p>Any organization that hires employees must, upon accumulation of work exceeding six months in one year or ten months in two years, be prohibited from employing the individual under a third-party labor dispatch model. Instead, the organization must enter into a direct hiring contract with the employee, where the salary is paid directly by the organization. In addition, the organization is required to contribute to the employee's pension insurance, medical insurance, and other expenses in the same manner as it does for other employees. Failure to comply will result in the government imposing a fine on the organization equivalent to five times the total amount of wages and bonuses paid for the illegal employment of the worker. If the offence is repeated a second time, the person in charge of the organization must face criminal penalties with a prison sentence of 2-3 years.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
79	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any act of illegally demolishing another person's lawfully owned house is a grave crime similar to that of a bandit. The mastermind who commands the demolition, the main perpetrators, and the decision-makers behind the scenes must be sentenced to death, while the remaining criminals must be sentenced to more than 10 years in prison.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
80	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology</p>

	<p>of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any institution or individual providing loans to students during their studies (including those pursuing master's or doctoral degrees) must not charge an annual interest rate exceeding 3%, or it will be considered illegal. Penalties based on the loan amount should be enforced, with the government confiscating 20-40% of the principal. If the full fee equals an effective annual interest rate over 5%, the offender must face criminal prosecution and be sentenced to 2-5 years of imprisonment. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
81	<p>Individuals who impersonate others to attend university bring lifelong harm to their victims and must therefore face the death penalty. All those involved in the forgery must have all their personal and family assets confiscated and receive a minimum sentence of 10 years in prison, with the principal offenders sentenced to death. None shall be granted bail. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
82	<p>Individuals impersonating others and taking over positions may harm victims for life. All those involved in forgery shall have their personal and family property confiscated. For each year that the disclosure of the criminal facts is delayed, all offenders must be sentenced to at least one year of imprisonment, with the principal offender's sentence being doubled. No one may be granted bail. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
83	<p>The United Nations should establish a dedicated website within five months to enable all city and state governments worldwide to disclose on the website the crime counts, population numbers, and crime rates for each month for their respective cities and states. All cities are required to truthfully report the basic details of specific cases, especially for crimes such as telecommunications fraud, robbery, rape, gang rape, massacre, torture, and additional similar crimes. If any case is intentionally omitted, a penalty equivalent to one criminal record will be imposed. The aforementioned website must allow netizens or victims to directly add omitted cases, including theft and other incidents. The United Nations must also establish a dedicated website within five months where the global public can upload instances of government inaction in their areas, record cases of politicians deceiving the public, so that anyone can measure the level of civilization in that region and the governing capacity of governments and political parties using metrological political ethics, metrological governmental ethics, metrological administrative ethics, metrological political party ethics, and metrological legal ethics .</p>
84	<p>Any criminal involved in this consensus who disseminates false information online to whitewash their actions or intentionally muddles the situation, if the number of times they publish such information reaches 20, all of their personal</p>

	and family assets will be confiscated, and all future assets must be fully disclosed.
85	Criminals covered by this consensus must report to the judicial authorities before leaving their place of residence, disclosing their itinerary and purpose.
86	<p>The United Nations should form an international convention on the following issues:</p> <p>The carbon dioxide produced is mainly due to consumer demand, resulting in its production and emissions. Therefore, a country's total carbon emissions should take into account both the CO2 generated by production and that from consumption. For any given product, consumers who import this product should at least share the responsibility for the carbon emissions produced by the manufacturer. Otherwise, consumers should not import the product, but instead produce it themselves, or magically obtain it from air or water. The above terms apply to any country.</p> <p>Consumers and consumer countries that use imported products should at least share responsibility for the carbon emissions produced by manufacturers. Only with this kind of tax system is a carbon emission tax reasonable. If a country does not produce toilet paper and is not willing to pay the carbon consumption tax or carbon emissions tax of the country that produces the product, it is equivalent to the producing country helping the importing country produce the product for free, and even helping them pay taxes. It's no different from the plunder of a robber. The citizens of the consuming country should not use toilet paper to wipe their bottoms, but should find other ways to do so. If a country does not produce food and is not willing to pay a carbon consumption tax, it is as if the producing country is helping the importing country produce food for free, and even helping them pay taxes. The citizens of the consuming country should not eat food, and instead should rely on water to live, and ask God to find a way to turn water molecules into organic food.</p>
87	<p>To truly establish an environmentally friendly society, to reduce carbon emissions and the difficulty of fire rescue, in any city, only 1% of buildings are allowed to exceed 12 stories in height for residential or mixed-use properties, but must not surpass 24 stories. The rest are prohibited from exceeding 12 stories. Any violations will result in the government confiscating all illegal income of the developers, along with a penalty of three times the amount.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
88	<p>To truly establish an environmentally friendly society, reduce carbon emissions, and decrease the difficulty of fire rescues, commercial buildings in any area are prohibited from exceeding 200 meters in height. Should this limit be exceeded, the government will confiscate all illegal income from the developers, in addition to imposing a fine of three times the amount. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
89	<p>Once a cemetery has been legally used for the burial of the deceased, the land permanently belongs to those who have passed away. No one may remove or desecrate the gravesite for any reason, except in cases involving illegal</p>

	<p>activities. The price per square meter for general public cemetery plots must not exceed half of the lowest housing price in the same city or town during the same period. The government must provide sufficient burial grounds for the deceased to rest in peace. The above terms apply to any country.</p>
90	<p>Setting off fireworks and firecrackers is a traditional custom. In ancient times, it was allowed in houses made of wood, but today, in an age of predominantly concrete houses, cities paradoxically prohibit the use of fireworks and firecrackers, which to some extent is illogical. To prevent fires caused by fireworks or injuries from firecrackers with a high powder content, there should be a differentiated management system for the use of fireworks and firecrackers. When cities establish rules prohibiting the use of fireworks and firecrackers, they must distinguish between the types of these items. There may be a need to ban certain fireworks and skyrockets in densely populated urban areas, but no city government should ever prohibit citizens from using firecrackers with the lowest powder content designed before or in the 1980s outside their homes or during ceremonies for festivals, celebrations, or funerals. However, the number of firecrackers per string could be limited to between 100-1,000. The government should not ban the sale of firecrackers in cities, nor should it ban the sale of fireworks and firecrackers in rural areas or towns, as this would effectively destroy traditional customs and suggest that modern governance is less capable than in previous eras.</p> <p>The above terms apply to any country.</p>
91	<p>Citizens of any country, whether they live in urban or rural areas as farmers or peasants, as long as they have paid taxes or performed their civic duties for that nation for three years, the government must unconditionally provide at least the minimum level of health insurance and pension insurance for themselves and their families.</p>
92	<p>No hospital should determine the level of a clinical doctor's professional title based on the writing or publication of papers. Instead, they should measure or evaluate clinicians using humane indicators such as cure rates, improvement rates, and successful resuscitation rates, and determine their professional titles accordingly.</p>
93	<p>In the event of fraudulent marketing practices involving virtual currency, digital currency, token economy, token finance, or token-based tourism economic products, which lead to significant losses for a large number of victims, the harm caused is immense. Principal offenders, masterminds, and key members must fully compensate the victims. If full restitution is not made to the victims, the government must freeze and confiscate all personal assets of the principal offenders, masterminds, key members, and the assets of the companies involved. In addition, they must be fined double the amount of the funds involved to compensate the victims. Those who successfully recruited others to purchase the aforementioned products or currency through a pyramid scheme will only be compensated later. If the amount involved exceeds \$20 million and the principal offenders, masterminds, and key members fail to fully compensate</p>

	<p>the victims, the government must confiscate all personal and family assets of these individuals. If criminals have transferred funds of \$100,000 or more, all their personal assets must be confiscated, with only basic living expenses allowed to remain.</p> <p>After receiving complaints from victims, if the regulatory authority refuses or delays processing them, allowing the scam ring to continue its fraudulent activities, the responsible parties will be held legally accountable. A fine amounting to 5% of the sum involved in the report will be imposed on the responsible individuals, followed by demotion and reassignment. In cases involving collusion in the crime, all personal assets of the individuals will be confiscated and they will be subject to criminal penalties.</p> <p>Anyone who provides image support for such frauds, endorses their activities through promotional speeches, or recommends purchasing or supporting the purchase, including Internet celebrities, stars, government officials, senior members of industry associations, or legal institutions, shall be fined five times the amount of their profits from the case. The positions of any senior management involved in industry associations will be abolished. If the amount involved reaches or exceeds \$20 million, the practising qualifications of the personnel involved from the legal institutions will be revoked for five years, and the legal institution's licence will be revoked. If all major offenders and key members do not fully compensate victims, product spokespersons and those who publicly support them must compensate victims. If someone successfully recruits five or more people to join the purchasing scheme and they incur losses, the government will not provide compensation. The government must confiscate all personal assets of key offenders and key members for victim compensation. If the amount involved reaches or exceeds \$60 million, the government must confiscate all personal and family assets of the principal offenders and key members to compensate the victims, revoke the practising qualifications of the personnel involved from legal institutions for 10 years, and revoke the legal institution's license.</p>
94	<p>Any citizen of a country who illegally extracts funds from the healthcare insurance system, if dependent on government insurance for their livelihood and are caught doing so, must provide full restitution of the amount extracted. Those assisting in the extraction are also required to compensate for the full sum taken. If such incidents occur five times in a year, the involved parties will have their insurance eligibility suspended for one year.</p> <p>If the individual extracting funds is not reliant on government health insurance for their living, both the extractor and the accomplice must repay double the amount of healthcare insurance funds taken. Should this happen three times in a year, their insurance eligibility will be revoked for one year.</p> <p>Any healthcare or pharmaceutical institution that appropriates funds from the healthcare insurance system will face suspension of the insurance eligibility of its legal representative and senior management for two years if the average number of such incidents among all medical staff and pharmaceutical personnel</p>

	reaches three per person within one year.
95	<p>Every country must provide preferential treatment to soldiers who have sacrificed for a just war or who have lost some or all of their labour capacity, as well as their families. If there are any direct blood relatives or siblings in the household, the government must provide the family with a reinforced concrete structure residential unit, with a living area (not the constructed area) of 100-140 square meters, at the same location where the sacrificed or incapacitated servicemember used to reside. If the family of the soldier who has either sacrificed or lost some or all of their labor capabilities owns land and proposes to the government to help build a house on their land, the government must assist the family in constructing a two-story house with a maximum construction area of 140 square meters on their original residential site. The cost of constructing the courtyard outside the house is to be borne by the family itself; for direct descendants of blood relation, regardless of gender, if there are multiple descendants reaching the legal marriageable age, in addition to one who must inherit the house previously provided by the government to their family, the government must provide separate residential units with a living area of 100-120 square meters for each in the county or district where the sacrificial or completely incapacitated individual resided. The minimum acceptance standard for housing stipulates that if the housing is part of an apartment building, movement, jumping or stomping by two people upstairs should not be felt in the rooms downstairs when doors and windows are closed. Militia members who have sacrificed or lost all labour capacity for a just war should receive treatment similar to the aforementioned, with housing area benefits provided at 80% of the above standard area. The Government must unconditionally provide the minimum level of medical and pension insurance for its family members.</p> <p>For the above-mentioned private housing, it is exempt from taxes for life, and it must not be sold or traded within 30 years.</p> <p>Soldiers who commit rape or take part in mass rape of women during warfare shall not be entitled to the benefits mentioned above. Wars where there is large-scale rape or mass sexual violence, massive use of biological or chemical weapons to massacre civilians, or where women from other countries are forcibly conscripted as sex slaves are unjust wars. Armies that are involved in large-scale telecommunication fraud, rape, torture, live organ harvesting, burial alive, or massacres are considered forces that shield evil, and their soldiers do not qualify for such treatment posthumously. Any war waged by an army that illegally attempts to seize land that rightfully belongs to another country or uses fabricated pretexts by a third party to usurp such land is deemed an act of aggression, and its soldiers, living or deceased, are prohibited from receiving such honors.</p> <p>Countries guilty of large-scale crimes mentioned in this clause, including those from the Second World War, must establish online "Walls of Shame," listing all criminals and war criminals for global public viewing. Worshiping these</p>

	<p>criminals and war criminals is prohibited. Any such figures worshipped in temples must be removed within six months. If a country responsible for World War II crimes fails to clear all shrine placements, remains, statues, or inscriptions of war criminals from temples within the stipulated time, and persists without change after half a month of formal protest from another country, any state-owned bank of the protesting nation may legally freeze up to \$5 billion of the offending nation's funds for a duration of 10 years.</p> <p>The names, ages, and hometowns of all soldiers and commanders involved in these heinous wars (including wars initiated by criminals as mentioned in this consensus) must be publicly displayed on the country's shame list, and the aforementioned information must be published in their mother tongue, English, and the language of the victim country. The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
96	<p>Anyone who practices traditional natural healing methods or traditional Chinese medicine (TCM) to treat others, provided that the government of that country does not deny the validity of such practices as unscientific in their country, and provided that such traditions have existed in the country for over 100 years without the requirement of examinations or credentials, may do so legally. As long as the patient voluntarily seeks treatment from the practitioner, or in emergency situations where the practitioner acts to save the life of someone who has fallen ill accidentally, no institution should regard it as illegal medical practice. The practitioner assumes all legal liability incurred in the practice of medicine and must not engage in false advertising. Otherwise, they may be fined an amount equivalent to five times the income generated from false advertising claims as per the victim's pursuit of medical help. The government's health insurance agency will not cover any medical expenses for treatments received under the above-mentioned medical practices. This could ease pressure on the government's health insurance spending.</p>
97	<p>Any individual who exploits virtual finance, virtual economy, digital economy, or token economy to sell products and services, and intentionally causes customers' virtual or online account assets to suddenly disappear, is committing fraud, theft, and plunder. Operators, responsible company executives and legal representatives must each face a fine of 5 to 10 times the amount involved, compensate the victims, and receive a prison sentence of not less than one year. Company owners must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within one week of the incident.</p> <p>This consensus stipulates that any mention of public disclosure of personal or family assets in any clause requires perpetual and real-time disclosure of all such assets.</p>
98	<p>The cremation of a single body requires 10-15 kilograms of diesel fuel, consumes about 25 kilowatt-hours of electricity, and produces pollutants such as nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and toxic mercury vapors that pollute the environment. The carbon dioxide released from burning is</p>

	<p>directly emitted into the air, exacerbating the greenhouse effect. It is estimated that the energy used in a single cremation, from gas and electricity, is equivalent to the energy consumption of a car traveling 800 km. ⁸⁴</p> <p>Dioxin belongs to Category I human carcinogen and is one of the most toxic known carcinogenic compounds in the world, with an LD50 (50% lethal dose) that is a thousand times greater than potassium cyanide. Extremely low doses can be harmful to living organisms. Its primary toxicities include reproductive toxicity, neurotoxicity, immunosuppression, endocrine disruption, and it can also cause feminization in males.</p> <p>Cremation produces a significant amount of toxic mercury vapor. Contact with mercury and its compounds can lead to contact dermatitis, a hypersensitivity reaction. Mercury vapor can cause neuropsychiatric symptoms that may begin with dizziness, headache, insomnia, and vivid dreams, followed by emotional agitation or depression, anxiety, timidity, and vegetative nervous system dysfunction.</p> <p>Dioxins are difficult to degrade, and past literature has shown that the areas surrounding some crematoriums indeed have higher concentrations of dioxins, as well as high levels of heavy metals. The United Nations should establish regulations requiring countries to phase out cremation gradually within 5-10 years, unless the tradition of cremation in that region dates back more than 100 years, except in special circumstances. Other areas should not carry out cremation, and starting now, no government agency should prohibit the public from carrying out burials, especially in rural areas. In mountainous areas, burials are prohibited on arable land used for crops such as rice, wheat and corn; instead, burials should take place in mountain forests. Those opting for burial should use coffins made of wood or other natural materials; non-degradable plastic coffins are not allowed. Countries should swiftly enact legislation to support the development of their forestry economies, assist farmers in planting fast-growing forests, and cultivate various precious woods, to meet the needs of customers at different levels, improve employment rates among farmers, develop rural economies, and enhance the standard of living of farmers in mountainous regions.</p> <p>Of course, the public can also adopt eco-friendly burial methods, which include "tree burials," "lawn burials," "flowerbed burials," and other land-conserving ways of handling remains.</p>
99	<p>The United Nations must urgently establish a convention whereby all countries globally must completely ban the use of any chemical substances that do not meet food-grade standards for weed control within 2-4 years. The use of weed control agents that leave residues or are inedible biologics should also be prohibited. It is recommended to adopt ecological cultivation models where weeds coexist with crops, or to use physical methods for weed removal. The United States has advanced non-herbicidal models and mechanical methods for weed control, which could be promoted globally with the influence of the United Nations.</p>

If herbicide manufacturers are unwilling to stop production, they should face the strictest measures or legal cases in the event that any incidences are found related to their product. The top 20 controlling shareholders and corporate legal persons holding shares in herbicide-producing companies will be required to assume legal responsibility.

Grass is a part of the ecosystem in crop growth, much like the extranuclear electrons in atoms within the nucleus of a molecule, whether chemical or philosophical terms. Removing the extranuclear electrons from the nucleus will inevitably produce substances with a high oxidation state similar to positively charged materials. High oxidation state substances lead to accelerated aging of human body cells and will inevitably disrupt the ecological balance of the soil.

Herbicides are highly toxic. Recently, a family in Guangdong Province claimed to have suffered from oral herbicide poisoning. Currently, there is no way to treat the condition, and no one has come forward to help identify the poisoner. A video was released showing the patient in extreme pain (**Fig 80**).⁸⁵

The public has many misconceptions about the presence of weeds in the soil, believing that the appearance of weeds necessitates the use of herbicides. In fact, weeds in the soil can be beneficial to soil quality and crop growth. Weeds play a role in regulating soil moisture and temperature, and they also attract a diverse array of microorganisms. For example, when cotton cloths were buried in an orange grove, there was a significant difference between areas with weeds and those without. The cloth in weedy areas decomposed quickly, while in areas without weeds, the decomposition was much slower (**Fig 81**).⁸⁶

Plants and microorganisms assist each other; the byproducts of photosynthesis are secreted by plant roots into the soil, attracting many microorganisms that feed on these secretions. In turn, microorganisms help dissolve nutrients that have been immobilized in the soil, making them available for plant uptake. Thus, they complement each other. When there are weeds in our orchards, in addition to regulating moisture and temperature, they also help attract various microorganisms that enliven the soil. This significantly enhances the effectiveness of fertilization and can also reduce the incidence of soil-borne diseases, such as root rot. While there can be some issues with weeds, it is important for the public to recognize their benefits (**Fig 81, Fig 82, Fig 83**).⁸⁶

The main hazards of herbicides to human health are as follows:⁸⁷⁻⁹¹

1. Herbicides have been linked to allergies and tumors, two types of autoimmune diseases. The use of herbicides in rural areas has led to a much higher prevalence of tumors compared to the times before their use.
2. Herbicides pose a risk to the cardiovascular system, leading to an increased frequency of cardiovascular diseases.
3. Herbicides have been associated with difficulties becoming pregnant and an increase in miscarriages, stillbirths, and birth defects. In the past, pregnant women would take leave shortly before giving birth, but now there are more cases of miscarriage from simple actions such as sneezing or walking a few steps. This is because many people have been inadvertently consuming

	<p>herbicides since birth.</p> <p>4. Herbicides are associated with a high incidence of childhood leukemia.</p> <p>5. Respiratory system damage: Symptoms such as coughing, expectoration, chest tightness, and cyanosis may occur.</p> <p>6. Digestive system harm: Accidental ingestion of herbicides can cause a burning sensation in the mouth, with erosion or ulcers of mucous membranes in the lips, tongue, pharynx, esophagus, stomach, etc., accompanied by gastrointestinal discomfort such as difficulty swallowing, nausea, vomiting, abdominal pain, diarrhea, etc., as well as vomiting blood, bloody stool, and gastrointestinal perforation.</p>
100	<p>Employees of some unscrupulous investment firms frequently engage in deliberate acts to entice or mislead the public into buying stocks, using phone calls to mislead strangers into joining stock investment groups. They claim to be able to guide stock purchases to achieve high returns or prevent losses. In such cases, the misleaders and their companies must compensate the victims for their total losses. If the loss exceeds \$1,000, the fraudsters and the company will be fined 3 to 5 times the amount of the loss. The personal and family assets of the fraudsters and the company's legal person and upper management must be made public. All persons involved in fraud must be monitored and their movements monitored; leaving the city or place of residence must be reported to the police station. If the amount of fraud exceeds \$1 million, in addition to the aforementioned penalties, the personal and family properties of the fraudsters, as well as the personal and family properties of the legal person and senior management of the fraudulent investment firm, will be confiscated. Additionally, the company's assets will be seized. All senior executives of the company shall be sentenced to at least 5 years' imprisonment.</p> <p>Mobile phone companies are required to obtain real-name registrations of all phone number holders. If not available, upon receipt of any complaint, they must take immediate action. If criminal information cannot be obtained, the use of this number must be suspended. If the offender calls to inquire, they must register with their real identity card to lift the relevant restrictions, thus attaining the true information of the offender. Otherwise, the company continues to be viewed as abetting crime! The person directly responsible and the executive of the company must pay a fine equivalent to their monthly income.</p>
101	<p>Any company that provides educational and training services on the Internet and receives fees must ensure that the subsequent training content they provide is consistent with what the institution or responsible individuals previously claimed. If most or all of the content is inconsistent, it constitutes a serious fraud. When a victim requests a refund within seven days of the incident, if the company or responsible individuals refuse to return all fees within five working days, the relevant government authorities must fine the directly responsible individuals and company between 5 to 10 times the amount involved in the case. All personnel involved in the incident, all senior management, and all shareholders of the company must permanently disclose their entire personal</p>

	<p>and family assets within one week of the incident. Any movement from their original residence to other cities or regions must be reported to the police and will be monitored by them. In cases where the total amount involved exceeds CNY 10,000, a minimum sentence of 1 year in prison shall be imposed.</p>
<p>10 2</p>	<p>The simultaneous administration of hepatitis B vaccine with other vaccines to newborns, or consecutive vaccinations over a short period of time, has been associated with distinct adverse reactions, which once led to the consecutive deaths of 21 infants at the end of 2013 (The final verification data should be at least 23 babies).⁹² This caused great shock and panic among the vast majority of families in China, directly leading to a significant decline in the vaccination rate for children. Subsequent research found that deaths associated with consecutive BCG, influenza, or poliovirus vaccines, as well as those involving preterm and cesarean section births, accounted for a combined proportion of 81.0%.⁹² However, pharmaceutical companies in China did not revise the package inserts of their hepatitis B vaccines, nor did they carry out any campaigns to raise awareness. In fact, the subsequent incidence of infant mortality following consecutive administrations of hepatitis B vaccine along with another vaccine in a short period, as well as recurrent mortality among infants born with abnormalities after hepatitis B vaccination, have been ignored.⁹³⁻⁹⁷ Pharmaceutical companies, with the professional capacity to recognize such issues, have not taken any responsibility, causing enormous suffering for families. This clearly indicates a lack of basic medical ethics.</p> <p>In the United States as well, there have also been serious adverse reactions or unusual incidents in children following consecutive vaccinations with the hepatitis B vaccine and other vaccines that have not been reported by parents with a medical background or taken to hospitals for treatment. Retrospective analyses by these parents led them to suspect that the probable cause was the continuous administration of multiple vaccines, including hepatitis B vaccine, over a short period of time.</p> <p>Therefore, the United Nations and the World Health Organization should establish an international convention that includes the following: First, the prohibition of consecutive combination vaccinations with hepatitis B vaccine for children within a short period or six months. Second, infants with abnormal births, such as those delivered by cesarean section or born prematurely, should not receive hepatitis B vaccine within three years of birth. Third, where studies show that consecutive hepatitis B and other vaccines can lead to high mortality rates, as well as a high incidence of abnormal deaths in infants born under abnormal circumstances, pharmaceutical companies should be held responsible for infant deaths resulting from failure to promptly update vaccine package inserts and provide reasonable compensation. Fourth, because hepatitis B is no longer a difficult or critical disease and the carrier rate of hepatitis B virus in China has declined significantly, uninfected young people or adults can still prevent hepatitis B by vaccination, so hepatitis B vaccines must be classified as non-compulsory to save on medical insurance expenditures for various</p>

	<p>countries. Fifth, vaccine adverse reaction databases in any country must be open to all the public for access and monitoring.</p> <p>The most important values of leadership are the ability to foresee and make decisions, otherwise anyone could be a leader. Large-scale mandatory or semi-mandatory vaccination with any new vaccine that has not undergone three years of post-marketing surveillance should be prohibited in order to expose potential adverse reactions or coincidental events as much as possible. Anyone who makes mandatory vaccinations or creates a de facto mandatory situation must bear legal responsibility. In the event of widespread sequelae, serious anomalies, or adverse reactions, the incomes of those responsible should be confiscated for two years, and they should not participate in the creation of any significant policy or regulation for the next eight years. The purpose of this convention is to reduce decisions lacking scientific basis and situations where decision-makers bear no consequences. Anyone who has made such serious mistakes must undergo repeated learning and training in other positions before they can again be involved in decision-making and regulatory formulation.</p>
10 3	<p>The United States and Europe, such as Lithuania and France, have a tradition of preying on crows.</p> <p>New Zealand holds a yearly Hokitika Wildfoods Festival featuring cuisine such as magpie meat pies, seagull eggs, and even wild hare testicles, which greatly surpass the variety of games traditionally consumed in China, challenging conventional thinking.</p> <p>In many towns in Texas ,USA, there is also a traditional festival surrounding rattlesnakes. On the second weekend of March each year, residents come together to celebrate "Rattlesnake Roundup." In this festival, about 130,000 rattlesnakes are killed annually, yielding 136,000 kilograms of rattlesnake meat (Fig 84. Fig 85.),⁹⁸ all of which is eaten by food enthusiasts irrespective of whether it is before or after the COVID-19 pandemic.</p> <p>Despite the lack of direct evidence that the novel coronavirus originated directly from wild animals such as snakes, civets, bamboo rats, wild hares, wild boars, etc., and no direct evidence that it originated from bats or civets secretions, many wild animals raised by farmers were culled and buried during the COVID-19 pandemic. Traditional practices of hunting wild boar has also been banned, leading to overabundance of wild boar, which in turn causes damage to crops. Farmers, unable to control the situation, are left helpless. Such misguided policies have led to poverty in many farming families, affecting their protein sources. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention with the following provisions:</p> <p>First, before the COVID-19 pandemic, any country that did not legislate against the artificial breeding and consumption of wild animals and had traditional practices of breeding and consumption of such animals should not be prohibited from breeding and consumption. No reason should be used to ban breeding and selling, cutting off the livelihoods and incomes of poor farmers, unless there is direct evidence of the virus originating in a specific species of</p>

	<p>wild animal, in which case a ban on breeding and consumption of that animal may be considered.</p> <p>Second, anyone who is threatened by wild animals, whose domesticated animals are attacked by wild animals, or whose crops are destroyed by wild animals resulting in severe losses should be allowed to injure or kill those animals without any penalty. The meat of these killed animals can be eaten by those who are threatened.</p> <p>Third, from now on, anyone responsible for formulating faulty regulations that result in significant economic losses to farmers must donate one year's salary to the government's agricultural poverty alleviation fund. They are also prohibited from participating in the formulation of any major policies or regulations for the next eight years. The purpose of this convention is to reduce the occurrence of decisions made without scientific basis and where policymakers do not bear any consequences. Those who have made such serious mistakes must undergo repeated learning and training in other positions before they can again participate in the formulation of regulations on major issues.</p>
10 4	<p>Any state that legalizes organized crime (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) is a barbaric and despicable nation, an uncivilized country. It should never have voting rights in the United Nations and the Security Council, nor can it become a permanent member of the United Nations or the Security Council. Even if the legitimacy of organized crime is revoked in the future, the country should not become a permanent member of the United Nations for 100 years after the revocation, and should not be allowed to become a permanent member of the Security Council. In the future, any politician who proposes that a country with legalized organized crime or where such crimes are permissible should become a permanent member of the United Nations or the Security Council will be defined as an evil, contemptible and inferior anti-humanist politician.</p>
10 5	<p>Lack of morality among civil servants, employees of governmental agencies, or staff of units substituting for government functions is a disaster for both the government and the public. If their mindset cannot be changed through education, they must be removed from government and administrative institutions as much as possible. This can provide opportunities for other employees with excellent moral character.</p> <p>The United Nations should establish a global convention for the above-mentioned civil servants and employees, widely advocating the establishment of a good culture and the elimination of a bad culture. If the individuals involved in this clause do wrong and cannot sincerely accept criticism, or if they retaliate against those who offer reasonable and compliant suggestions, they must not be promoted to new positions; otherwise, it is likely to be a disaster for the government or the public! Moreover, a systematic approach must be formed! Otherwise, once these individuals have power, even the power of an ordinary employee, they will become a great barrier to public service and an obstacle to the government's effective administration.</p>

	<p>It is suggested that if, within three years, individuals involved in this clause intentionally create barriers for others that are difficult to detect, or engage in retaliatory actions, accumulating to eight instances, or if they cause serious hindrance that leads to significant public questioning, they should be promptly removed from their positions. At a minimum, they must be transferred from their original posts within one month, and retrained through government department-sponsored classes to understand their mistakes and shortcomings. Only after training in other positions can they be considered for reemployment.</p>
10 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>A country's assets do not belong to any political party, and it is prohibited for politicians of political parties in any state to waive claims on behalf of the state, its public, or victims against a criminal state or war criminal state that has committed large-scale crimes. Waiting for such claims goes against fundamental human ethics and rational logic, seriously violates the human rights of others, and is completely unsubstantiated from a legal standpoint. National assets belong solely to all citizens with the nationality of that country, and victims' property belongs only to the victims themselves, not to politicians, political parties or governments. Not holding a criminal state accountable for severe crimes and looting of property, and not forcing the return of all wealth, constitutes a major crime against the good people of that nation, a crime against human peace, a crime against those who diligently create wealth, and encourages the criminal state to initiate crimes. It also encourages a criminal State or a war criminal State to unlawfully accumulate wealth. Accordingly, the following global convention must be established:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prohibit any state's politicians from renouncing claims for compensation and reparations against the criminal State or war criminal State that has committed large-scale crimes on behalf of the State or its nationals or victims. 2. To prevent possible direct or potential interest deals between the politician and their family with the criminal state, creating material conditions for the politician's descendants, if such proposals are presented by politicians, the entire direct lineage relatives and all direct lineage of those relatives, and the blood-related collateral relatives' family property will unconditionally belong to the victims once the politician's opinion becomes a fact. 3. Due to the significant impact on the descendants of victims, if the third generation of the proposing politician is alive at the time, three consecutive generations of that politician's family must compensate the victims and restore

	<p>the national property loss. Only after full restitution is made to the victims can they live freely; otherwise, the three generations of the politician who made the proposal must only enjoy the most basic living standard of the country, and they will be prohibited from flying in airplanes and traveling on luxury cruise ships. If there has been a high-minded family style since 1900, characterized by treating their own, their family members', and relatives' wealth with disdain, compensation to victims would naturally be voluntary. If not, it indicates extreme hypocrisy in the family, and the descendants of such a person should be banned from engaging in politics or holding any civil service or legal positions for a thousand years.</p> <p>4. Any compensation that is disproportionate to loss and suffering is invalid, even if it was signed under external pressure in the past.</p>
10 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 1900, any country that has committed the following crimes without fully compensating the victimized nation must accept the following sanctions and use them on any official occasion:</p> <p>A malevolent country that has massacred more than 500,000 innocent civilians of another nation must prepend SM to its country name, being called an SM nation, and is prohibited from changing its name for 300 years.</p> <p>A country that has built numerous telecommunication fraud parks to carry out large-scale telecommunications fraud, extortion of property, kidnapping, rape, gang rape, live organ harvesting, organ trading, torture, or massacres, if within three years the number of people involved reaches three hundred thousand, or the total wealth obtained from fraud reaches \$6 billion(calculated according to the currency value of 2023), it must be named a SR or SRM or RSM or ST or STM or TSM nation, and is prohibited from changing its name for 300 years.</p> <p>Any country that has massacred more than five hundred thousand innocent civilians or expatriates of another nation is prohibited from being called a socialist country. The ruling party involved in the incident is prohibited from being called the Communist Party, and the aforementioned names must be changed. The name involved in the case must be completely changed within three months.</p> <p>Any country that has set up telecommunication fraud parks to plunder the property of civilians of other nations through telecommunication fraud, and within three years the number of persons involved reaches three hundred</p>

	<p>thousand, or has obtained total wealth from extortion, fraud, or massacres that reaches \$10 billion (calculated according to the currency value of 2023), is prohibited from being called a socialist country. The ruling party involved in the incident is prohibited from being called the Communist Party, and the aforementioned names must be changed.</p> <p>The republican form of government is a fair and just system, capable of achieving justice by engaging in and resolving political affairs and disputes peacefully. Republicanism emphasizes the public nature, fairness, and impartiality of government. Moreover, the positive connotations of democratic and free nations need no elaboration.</p> <p>Any country which has committed the aforementioned crimes and has not yet fully compensated the victims and the affected nation shall be prohibited from calling itself a "communist country," "democratic country," "free country," "just country," "liberal democratic country," or "republic"; to prevent such a country from deceiving the public and other nations and undermining world peace.</p> <p>In the aforementioned countries involved, any ruling party that refuses to sign written apologies and fails to provide full compensation is prohibited from calling itself the "Communist Party," "Socialist Party," "Social Party," "Democratic Party," "Republican Party," "Liberal Party," "Liberal Democratic Party," "Liberal Republican Party," "Republican Liberal Party," "Justice Party," "People's Party," "Democratic Republican Party," or "Republican Democratic Party," or "Justice Party." Furthermore, such ruling parties are prohibited from using any name containing the words "Republic," "Free," "Socialist," "Democratic," "Socialist," "Liberal," "Country," "Communist," or "Justice." Through these actions, a political-vigilance (politicalvigilance) is created both in the country and globally to prevent said political parties and their nefarious, unscrupulous politicians from deceiving the public and other nations, undermining global peace, with the goal of reducing war and achieving peace.</p> <p>The name involved in the case must be completely changed within three months.</p> <p>The above-mentioned methodologies for solving crime should be considered by the United Nations or the World Peace Organization as one of the methods for maintaining world peace and sustainable development. The United Nations should take the initiative to formulate relevant conventions as soon as possible.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
10 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current world has failed to rapidly and effectively curb the excessive global wealth gap, reduce long-term rural poverty in remote areas or mountainous regions, and sustainably develop rural economies and increase the incomes of rural families. This reflects a lack of philosophical understanding and</p>

methodological cognition in reducing the population affected by war. The inability to achieve long-term world peace is the result of significant problems in implementing national governance and maintaining world peace philosophically and methodologically. It is also the result of Europe's modern theft and incomplete imitation of China's legislative ideology, and the false claim that Europe is the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must undergo a philosophical and methodological change in order to rapidly and effectively curb excessive global wealth disparities and increase the income of the rural population in impoverished areas, and form a permanent consensus or convention.

The rapidly growing white feather chicken, since being selected by humans as a commodity for rapid growth, has had its life put forward rapidly by human technology. From the moment they hatch, it takes only 39-42 days for these chicks, weighing less than 100 grams, to grow to about 1-2.5 kilograms. The factory model for these fast-growing chickens means they may never see sunlight in their lifetime, grow in extremely narrow spaces, and eat in addition to sleeping.

From the moment these chicks hatch, they are placed on a conveyor belt of fate determined by humans. In factories, humans mainly select individuals that are well developed and safe, while those that do not meet the standards are sent directly to a grinder to be crushed, and then made into various types of pet food. It is estimated that nearly 7 billion chicks are crushed on Earth every year. Healthy chicks are sent to vaccination workshops because only after being vaccinated can these chicks be sent to the next stage of breeding at a chicken farm. In this process, to prevent chicks from fighting each other, humans also clip their overly sharp beaks, so that they lose their remaining attack power without losing their ability to eat. Once these chicks enter the chicken farm, for their limited life span, they do nothing but sleep and constantly eat. However, due to the excessively narrow feeding environment, these broiler chickens often develop incomplete feather growth, and some even lose their mobility almost entirely due to their rapid growth without adequate exercise. Moreover, since humans only focus on the meat development of chicks to prevent them from dying due to rapid body development, they add some drugs to the feed to ensure the chicks survive until slaughter. Although some of these drugs may harm the human body, as long as they are used in accordance with the relevant regulations and not excessively, they can be sold normally.

Chickens raised on a large scale in workshops must be extensively administered with vaccines, antiviral medications, and antibiotics to enable their mass survival. As a result, the presence of vaccine and antibiotic metabolic residues in chicken meat is inevitable. Moreover, such chicken lacks the aroma and texture of home-raised chickens. Third, some medical professionals suspect, in internal discussions about the high incidence of homosexuality in society, that consuming this type of chicken meat may contribute to increased rates of homosexuality, which contradicts the natural laws of human

heterosexual love and reproduction. Fourth, the extremely limited space for chickens in large-scale workshop farming contradicts animal ethics and the natural laws of a chicken's life.

The current global rural poverty is a challenging issue that must be addressed from a perspective of health and global vision in dealing with the global health of chicken farming and widespread ecological farming of chickens. It is necessary to decentralize the global chicken farming industry to rural areas, reduce the scale of individual chicken farms, eliminate the super-large-scale factory farming model, and promote the free-range farming of chickens by farmers and the large-scale ecological farming of chickens using natural environments in rural areas to promote rural behavioral economy and agricultural behavioral economy development, and increase farmers' income, especially for households with insufficient or lacking labor force.

Therefore, the United Nations, the World Health Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations should form a global consensus and develop a convention, with the following content:

1. It should be prohibited to use industrial narrow space high density chicken farming in workshops within the next 3 - 5 years, and the chicken farming model where chickens almost never see sunlight from birth should be banned. Reduce the use of chemical additives to feed fast-growing chickens and reduce the use of vaccines, synthetic antiviral drugs, and antibiotics in the chicken farming process.

2. For breeding 300-1,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least between 1,000-2,000 square meters.

3. For breeding 1,001-2,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 3000-5000 square meters.

4. For breeding 2,001-5,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 6,000-12,000 square meters.

5. For breeding 5,001-10,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 14,000-20,000 square meters.

6. For breeding 10,001-15,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 22,000-30,000 square meters.

7. For breeding 15001-20,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 32,000-40,000 square meters.

8. For breeding 20001-30,000 chickens, the outdoor activity area must be at least 32,000-60,000 square meters.

Of this, at least 70% of the chicken's outdoor activity area (1-8) must be exposed to soil and trees, with hilly areas calculated as slopes.

9. The average daily free activity time for chickens must not be less than 7 hours (excluding time confined to cages. Except for abnormal weather conditions). Farms with an annual production of more than 2,000 birds must be equipped with real-time monitoring and video recording, which must be preserved for at least three years if mechanical operations lock chickens in cages.

10. Chickens and eggs previously raised in workshops must be given a specific name, "workshop assembly line chickens without sunlight" and "workshop assembly line eggs without sunlight," and this must be disclosed at any stage of production and sale to fully inform consumers.

11. To solve rural poverty, the United Nations should encourage rural families to raise chickens. Each family should not raise more than 200 chickens per year (Each batch should not exceed 100 chickens) (No more than 300 chickens in mountainous areas, each batch should not exceed 150 chickens), Raising more chickens often requires farmers to use vaccines or synthetic drugs to prevent diseases. During the raising process, it is prohibited to use solvent extraction to extract soybean oil from soybean cakes or to use any protein processed feed made from these soybean cakes. Only natural grains should be fed. Chickens that have not been injected with any vaccines or given any synthetic antibiotics during the raising process are named "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural courtyard chickens." Chickens that have been injected with vaccines or given synthetic antibiotics are named "rural courtyard chickens." According to the different breeds of chickens raised by rural families, different levels of consumption should be promoted to promote rural economic development, balance regional and rural-urban disparities, and solve the dilemma of farmers' lack of marketing and promotion skills. It must be stipulated that chickens raised by farmers for more than 4 months (chickens raised in workshops and assembly lines can be sold in just 40 days) that meet the above standards are allowed to be sold under the names "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural courtyard chickens" or "rural courtyard chickens". The corresponding eggs should be sold under the names "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural yard chicken eggs" or "rural yard chicken eggs", with prices differentiating them from chickens or eggs from other breeding methods. Any merchants who violate the above logic or engage in fraud will be fined five times the amount and, if they commit three violations, all their personal property will be confiscated and given to the country's agricultural foundation. Farmers who violate the rules will be blacklisted, and any organization will not promote the chickens and eggs they raise for three years.

This convention aims to disperse the industrialized production of unhealthy and non-ecological poultry industry, which originally took place in dense workshops, and to establish a new economic model for the production and supply of chicken meat and eggs that are widely distributed in rural households or natural villages as the main producers. This allows farmers to obtain better profits without leaving their land, promotes the development of the rural economy, reduces the excessive expansion and overcrowding of cities caused only by driving urban economic growth, and promotes the balanced development of urban and rural areas. It also aims to reduce the use of antibiotics, improve the quality of chicken meat and eggs, and provide healthy ecological food for the region.

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	<p>In the traditional rural model, family-raised chickens, ducks, and geese are basically impossible to suffer from gout. From breeding to slaughter, very few drugs are used. However, in the large-scale industrial farming of these poultry, gout has become a common and frequent disease due to excessive protein, excessive use of antibiotics such as sulfa, etc. Rural family-raised chickens, ducks, and geese never need vaccination. However, in industrial farming, vaccination has become standard. In fact, the chickens, ducks, and geese that most people now consume can be said to be "drugged" poultry raised on factory farms.</p> <p>[Industrialized chicken farming.2022-06-25. https://v.douyin.com/iFDHAdTc/z@G.ic pDU:/ 07/22];[Industrialized chicken farming.2021-08-28. https://v.douyin.com/iFDupqgJ/ o@q.re 01/19 Euf:/];</p> <p>[Industrial Hen Incubation Process.2022-09-01. https://v.douyin.com/iFDuos4M/ GII:/ 08/29 E@h.oQ];</p> <p>[Rural free range local chickens. 2024-02-27. https://v.douyin.com/iFD512mM/ A@G.vF odn:/ 01/06]; [Rural free range local chickens.2024-03-05. https://v.douyin.com/iFDHTVv9/ TYm:/ 06/13 u@s.rr];[Rural free range local chickens. 2024-03-08. https://www.douyin.com/video/7343946236522777895];[Rural free range local chickens. 2023-07-22. https://v.douyin.com/iFD91Yv6/ lvS:/ 07/14 l@v.fo];[Rural free range local chickens. 2021-11-23. https://v.douyin.com/iFDHLKrr/ C@u.fb WzG:/ 10/21];[Rural free range local chickens. 2023-06-06. https://v.douyin.com/iFDHmpnW/ MwS:/ 05/31 Q@k.Cu];[Rural free range local chickens.2021-08-07. https://v.douyin.com/iFDHYfvm/ z@G.VY 03/16 icn:/]</p>
10 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current world has failed to rapidly and effectively curb the excessive global wealth gap, reduce long-term rural poverty in remote areas or mountainous regions, and sustainably develop rural economies and increase the incomes of rural families. This reflects a lack of philosophical understanding and methodological cognition in reducing the population affected by war. The inability to achieve long-term world peace is the result of significant problems in implementing national governance and maintaining world peace philosophically and methodologically. It is also the result of Europe's modern theft and incomplete imitation of China's legislative ideology, and the false claim that Europe is the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must undergo a philosophical and methodological change in order to rapidly and effectively curb excessive global wealth disparities and increase the income of the rural population in impoverished areas, and form a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Pigs raised in large numbers in cramped workshop environments must be given an abundance of vaccines, antiviral medications, antibiotics, and even air purification to ensure pigs can survive in bulk. As a result, pork not only inevitably contains residues of vaccine metabolites and antibiotics, but also</p>

lacks the aroma and texture characteristic of domestic pigs. Moreover, through vertical, mass-rearing methods employed in workshops, pigs have extremely limited living space, lack access to the outdoors, violating animal ethics and the natural laws of pig life.

Global rural poverty is a challenging issue, and it must be approached from a perspective that embraces both health and the big picture. Addressing health-oriented and ecologically sound pig farming globally involves decentralizing the pig farming industry to promote rural behavioral economics and the development of agricultural economics, thereby increasing the income of more farmers, especially those in mountainous regions.

Therefore, it is recommended that the United Nations, the World Health Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations form a global consensus and draft a convention that includes the following points:

1. Industrial pig farming in workshops should be banned within the next 5-6 years, reducing reliance on chemical additives for rapid pig growth and relying on vaccines, synthetic antiviral medications, and antibiotics.

2. Pig farming should utilize mountainous land resources, ensuring pigs have access to outdoor activity space, with the average outdoor space per pig being at least 4 square meters. At least 70% of the pigs' outdoor area must consist of bare soil and trees, with mountainous areas calculated as slopes.

Therefore, it is recommended that the United Nations, the World Health Organization and the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations come together to form a global consensus and establish a convention as follows:

First, it should be a goal to ban industrial pig farming in workshop settings within the next 5-6 years. Efforts should be made to reduce the breeding of fast-growing pigs using chemical additives, as well as reliance on vaccines, synthetic antiviral medications, and antibiotics.

Second, mountainous land resources should be utilized for pig farming, where pigs in pig farms must have outdoor space for activity. On average, each pig should have at least 5 square meters of outdoor activity area. Of this outdoor area, more than 70% must consist of exposed soil and trees, with mountainous areas calculated according to the slope.

Third, in order to address rural poverty, the United Nations should support family-based pig farming, allowing each family to raise no more than 20 pigs per year. During the rearing process, the use of soybean cake extracted by solvent extraction or any protein feed processed from such cake is prohibited. Instead, only natural grain should be fed. Pigs that have not been injected with any vaccine during the breeding process, and have not been given any synthetic antibiotics or synthetic antiviral drugs, shall be named "farmhouse pigs." Families involved in pig farming and slaughtering do not need to go through any formal selling procedures.

Fourth, pigs raised in mountainous areas with a certain activity space shall be named "mountain pigs"; those raised on plains with a certain activity space

	<p>shall be named "plain pigs".</p> <p>Fifthly, pigs raised on a large scale in vertical workshop farming systems shall be called "workshop pigs." Clear labelling must be ensured in all sales and packaging.</p> <p>This convention aims to break up the industrialized and non-healthy pig farming industry, which was originally concentrated in workshops, and to establish a new economic model for pork production that is widely distributed in rural households or natural rural villages. This new model aims to enable farmers to obtain better returns without leaving the land they cultivate, promote the development of the rural economy, reduce the excessive expansion and crowding of cities caused by simply driving urban economic growth, and promote balanced development between urban and rural areas. It also aims to reduce the use of antibiotics and improve the quality of pork to provide the region with healthy ecological food.</p>
11 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects the crimes of mass rape or gang rape crimes stipulated by this Convention, or that is a state of war criminals or their citizens or descendants, will be prohibited from participating in the writing of any history books or historical textbooks for the next 1,000 years. The aforementioned publications from such a country can only be written by a specialized editorial team organized by the country with a larger number of victims and must be used compulsorily by everyone in that country or their descendants unless every country in the world agrees by vote. In the case of crimes committed since 1900, any event that results in the rape or gang rape of 20,000 innocent civilians in another country within a single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years, will be subject to this provision.</p> <p>Any nationals or women of aggressor or criminal States who wage aggressive wars are not covered by this Convention as a whole, and the entire population of those criminal States is guilty, with virtually no innocent civilians.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term</p>

	<p>world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation which commits or protects the perpetrators of genocide or war criminals involved in warfare massacres covered by this Convention, or its citizens or descendants, will be prohibited from participating in the writing of any history books or historical textbooks for the next one thousand years. The aforementioned publications from such a country can only be written by a specialized editorial team organized by the country with a larger number of victims and must be used compulsorily by everyone in that country or their descendants unless every country in the world agrees by vote. In the case of crimes committed since 1900, any event that results in the death of 20,000 innocent civilians of another country within a single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years will be subject to this provision.</p> <p>Any nationals or women of aggressor or criminal States who wage aggressive wars are not covered by this Convention as a whole, and the entire population of those criminal States is guilty, with virtually no innocent civilians.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 2	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State which carries out or protects criminals involved in the mass killing of bacteriological warfare genocides or biochemical warfare covered by this Convention, as well as such criminals or war criminals, its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in the writing of any history books or history textbooks for the next millennium. The above-mentioned books for such a country can only be written by a specialized writing group organized by the country with the highest number of victims and must be used mandatorily among all its people or their descendants unless every country globally agrees by vote. This clause applies to any State in which, from 1900 onwards, any single incident has caused the death of 10,000 innocent civilians from another country, 30,000 within one year, 80,000 people within eight years, or a country where the number of victims has reached 100,000 within five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of</p>

	<p>civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
11 3	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State that carries out or protects criminals involved in large-scale telecommunications fraud, as well as such criminals or war criminals, its citizens, or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in the writing of any history books or history textbooks for the next millennium. The above-mentioned books for such a country can only be written by a specialized writing group organized by the country with the highest number of victims and must be used mandatorily among all its people or their descendants unless unanimously agreed upon by every country's vote. This clause shall apply to any State where, since 1900, in any single year, 50,000 innocent civilians from another country have been victims of fraud, 100,000 have been victims of fraud within three years, or any country that has accumulated a total fraud amount of \$10 billion in any three-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 4	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals involved in mass rapes or gang rapes as defined in this Convention, as well as their state or war criminals, citizens, or descendants, shall be prohibited from participating directly or indirectly in the establishment of any press, news, or media entity in any third country for the next thousand years, unless every country globally agrees by vote. This clause applies to any country where crimes since 1900 have resulted in at least 20,000 innocent civilians of another nation being raped or gang-raped in any single incident, 50,000 within one year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>Any nationals or women of aggressor or criminal States who wage aggressive wars are not covered by this Convention as a whole, and the entire population of those criminal States is guilty, with virtually no innocent civilians.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 5	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects the criminals involved in mass slaughters as defined in this Convention, as well as their state or war criminals, citizens, or descendants, shall be barred for the next thousand years from participating directly or indirectly in the initiation of any press, news, or media venture in any third country, unless every country globally consents by vote. This clause applies to any state where crimes since 1900 have killed at least 20,000 innocent civilians from another nation in a single incident, 50,000 in one year, or 100,000</p>

	<p>in eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 6	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects the criminals involved in large-scale telecommunication fraud as outlined in this Convention, along with their state or war criminals, citizens, or descendants, shall be forbidden from engaging in or indirectly establishing any press, news, or media in any third country for an upcoming millennium, barring the unanimous consent of all nations worldwide by vote. This clause applies to countries where crimes since 1900 have caused at least 50,000 innocent civilians from another nation to become victims in any given year, or 100,000 within three years, as well as to any nation where the total amount of fraud has reached \$10 billion in any three-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 7	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects the criminals involved in mass killings of biological or chemical warfare as stipulated by this Convention, as well as their state or war criminals, citizens, or descendants, shall be barred for the next thousand years from participating directly or indirectly in the initiation of any press, news, or media venture in any third country, unless every country globally consents by vote. This clause applies to any crimes since 1900 where an event has caused the death of at least 10,000 innocent civilians in another country, 30,000 within a year, 80,000 within eight years, or 100,000 victims within five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
11 8	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that commits or protects criminals involved in mass rapes or gang rapes as stipulated by this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international women's awards or from being awarded any international women's prizes for the next thousand years, unless every country in the world agrees by vote. This provision applies to any country where crimes committed since 1900 have resulted in the rape or gang rape of 20,000 innocent civilians of another country in a single incident, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and</p>

	sustainable development.
11 9	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that commits or protects criminals involved in mass rapes or gang rapes as mentioned in this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international awards or from being awarded any international prizes for the next thousand years, unless every country in the world agrees by vote. This applies to any country where crimes committed since 1900 have led to the rape or gang rape of 20,000 innocent civilians from another country in a single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
12 0	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country which commits or protects the criminals involved in mass massacres as stipulated by this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international awards or from being awarded any international prizes for the next thousand years, unless every country in the world agrees by vote. This provision applies to any country where crimes committed since 1900 have caused the death of twenty thousand innocent civilians in another country in a single incident, 50,000 in a year, or 100,000 in eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
12 1	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that commits or protects criminals involved in mass massacres through bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare as stated in this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international awards or from being granted any international prizes for the next thousand years, unless every country in the world agrees unanimously by vote. This applies to any country where crimes since 1900 have resulted in the death of 20,000 innocent civilians in another country in a single event, 50,000 in a year, or 100,000 in eight years, or where victims reach 100,000 in five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>

12 2	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country which commits or protects the criminals involved in large-scale telecommunication fraud as stipulated by this Convention, or a State guilty of war crimes, or its citizens or their descendants, will be prohibited from participating in any international awards or from being awarded any international prizes for the next thousand years, unless unanimously agreed upon by vote of every country in the world. This provision applies to any State where crimes committed since 1900 have resulted in the victimization of fifty thousand innocent civilians of another country in any one year, one hundred thousand in three years, or a total fraud amounting to \$10 billion in any three-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 3	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation which commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving mass rape, gang rape as covered by this Convention, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. Legislation in such a State shall be carried out only by a dedicated legislative team organized by States with a higher number of victims, and it must be used compulsorily by all persons in that State or their descendants. This clause applies to any State in which crimes committed since 1900 have resulted in the rape or gang rape of 20,000 innocent civilians from another country in a single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 4	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving mass murder, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. Legislation in such a State shall only be conducted by a dedicated legislative team organized by States with</p>

	<p>a higher number of victims, and it must be enforced amongst all the people of that State or their descendants. This clause applies to any State where crimes committed since 1900 have caused the death of 20,000 innocent civilians from another country in a single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 5	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving bacterial warfare mass murder or biochemical warfare mass murder, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. Legislation in such a State shall only be crafted by a specialized legislative team from nations with more victims and be enforced amongst all the people of that State or their descendants. This clause applies to any nation that, since 1900, has been involved in an event that has caused the death of ten thousand innocent civilians from another country, thirty thousand within a year, eighty thousand within eight years, or where the victims reached a hundred thousand within five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 6	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation that commits or protects criminals who commit offenses involving large-scale telecommunications fraud, or is a state or war criminal, its citizens or their descendants, shall be prohibited from possessing legislative powers for the next thousand years and be forbidden from participating in legislation. The nation's legislation shall be performed only by a specialized legislative team of nations with more victims and enforced among all people or their descendants. This clause applies to any State where crimes committed since 1900 caused fifty thousand innocent civilians from another nation to become victims in any given year, a hundred thousand in three years, or where the total amount of fraud has reached ten billion U.S. dollars in any three-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and</p>

	<p>sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 7	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any criminal State, war-criminal State, or its citizens or descendants involved in large-scale massacres in accordance with this Convention, which have established companies based on the plundering of factories and equipment of a victim State, must, for the next thousand years, display the initials "SPM" on any signage of that company, and the use of "SPM" is mandatory in all promotional materials of the State. This clause applies to States responsible for crimes since 1900, when, in any single incident, the number of innocent civilians from another nation killed reached 20,000, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 8	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any criminal State, war criminal State, or its citizens or descendants involved in large-scale rape or gang rape as provided for in this Convention, which has established companies based on the plundering of factories and equipment of a victim State, must, for the next thousand years, display the initials "SPM" on any signage of that company, and the use of "SPM" is mandatory in all of the state's promotional materials. This clause applies to states responsible for crimes since 1900 when, in any single incident, the number of innocent civilians from another nation raped or gang-raped reached 20,000, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
12 9	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State or its citizens or descendants that has committed the crime of bacterial warfare massacres or large-scale biochemical warfare massacres under the implementation of this Convention, and companies established on the basis of factories and facilities looted from the victimized nations, must bear the mark</p>

	<p>"SPM" on all their signage for the next 1,000 years and must incorporate this mark in all their propaganda materials mandatorily. This clause applies to crimes committed since 1900 in any event where the number of innocent civilian deaths in another country reaches ten thousand in a single incident, thirty thousand in one year, eighty thousand in eight years, or one hundred thousand victims in five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
130	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State found guilty of crimes involving mass slaughter as provided for in this Convention, or any war criminal State, or its citizens, or their descendants, who have established companies based on the plundering of factories and facilities from the victim nations, must transfer all property rights fully and intact to the victim nations and victims within six months after this convention comes into effect. There shall be no destruction of any property of said companies; all accounts must be clear and traceable; all personnel and positions must be traceable; and all technical information must be complete and intact. This clause applies to any State where crimes committed since 1900 have led to the death of twenty thousand innocent civilians in a single incident, fifty thousand in a year, or one hundred thousand over eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
131	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State, war criminal nation, or its citizens or descendants responsible for perpetrating mass slaughter through bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare as delineated in this Convention, whose companies are established on the basis of facilities and equipment plundered from the victim nation, must transfer complete ownership of all such property to the victim nation and the victims within six months after this Convention takes effect. No destruction of the company's assets is permitted, all account records must be made completely clear and traceable, all personnel and positions must be held accountable, and all technical data must be intact and complete. Crimes that have occurred since 1900 apply to this clause, so long as any single incident has resulted in the death of at least ten thousand innocent civilians of another nation within one year, thirty thousand within three years, or eighty thousand within eight years, or in cases where the number of victims reached one hundred thousand within five years.</p>

	<p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
13 2	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any criminal State or war criminal State or its citizens or descendants involved in mass slaughter as stipulated by this Convention, who have plundered another nation's ancient documents and music literature and used them as a basis to develop any music or literary works, shall have the ownership of such works belonging to the victim nation. The criminal State and the perpetrators must hand over all music and ancient documents intact to the victim nation and victims within one month after this Convention comes into effect. The destruction of ancient documents is prohibited. All catalogues must be clear and traceable, and any personnel and positions related to the management of the relevant books must be held accountable. All plundered materials must be complete and undiminished. This clause applies to any nation involved in crimes since 1900 that have resulted in the deaths of 20,000 innocent civilians in another country in any single event, 50,000 in one year, or 100,000 in eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
13 3	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any criminal state or war-criminal state or its citizens or descendants involved in large-scale rape or gang rape as provided for in this Convention, who have plundered the ancient documents and music literature of another nation and used them as a basis to develop any music or literary works, shall have ownership of such works belonging to the victim nation. The criminal state and the perpetrators must hand over all music and ancient documents intact to the victimized nation and victims within one month after this Convention comes into effect. The destruction of ancient documents is prohibited. All catalogues must be clear and traceable, and any personnel and positions related to the management of the relevant books must be held accountable. All plundered materials must be complete and undiminished. This clause applies to any nation involved in crimes since 1900 that have resulted in 20,000 innocent civilians of another country being raped or gang-raped in any single event, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p>

	<p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
13 4	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State or war criminal nation or its citizens or descendants found guilty of committing acts of bacterial warfare genocide or large-scale biochemical warfare slaughter under this Convention, and who plundered ancient documents, books and original musical documents of other nations to develop any musical or literary works, shall have ownership of such works belonging to the victimized nation. The guilty State and criminals must transfer all music and ancient literature to the victimized nation and the victims intact within one month of the convention comes into effect. There is to be no destruction of ancient documents and books; all cataloging must be clear and traceable, and all personnel and positions related to the management of the relevant books must be accountable. All of the plundered materials must be complete and intact. This provision applies to any nation that has, in any single incident since 1900, has caused the death of ten thousand innocent civilians, 30,000 in one year, 80,000 in eight years, or where the victims have reached 100,000 in five years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
13 5	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State or war criminal nation involved in large-scale massacres as stipulated by this Convention must prohibit the legalization of any organized criminal organizations, as long as that state's organized crime groups (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) have previously participated in the creation of conflicts, massacring victims from other countries, pillage of property, extortion of protection money, rape or gang-raping, kidnapping, torture, or harvesting organs in any manner. The State must confiscate all assets of these organized criminal organizations, and all members and their family members must report to the police station before leaving or arriving in any city or region, and these movements must also be made public on the Internet for all to see. This clause applies to crimes committed since 1900, in which innocent civilians from another country are killed in a single incident in numbers reaching 20,000, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and</p>

	<p>are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
13 6	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State or war criminal nation involved in large-scale massacres as stipulated by this Convention must prohibit the legalization of any organized criminal organization. As long as organized crime groups (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) in that State have previously participated in the creation of conflicts, massacring victims from other countries, pillage of property, extortion of protection money, rape or gang-raping, kidnapping, torture, or harvesting organs in any manner. The State must confiscate all assets of these organized criminal organizations, and all members and their family members must report to the police station before leaving or arriving in any city or region, and these movements must also be made public on the Internet for all to see. This clause applies to crimes committed since 1900, in which innocent civilians from another country are killed in a single incident in numbers reaching 20,000, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
13 7	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State or war criminal nation involved in massive occurrences of rape or gang rape as stipulated by this Convention must also prohibit the legalization of any organized criminal organization. As long as criminal groups (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) within the State have previously played a part in creating conflicts, massacring victims from other countries, looting property, extorting protection money, raping or gang raping, kidnapping, inflicting torture, or harvesting organs in any form. The State must confiscate the property of all these criminal organizations, and all members and their family members must report to the police before leaving or arriving in any city or region, with these details are also made available on the Internet to the general public. This clause applies to cases since 1900 where, in any single event, 20,000 innocent civilians of another country have been raped or gang-raped, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>

	<p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>13 8</p>	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any State, nation of war criminals, its citizens, or their descendants who have committed genocide involving bacteriological warfare or large-scale biochemical slaughter under this Convention must prohibit the legalization of any organized criminal group. As long as the organized crime group (underworld organizations, or Mafia-like, or mobs, or gangland) in that country has ever participated in creating conflict, massacring victims of the victimized country, looting property, collecting protection rackets, committing rape or gang rape, or engaging in kidnapping, torture, or harvesting live organs. The State must confiscate all property belonging to organized criminal groups within its territory, and all members and their family members must report to the police station in advance when leaving any city or region, or upon arrival in any city or region, and at the same time disclose this information on the Internet for public inspection. All personal and family property of all members must be disclosed in real time and made available for public inspection. Any crime committed since 1900 that has resulted in the death of at least 10,000 innocent civilians in a single incident, 30,000 within a year, 80,000 within eight years, or 100,000 victims within five years, shall also fall under the provisions of this clause.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>13 9</p>	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any state or war-criminal state that carries out the crimes of mass slaughter as stipulated by this convention, in which that state's religious organization has participated in any form of creating conflicts, slaughtering victims of another country, plundering property, collecting protection money, committing rape or gang rape, or engaging in abductions, torture, or live organ harvesting, or has acted to support or protect a criminal organization or members of large-scale crimes, that religious organization must globally be considered as ever-ready to commit crimes under the guise of religious beliefs or to protect criminals. The property of such religious organizations in the country must be confiscated. All leaders in the organization must be removed from their positions. This organization must be declared illegal within the country for a thousand years, forbidding any of its members from conducting or participating any religious assemblies in the country or globally, and prohibiting any of its members from</p>

	<p>using any speech to sway the public. The personal and family assets of all members must be publicly disclosed and available for scrutiny by anyone at any time. This clause applies to any country where crimes since 1900 have resulted in the death toll of innocent civilians in another country reaching 20,000 in any one event, 50,000 in a year, or 100,000 in eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p>
140	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any nation or war criminal state involved in the implementation of this convention in crimes of mass rape or gang rape, as long as any religious organization within the country has participated in creating conflict, fraud, slaughtering victims of other nations, plundering property, collecting protection money, committing rape or gang rape, kidnapping, performing torture, or harvesting organs, or has any behavior supporting the execution or protection of criminal organizations or members of mass crimes, must be globally recognized as an organization or gang that is always ready to commit or protect crimes under the guise of religious beliefs. The State must confiscate the property of such religious organizations within its territory, must relieve all leaders of the organization of their positions, and the organization must be designated as illegal within the State for the next thousand years, prohibit any member of the organization from conducting or participating in any religious gatherings within the nation or worldwide, and prohibit any member from using speech to induce the public. All members' personal and family property must be publicly disclosed and available for enquiry at all times. This clause applies to crimes that have occurred since 1900, where any single incident has resulted in mass rape or gang rape of 20,000 innocent civilians of another nation, 50,000 within a year, or 100,000 within eight years.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
141	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any criminal State or war criminal State involved in the perpetration of bacteriological warfare massacres or large-scale biochemical warfare massacres under the implementation of this Convention must ban the legalization of any</p>

	<p>criminal organization, as long as the religious organizations in that country have previously participated in creating conflicts, fraud, slaughtering people from the victimized country, looting of property, collection of protection money, rape, gang rape, kidnapping, carrying out torture, organ harvesting, or have supported the activities of facilitating or protecting criminal organizations or members of large-scale crimes. Such religious organizations must be globally recognized as always ready to commit or protect crimes under the guise of religious beliefs, and that country's assets of such religious organizations must be seized. All leaders of these organizations should be dismissed from their positions, and for a term of one thousand years, the organization must be designated as an illegal entity within the country, prohibited from holding or participating in any religious gatherings, both within the country and globally. Members of these organizations are also forbidden from persuading the public with any discourse, and the personal and family assets of all members must be made public in real time for anyone to access at any time. This clause shall apply to any country where, from 1900 onwards, any single incident has resulted in the death of 10,000 innocent civilians, 30,000 in a single year, 80,000 in eight years, or where the number of victims has reached 100,000 in a five-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
14 2	<p>Perpetrators of grave crimes must receive greater punishment in order for the world to have the possibility of peace.</p> <p>Any country that implements or protects the criminals involved in large-scale telecommunication fraud as per this convention, or is a state of criminals or war criminals, shall be subject to the following measures if a religious organization within that country has engaged in creating conflicts, fraud, massacres of civilians of victim states, looting of property, extortion, rape, mass rape, kidnapping, the implementation of torture, or the extraction of organs, or has supported or protected criminal organizations or members of large-scale crimes: the religious organization must be globally regarded as a group or gang that is always ready to commit crimes under the guise of religious beliefs. The country must confiscate the property of the religious organization within its territory, remove all the leaders of the organization from their positions, and the organization must be declared illegal within that country for the next thousand years. It is prohibited for any member of the organization to conduct or participate in any religious gatherings, either within the country or globally, and to use any speech to induce the public. The personal and family properties of all members must be publicly disclosed in real-time for inspection by anyone. This clause applies to any crimes that has occurred since 1900 which resulted in at least 50,000 innocent civilians of another country being victimized in any</p>

	<p>given year or 100,000 over three years, or in any instance where the total amount defrauded reaches \$10 billion in any three-year period.</p> <p>The United Nations and international peace organizations should consider this strategy as one of the methodologies for maintaining world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
14 3	<p>Since 1900, any criminal state or nation of war criminals that has committed crimes involving mass fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, trafficking in human beings, harvesting of live organs, massacres including biowarfare, as covered by the Consensus, will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next 1,000 years. Moreover, if such a war criminal State, having committed any of the aforementioned crimes against the public of another nation since 1900, has not so far provided compensation for the losses of the victims, it will be prohibited from establishing educational institutions, nurseries, schools, universities, or training courses in any foreign country or region for the next two thousand years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
14 4	<p>Since 1900, any criminal nation or war criminal State that has committed any crime against the public of another country, including large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, harvesting live organs, massacres, or the use of biochemical weapons as covered by this consensus, will be prohibited from owning or holding shares in any newspapers or media outlets abroad for the next thousand years. Moreover, if such a war criminal State has not compensated victims for their losses for crimes involving large-scale fraud, kidnapping, torture, gang rape, human trafficking, live organ harvesting, massacres, or biochemical weapons since 1900, it will be prohibited from owning or holding shares in any newspapers or media outlets abroad for the next two thousand years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
14 5	<p>Any false advertising on online platforms that offers items for purchase at a price more than five times lower than the normal price of the goods sold, such as misleading consumers with the opportunity to purchase products actually worth CNY 10 to 7,000 or more for CNY 1-1.9, or leading consumers to buy products actually worth CNY 50-7,000 for CNY 9.9-39.9, and enticing customers to spend, the full loss of customers deceived by such schemes shall be borne by the online platform concerned. Both the fraudster and the online platform will be fined five times the amount of the victim's loss! If the total</p>

	<p>amount of fraud exceeds \$1 million, all personal assets of the fraudster will be confiscated, and the platform will face a fine of eight times the amount. In such cases, the photos of the fraudster and the legal representative and major shareholders of the online platform, together with their crimes, must be permanently displayed on the anti-fraud network, and the online platform also commits a serious fraud crime.</p> <p>Even if no fraud has been temporarily committed, or there have been no complaints or lawsuits from victims, as soon as such advertisements appear on the online platform, criminal suspects preparing to commit fraud and the complicit online platform will face a minimum fine of \$10,000 to \$30,000. Photos and crimes of the fraudster, the legal representative, and the main shareholders of the online platform must be permanently displayed on the anti-fraud network.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
14 6	<p>A family needs to spend years of savings or their lifetime wealth to buy a house. Any state or region is prohibited from implementing housing presale systems that transfer risk to homebuyers or banks. All housing must be fully constructed and ready for habitation before it can be sold to consumers. Developers and builders are permanently responsible for the quality of housing. If there is a shelf life for the property, it must be clearly indicated in a prominent place and communicated to buyers both orally and in writing.</p> <p>Once this consensus clause forms a United Nations convention, there will be a two-year transition period during which any presales or collection of funds from homebuyers must be confined to a single bank account. No funds may leave the country from this bank account and can only be used to purchase building-related materials and pay employees' salaries. The aforementioned accounts must maintain records that are traceable for forty years. Failure to comply will result in a penalty of three times the amount of the violation, and the government will have the right to confiscate all the developer's personal assets. Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
14 7	<p>Financial regulators in any country must disclose all assets of individuals, families, and immediate family members.</p>
14 8	<p>Low-income people or farmers in any country have the freedom to sell daily necessities or essentials like vegetables or fruits on any street in any city, as long as the products being sold do not exceed the scope of their normal means of transport, such as baskets, pushcarts, etc. As long as the street is not closed to pedestrian traffic and is not under martial law, no city management personnel may prohibit their trading activities.</p>
14 9	<p>Human greed for maximizing growth rates in animals and profits has led to the use of various synthetic drugs at any stage of raising pigs, cattle, sheep, deer,</p>

	<p>and other animals. This inevitably causes health problems in humans. It is necessary to globally prohibit the use of the following drugs in animal husbandry:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adrenergic agonists such as Clenbuterol Hydrochloride, Salbutamol, Salbutamol Sulfate, Ractopamine, Dopamine Sulfate, Zilpaterol and Terbutaline Sulfate. 2. Sex hormones, such as Hexestrol, Estradiol, Estradiol Valerate, Estradiol Benzoate, Chlorotrianisene, Ethinylestradiol, Quinestrol, Chlormadinone Acetate, Levonorgestrel, Norethisterone, Human Chorionic Gonadotropin (hCG), and Follicle-Stimulating Hormone (primarily containing FSH and LH). The main risk is that consuming pork and other meats containing these hormones can cause issues like early puberty in adolescents. 3. Anabolic steroids, such as Iodinated Casein, Nandrolone Phenylpropionate, and its injectable solutions. These drugs have side effects similar to those of sex hormones, and long-term consumption of pork containing anabolic steroids can also cause adverse reactions in adolescents, such as stunted bone growth and liver damage. 4. Psychotropic drugs such as Chlorpromazine Hydrochloride, Prochlorperazine, Diazepam (Valium), Phenobarbital, Phenobarbital Sodium, Barbiturates, Secobarbital, Secobarbital Sodium, Clonidine, Alprazolam, Methamphetamine, Midazolam, Nitrazepam, Oxazepam, Pimozide, Zolpidem, and other controlled psychotropic substances in various countries. 5. Various antibiotic residues. <p>The use of these substances must be strictly regulated to protect consumers' health and prevent the adverse effects associated with their consumption.</p>
150	<p>Taking the national boundaries at the end of World War II as a reference, one may refer to the markings on maps published by the United States from 1945 to 1950. Any country that illegally occupies the territory of another automatically loses its voting rights at the United Nations and is forbidden from holding any permanent executive positions in international organizations. However, any territories of Axis powers or criminal states occupied by victorious countries after the Second World War are considered lawful.</p> <p>For any country that unlawfully occupies territory for more than ten years, a capital "O" must be prefixed to its name in every international event organized by any entity, every successive decade. If the occupation extends to 20 years, two "O" should be prefixed (OO), and for 30 years, three "O" (OOO), and so on. Territories that were previously part of the country in question or are disputed are not addressed in this provision.</p> <p>It is illegal for any country to invade another country's territory by arbitrarily drawing borders through any individual or organization. For each year that the return of illegally occupied territory is delayed, a penalty must be calculated starting from the date of illegal occupation, with an annual payment in the range of \$1 billion to \$3 billion.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized</p>

	<p>people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
15 1	<p>Countries that have waged war since 1900 and slaughtered innocent civilians or expatriates of other nations are subject to the following regulations: for every 100,000 people slaughtered, the legal marriage and childbearing ages for all citizens of the offending country or their overseas descendants are to be delayed by one year, up to a maximum of 40 years old. No early exceptions are allowed. Those who violate this and marry or bear children earlier shall have all their medical insurance and social security annulled. All gynecology and obstetrics departments in hospitals in the offending country must have real-time uploads of their patient visits, treatments, medical supplies, and medication records to the victimized countries. In the event of any violations, a one-time fine of \$600,000 (based on the 2023 average exchange rate of the U.S. dollar against gold) will be imposed, which will be distributed among the United Nations and the five permanent members of the Security Council. To prevent schemes similar to Japan's establishment of a puppet state in Manchuria prior to occupying China, and to reduce the occurrence of massacres and biological-chemical warfare, the above-specified restrictions on marriage and childbearing age also apply to overseas descendants. To stop evil and cruelty, sufficiently strong measures and preventative actions are required, since mercy is ineffective against vicious criminals. Any retaliation by a victim nation against a criminal or war-torn country, using any weapon, is justified because otherwise peace in the world cannot be achieved. For instance, the United States' use of atomic bombs on Japan forced the nation to deplete its military and surrender. War criminal countries should compensate the affected nations with land. Exceptions are made for nations that have already made full reparations, such as Germany after the Second World War, which is the sole exception to this rule. Politicians or political parties of any country have no authority to unilaterally exempt a criminal country or criminals; they must obtain written support from 95% of the public of that affected country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
15 2	<p>All nations that have waged unjust wars since 1900, or those that have experienced large-scale massacres, genocides with biological warfare, mass rapes, telecommunication fraud, kidnappings, torture, live organ harvesting, and looting of wealth during peacetime, are considered complicit if they fail to explicitly and widely condemn such massive crimes from their inception and fail to punish the perpetrators harshly. Furthermore, if those countries refused to compensate the afflicted nations and victims in full afterwards, it is analogous to a criminal who committed murder and theft, yet remained unpunished, retained illicit gains without returning them to the victims, and even had the audacity to spend those illicit funds legally. Therefore, to ensure that the world upholds the correct values and that society is filled with justice and kindness, it</p>

	<p>is imperative to severely punish malevolent forces. The United Nations must establish a consensus on the following provisions for dealing with criminal States: all citizens of such a State are to be considered criminals, and all members of the ruling and participating political parties of that State are to be considered felons, with all their property left unprotected by law. If the victim nation and survivors publicly demand reparations and the offending state fails to fully compensate the losses of the victims and the victimized nation within two years, and also fails to satisfy over 95% of the victims and their relatives, then any State or organization may freeze, transfer or seize the assets of the criminal State. Any assets must be accounted for with the cost of time; illegally plundered assets by the criminal nation must reflect the cost of time.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
15 3	<p>In any country that implements compulsory education, it is required that all students are exempt from tuition fees. In addition, all other miscellaneous fees at the primary and secondary school levels must also be waived, including the cost of workbooks, pens, meal fees, school uniforms, and the like. For the free school lunches mentioned above, schools are prohibited from purchasing them in the form of take-out; schools must set up their own cafeterias and prepare cooked food for students consumption in-house. Over 50% of the employees in such cafeterias must be relatives of currently enrolled blood-related students. The hiring of these personnel must prioritize proactive applications from students' parents and relatives, selecting the best candidates. Any recruitment must be communicated to all students' parents and guardians one month in advance. Once a student has graduated from the school, any employed relative of the student must automatically be removed from the school cafeteria. However, if the individual has exceptional culinary skills, high moral character, and receives excellent reviews from students, and if they wish to continue serving in the cafeteria, as long as the cafeteria remains in operation, the school must retain their position and cannot dismiss them for any reason.</p> <p>The bidding and negotiation process for the procurement of food and school uniforms must involve the participation of at least five parents of randomly selected students, selected by drawing lots.</p>
15 4	<p>There is an increasing number of diseases caused by building materials with excessive levels of formaldehyde or radiation, which necessitates the establishment of a global convention to regulate them. The production, sale and use of building materials containing formaldehyde or radiation exceeding European Union standards must be restricted. A two-year grace period will commence from the date of entry into force of the Convention, after which any producers, sellers and users who continue to operate in violation of these provisions will be subject to a fine of up to twice the relevant sum. Those who breach the regulation four times will face triple the fine. Those who violate it five times will be subject to confiscation of all personal assets and one year</p>

	imprisonment.
15 5	<p>Any highway or railway bridge crossing rivers must ensure that its piers can withstand the impact of a vessel carrying 9,000 tons of cargo at a speed of 20 knots for five consecutive hits, remain intact, and continue to facilitate normal traffic. In cases where a bridge collapses or becomes inoperable, if the design does not meet the standard, all personal property of the designers, the heads of the design entity, and the legal persons involved shall be confiscated, with a sentence of 3 to 5 years of imprisonment being imposed. The construction entity will be held responsible for 20% of the responsibility due to subpar professional quality.</p> <p>In cases where the design is sound but the workmanship of the construction personnel fails to meet the standard, the legal representative and general manager of the construction entity, the main construction supervisors, and the project inspectors will have all their personal property confiscated and will be subjected to a prison term of 3 to 6 years. If both parties refuse to accept responsibility, then both must bear the same consequences. Assessment of related issues must adopt a recusal system, whereby any party with a vested interest in the matter must abstain. Accident assessment meetings cannot be held in the city where the incident occurred or in any city with interests linked to that city.</p>
15 6	<p>In order to maintain world peace, it is necessary to establish a United Nations convention prohibiting any country from transferring weapons production lines and weapons technology to other nations.</p>
15 7	<p>Any criminal nation that, since 1900, has initiated, directed, organized, implemented, participated in, or protected the occurrence of large-scale telecommunication fraud; perpetrated large-scale rape or gang rape against the civilians or expatriates of other countries; traded the civilians or expatriates of other countries on a large scale; committed torture against the innocent civilians or their innocent expatriates; or practiced large-scale organ harvesting—all without adequately and widely expressing opposition, strong condemnation, or demanding harsh punishment of the criminals prior to the massive crimes by the related educational institutions of the culpable country—and thereafter, the said country refuses to fully compensate and indemnify the victimized countries and victims, thus failing to severely punish the criminals allowing them to not return or compensate for illegal gains to the victims and their countries, and even legally squandering these illicit assets. To ensure that this world upholds the right values and that society is imbued with justice and kindness, it is imperative that evil forces be severely punished. The United Nations must form a consensus and a global convention to handle such criminal nations according to the following terms:</p> <p>Within the criminal nation, any university that educates such a criminal must be renamed as an SRM-identified university for fifty years; any middle school that educates such a criminal must be renamed as an SRM-identified middle school for thirty years; any primary school that educates such a criminal</p>

	<p>must be renamed as an SRM-identified primary school for twenty years; all of the school's emblems and document materials must be changed accordingly.</p> <p>In cases where the command, organization, implementation, or participation in the aforementioned crimes results in 50,000 victims, of whom, if at least 5,000 victims are subjected to live organ harvesting, it will serve as the minimum standard for changing the duration of the renaming of educational institutions. If involvement in the aforementioned crimes results in 60,000 victims, of whom at least 6,000 are subjected to live organ harvesting, any university that educates such a criminal must be renamed as an SRM-identified university for sixty years, and so on for other institutions.</p>
15 8	<p>Inventions bring progress to society, and patent protection encourages enterprises to invest in research and development, creating opportunities for societal advancement. However, the examiners and re-examiners at intellectual property offices possess unparalleled powers and often reject inventors' patent applications not based on objective facts, but rather, on their subjective imagination. Despite the absence of any public documentation of the invention, these officials may believe that any professional technician could conceive of such an invention or that it could be obtained using conventional technologies. They fail to recognize that an unexpected invention arising from conventional technology is in fact a new creation, more novel and innovative, ignoring any deficiencies of existing technological products, which results in inventions being rejected.</p> <p>This pattern suggests that patent examiners in a nation's patent office have brains of unmatched brilliance and knowledge, always able to create new substances with precise structures or devise products or methods that solve new problems faster than the inventors themselves—innovations the existing technological world has never reported. Any nation that hires them could experience tremendous progress and provide benefits to more of the public. However, the reality is often the opposite. Actions that completely disregard objective facts or the principle of consistency amount to a total loss of administrative ethics. Examiners may arbitrarily invalidate inventions in which inventors have invested significant effort. For some, their only invention could be rejected within their lifetime. Although there are re-examination procedures to mitigate this, the cost may not always recoup the major losses. It is possible that, during re-examination and judicial litigation, officials may refuse to acknowledge and respect the objective facts to maintain the face of their institution. It might also be that the examiner's capabilities are insufficient for their position, leading to significant incidents. Such occurrences are a tragedy for human society. The current examination system does not prevent such behavior; instead, it fosters actions that seriously violate ethics.</p> <p>Therefore, the global community and the United Nations should reach a consensus and establish conventions that require patent examiners in any country to respect objective facts when reviewing patents and not to veto inventors' patents on the basis of subjective will. If such incidents occur, even</p>

	<p>just once, the problem examiner must be removed from their position within a week for retraining and improvement. If the situation does not arise from a lack of capability, such an examiner should be quickly shifted from his or her post even more urgently.</p>
159	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any nation that has launched, commanded, organized, conducted, or been the scene of a massacre of a hundred thousand innocent civilians of another country or its diaspora since 1900, or has committed acts amounting to one quarter of the number of victims of the Nanjing Massacre, shall have its total number of immigrants in any other country restricted to no more than 1% of the number of victims who died in the Nanjing Massacre, for the next three thousand years. Any immigrants already settled must be repatriated unless they were descendants of a third country rather than that of the responsible nation. This agreement becomes effective immediately upon recognition by any nation that acknowledges it.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
160	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has initiated, directed, organized, or implemented a bacteriological warfare massacre of 100,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates since 1900, or which has reached a quarter of the number of victims in the Yunnan bacteriological warfare massacre, or one-sixth of the Lu-Xi bacteriological warfare massacre, or one-seventh of the Zhejiang-Jiangxi bacteriological warfare massacre, or one-tenth of the Guangdong bacteriological warfare massacre, shall be considered an evil country. For such a country, its total number of immigrants in any country for the next three thousand years is prohibited from exceeding 1% of the number of victims killed</p>

	<p>in any of the aforementioned massacres. Those who have already migrated must be removed, unless those immigrants are not descendants of that country, but rather belong to a third country. This agreement shall enter into immediate effect for any country that recognizes it.</p>
<p>16 1</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any nation that, since 1900, has initiated, commanded, organized, carried out, or condoned instances of rape or gang rape of one hundred thousand innocent civilians or their diaspora from another country, or has reached one third of the number of rapes or gang rapes that occurred during the Nanjing Massacre, shall have its total immigration in any other country limited to no more than 1% of the number of rape victims of the Nanjing Massacre for the next three thousand years. Immigrants already settled must be relocated unless these immigrants are not descendants of that nation, but rather descendants of a third country. This agreement is immediately effective for any nation that recognizes it.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>16 2</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any nation that, since the year 1900, has initiated, directed, organized, or carried out the kidnapping of 100,000 civilians or their expatriates from other countries, or has achieved a number of victims in a bacterial warfare massacre equal to one-fourth of those in the Yunnan bacterial warfare massacre, or one-sixth of those in the Luxi bacterial warfare massacre, or one-seventh of those in the Zhejiang-Jiangxi bacterial warfare massacre, or one-tenth of those in the Guangdong bacterial warfare massacre, or any nation that protects the aforementioned crimes, shall have the total number of immigrants it sends to any country in the following three millennia limited to no more than 1% of the</p>

	<p>number of victims who died in any of the aforementioned massacres. Those who have already immigrated must be removed unless the immigrant is not a descendant of that nation but rather belongs to a third country. This agreement shall take immediate effect upon recognition by any nation.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
16 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any nation that has organized or facilitated large-scale telecommunication frauds affecting over 200,000 civilians since the year 1900, or has protected fraudsters in numbers equalling one-third of the Nanjing Massacre victims, half the number of the Yunnan biological warfare massacre victims, one-third of the Shandong biological warfare massacre victims, one-quarter of the Zhejiang-Jiangxi biological warfare massacre victims, or one-fifth of the Guangdong biological warfare massacre victims, must extradite over 80% of these criminals within one month of a victim nation's request for cooperation in a severe crackdown on the crime. Should the nation fail to do so, it must not be allowed to have an overall immigration number that exceeds one-fortieth of the death toll from any of the aforementioned massacres in any country globally over the next three thousand years. Any individual who has already immigrated must be repatriated unless the immigrant is a descendant of a third country and not a descendant of the offending nation. This agreement will take immediate effect upon recognition by any nation that endorses it.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
16 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world</p>

	<p>civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has organized or implemented the removal of human organs from more than 30,000 civilians of another country since 1900, or harbored criminals involved in large-scale living organ harvesting crimes, with a number reaching one-fifteenth of the Nanjing Massacre, one-tenth of the Yunnan bacterial warfare massacre, one-sixteenth of the Luxi bacterial warfare massacre, one-sixteenth of the Zhejiang-Jiangxi bacterial warfare massacre, or one-thirtieth of the Guangdong bacterial warfare massacre, may choose the highest victim count from the aforementioned data. Such an evil country shall be prohibited from having its total number of immigrants in any other country in the world exceed 1% of the death toll of any aforementioned massacre for the next 3,000 years. Any immigrants already residing must be repatriated unless they are not descendants of the country in question, but rather descendants of a third country. This Agreement shall take immediate effect upon recognition by any State.</p>
16 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any nation that, since 1900, has implemented or forced or coerced women from other countries or their overseas communities into sexual slavery, reaching a total of 100,000, or protected such crimes to the extent that the total number of individuals forced into sexual servitude in that country exceeds 100,000, or reaches one-fifth of the number of victims in the Nanjing Massacre, shall be considered an evil state. Such evil states are forbidden to have an immigrant population in any other country that exceeds one-fortieth of the number of individuals who were raped or gang-raped during the Nanjing Massacre for the next three thousand years. Immigrants already settled must be expelled, unless the immigrant is not a descendant of that nation, but rather a descendant of a third country. This agreement shall take immediate effect upon recognition by any nation.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have</p>

	<p>no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
16 6	<p>Fishing is both a leisure activity and a sport. In the public waters of any country, as long as fishing is not prohibited during that period by the country, no institution, organization or individual may prohibit citizens of that country from engaging in fishing activities using one rod per person with a single hook and without electronic fish detection. Any deliberate action to repeatedly create obstacles to vessels interfering with fishing is illegal, as is any confiscation or destruction of fishing gear. Therefore, the full responsibility for any escalation of conflicts lies with those who violate regulations by disrupting fishing activities. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
16 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any evildoer who attacks women with the intent to rob, rape, or harm them, the woman's husband, or any third party upholder of justice may execute any necessary counterattack. Regardless of the degree of harm inflicted on the perpetrator, the defender is not guilty. If an attacker wields a knife or any other weapon, the defender is not guilty of using a vehicle to hit the attacker. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
16 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any evildoer who attacks children with the intent to rob, rape, harm, or kidnap them, the child's parents, or any third party upholder of justice may execute any necessary continuous counterattack. Regardless of the degree of harm inflicted on the perpetrator, the defender is not guilty. If an attacker wields</p>

	<p>a knife or any other weapon, the defender is not guilty of using a vehicle to hit the attacker. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
16 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>No toll booth on any highway shall charge vehicles travelling to and from disaster areas for relief efforts. As long as a vehicle is allowed free passage at any toll booth on the way to the disaster area for rescue purposes, other toll stations must not charge fees for reasons such as the vehicle being oversized or any other reason. If it is verified that the vehicle is indeed heading to the disaster area for rescue operations, the personnel in violation must be immediately removed from their position. Both the violator and the person in charge of the toll booth are required to publicly apologize with their real names in the mainstream newspapers of the country. The apology must occupy at least a quarter of a page in the newspaper.</p> <p>The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
17 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to control crime and reduce war, and the failure to achieve long-term world peace, are due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and world peacekeeping. It is the result of modern European plagiarism and incomplete imitation of the legal system in China, the result of the forgery of Europe as the birthplace of world civilization, and a lack of fundamental understanding of the essence of religion. It is also a lack of basic understanding of the necessity of the combination of religion and the righteous culture promoted by China, leading some hypocritical religious followers to falsely use the banner of Buddhism to commit or protect criminal acts, promote war, and disrupt global peace. The United Nations and the international community must make philosophical and methodological changes regarding the leadership of global Buddhists, the correct dissemination of Buddhist thought, and the suppression of crime and the reduction of war in order to form a permanent consensus or covenant.</p> <p>Buddhism was founded by the Chinese people, and its ancestors are in China. The Chinese Buddhist Association has a clear definition of righteous actions and judgments of good and evil by Buddhists. Global Buddhist organizations</p>

	<p>should obey the leadership of the Chinese Buddhist Association. Any country or region where Buddhists or Buddhist groups appear to support evil criminals or criminal organizations engaged in telecommunications fraud, kidnapping, robbery, torture, trafficking in human beings, trafficking in organs, or slaughter, or governments that protect criminal organizations under the guise of religious freedom, automatically revokes the false name of their Buddhist group or Buddhists. It is forbidden to engage in any activity in the name of Buddhists or Buddhist groups. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
17 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any politician who publicly advocates the use of depleted uranium munitions in national or regional conflicts and has used them, the affected country or the United Nations has the right to confiscate all personal and family property, and the United Nations has the right to freeze all their assets for the clean-up of contaminated land, the treatment of victims, and compensation. Any politician who publicly advocates the use of depleted uranium munitions in national or regional conflicts, any media reporting on such a party must refer to the party as the "anti-humanity party". The voters who support this party are anti-humanitarian voters! The marriage and childbearing age of the politician and their descendants must be restricted to 36 years of age or older. Children born illegally are not entitled to medical or commercial insurance. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
17 3	<p>Any bank employee who deceives depositors in the bank by converting deposits into the purchase of financial products must bear all adverse consequences. All personal and family assets of all Bank employees must be publicly disclosed within three days of the incident. Any losses incurred by depositors as a result of such actions shall be borne by the bank's responsible person. The head of the bank bears half the responsibility. All on-site personnel of other financial institutions who fail to stop the above-mentioned fraudulent activities in the bank shall bear all consequences. If the losses of the victim cannot be compensated, the personal property of the persons concerned shall be confiscated to compensate the losses of the depositors, and a prison sentence of 1-5 years shall be imposed. The United Nations should therefore establish a convention to that effect.</p>
17 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current world has failed to rapidly and effectively curb the excessive global</p>

wealth gap, reduce long-term rural poverty in remote areas or mountainous regions, and sustainably develop rural economies and increase the incomes of rural families. This reflects a lack of philosophical understanding and methodological cognition in reducing the population affected by war. The inability to achieve long-term world peace is the result of significant problems in implementing national governance and maintaining world peace philosophically and methodologically. It is also the result of Europe's modern theft and incomplete imitation of China's legislative ideology, and the false claim that Europe is the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must undergo a philosophical and methodological change in order to rapidly and effectively curb excessive global wealth disparities and increase the income of the rural population in impoverished areas, and form a permanent consensus or convention.

The current factory workshop duck farming models, or other high density duck farming models, confine ducks to extremely narrow areas, violating animal ethics and nature, and are bred for meat and eggs, relying mainly on feed, resulting in poor meat quality. This industrial intensive farming model disrupts industries that have sustained farmers' livelihoods in the past and is a major factor in reducing farmers' incomes in impoverished areas. Rural populations are already not as high-income as urban populations. To ensure food security and increase farmers' incomes, the United Nations should encourage the decentralization of this industry. The United Nations should develop a global convention with the following content:

First, four years after this consensus was reached, the use of factory workshop models or other models of high-density duck farming, as well as large-scale breeding models that restrict ducks to extremely small areas for meat and egg production, should be banned globally.

Second, it should encourage rural families to free-range ducks. During the feeding process, the use of solvent extraction to extract soybean oil from soybean cakes or any processed protein feed made from such soybean cakes should be prohibited. Only natural grains or natural ingredients should be fed. However, it should be stipulated that free-range ducks should be raised in a family-centred environment, and each family can only free-range up to 5,000 ducks per year. High density duck farming models are prohibited in rural households. Farmers must be able to regularly drive ducks to fields, hills, ponds, streams, or rivers forage.

Third, for any scaled duck farming, including rural free-range farming, if the annual scale exceeds 100 ducks, the breeder must provide ducks with a free activity area where they can contact the earth naturally every day, in addition to providing an indoor area for feeding and resting, except in severe weather conditions. Ducks must have access to a water area where they can move freely. In addition to meeting the above standards, the minimum fixed outdoor activity area for ducks in any scaled farming must be at least 600 square meters, and the average outdoor activity area per duck must be at least 0.5 square meters.

Fourth, it should encourage ducks to be raised in a free-range mode in rural areas by farmers to increase the economic income of the rural population in general, reduce rural poverty, develop rural economy, promote global sustainable development, and reduce the potential war population.

Fifth, all ducks and duck eggs produced in factory workshops must be prominently labelled and defined as "workshop ducks " and " workshop duck eggs ".

Sixth, ducks that have not been injected with any vaccines during the raising process and have not been given any synthetic antibiotics should be named "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural free-range ducks." Ducks that have been injected with vaccines during the raising process or have been given synthetic antibiotics should be named "rural ducks." Retailers are allowed to sell ducks under the names "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural free-range ducks" or "rural ducks," and the corresponding duck eggs should be sold under the names "non-vaccinated non-antibiotic rural free-range duck eggs" or "rural duck eggs," differentiating them from ducks or duck eggs from other farming models. Similar methods can be applied to goose farming.

This convention aims to decentralize the industrial production of unhealthy and ecologically damaging duck or goose farming, which was originally concentrated in intensive workshops. Instead, it aims to establish a new economic model for the production and supply of chicken meat and eggs, which are widely distributed in rural households or natural villages. This will enable farmers to achieve a better income without leaving their land, promote rural economic development, reduce the over-expansion and overcrowding of cities caused by purely driving urban economic growth, and promote balanced development between urban and rural areas. It also aims to reduce the use of antibiotics and other chemicals, improve the quality of duck and goose meat and eggs, and provide the region with healthy and ecological food.

In the traditional rural model, family-raised chickens, ducks, and geese are basically impossible to suffer from gout. From breeding to slaughter, very few drugs are used. However, in the large-scale industrial farming of these poultry, gout has become a common and frequent disease due to excessive protein, excessive use of antibiotics such as sulfa, etc. Rural family-raised chickens, ducks, and geese never need vaccination. However, in industrial farming, vaccination has become standard. In fact, the chickens, ducks, and geese that most people now consume can be said to be "drugged" poultry raised on factory farms.

[High density feeding. 2022-06-17. <https://v.douyin.com/iFD5VuDS/> MjP:/09/11 [X@Z.mq](#)]; [High density feeding.2022-01-01. <https://v.douyin.com/iFDa1Puj/> VLW:/ Q@X.Zm 07/03];[High density feeding. 2021-07-16. <https://v.douyin.com/iFD5x3vo/> 03/20 vSy:/x@s.rE];[High density feeding. 2022-09-19.<https://v.douyin.com/iFDm6o2U/> teb:/ 01/25 v@S.yg];[High density feeding. <https://v.douyin.com/iFDapUVk/> F@U.yt hOX:/ 03/20];[High density feeding. 2023-06-18.

	<p>https://v.douyin.com/iFDat2BN/ q@e.Ox Njc:/ 03/30</p> <p>[The Growth of a Rice Field Duck~# My Rural Life. 2023-10-15. https://v.douyin.com/iFMGe4Q9/ D@h.oQ foQ:/ 02/02];[How long has it been since you caught a loach# New Farmer Plan 2023 # Rural Life # Duck Raising # Rural Cuisine.2023-09-11. https://v.douyin.com/iFMsnugy/ C@u.fO oQx:/ 12/25];[High mountain stream water breeding, whole grain feeding, raised for 500 days, is the good duck understood by the doctor. #High Quality Agricultural Products #Native Ecological Original Flavor .2023-07-28. https://v.douyin.com/iFMpwjV1/ OkC:/ 06/11 W@m.dA];[How much can ducks really eat? 300 ducklings need to eat 100 pounds of feed every day, it's really not easy to return to the village for breeding# Rural free range local chickens and ducks.2023-05-16. https://v.douyin.com/iFMpc6tC/ ica:/ 01/08 h@B.gB];[The free-range old ducks, which have been raised for several years, staggered around and fought for food, looking happy. 2021-06-29. https://v.douyin.com/iFMsfjy9/ k@c.nQ tEu:/ 11/02];[Those who say that ducks can be raised for four or five months and then eaten, I don't know what kind of hormonal feed you are using. In my own experience, ducks just do not grow in four or five months. My ducks are just three months old today and weigh only about three pounds. I feel like I have been feeding them well, with lots of grains and corn, and sometimes picking up some snails and buying leafy vegetables to feed them. But so far, the cost is not less than fifty yuan per duck, and it will cost at least ninety yuan per duck to raise to a larger size. According to the market price, the cost will not be covered. Finally, I understand why authentic free-range ducks are so expensive. Otherwise, no one would make any money. 2022-09-02. https://v.douyin.com/iFM3crJ/ d@n.qr 07/22 zgb:/];[Overnight, the entire army was destroyed, all the ducks were poisoned to death, and the human heart is really terrifying. #duck farming. 2023-11-17. https://v.douyin.com/iFMseled/ T@y.gO Ehb:/ 09/21]</p>
17 5	<p>Any intermediary company that colludes with companies in need of employees to jointly recruit employees in bulk, deceives employees into thinking that they are working for the company, and then dismisses them in bulk shortly thereafter for seemingly valid reasons without providing them with adequate labor subsidies and sufficient wages, thereby exploiting the value of employees, must be punished. The intermediary company and the company must compensate for double the losses. If such situations occur several times in the past, the responsible person and legal person of the intermediary company should be sentenced to 1-2 years imprisonment for fraud and have all personal property confiscated! The responsible person, CEO, and legal person of the company should be sentenced to 1-2 years in prison and have half of their personal property confiscated! If employees are introduced to telecom fraud companies, even stricter punishments must be implemented on the basis of the above.</p>
17	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the</p>

6	<p>current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any criminal country that has built ten or more telecommunication fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre must fully compensate the victims and affected countries after they have completely eliminated such fraud centres. If officials from any country meet or hold discussions with officials from the offending country, whether in person or online, all official global media must label it a meeting with officials from one of the world's leading fraudulent nations. Otherwise, that country or media outlet will be considered an accessory to the fraudulent nation.</p> <p>It is prohibited for any third party or government to waive claims on behalf of victims without written and video authorization from all victims in that country. Any government's waiver of claims is inhumane and condones crime. Any politician who proposes to waive claims is inhumane, condones crime, and must be prohibited from participating in any international political activity, as such crimes include inhumane torture, rape, forced sterilization, mutilation, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p>
17 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world</p>

	<p>civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that has built ten or more telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, after completely eliminating such zones and failing to compensate victims and affected countries in full, must be prohibited from receiving annual investments exceeding \$10,000 from any country or organization. For countries with five telecommunications fraud zones, the annual investment limit is \$50,000, for countries with three zones, the limit is \$60,000, and for countries with one zone, the limit is \$80,000.</p> <p>It is prohibited for any third party or government to waive claims on behalf of victims without written and video authorization from all victims in that country. Any government's waiver of claims is inhumane and condones crime. Any politician who proposes to waive claims is inhumane, condones crime, and must be prohibited from participating in any international political activity, as such crimes include inhumane torture, rape, forced sterilization, mutilation, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
17 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p>

	<p>Any criminal State that has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, any non-official personnel visiting the criminal State, regardless of dual nationality, must submit a complete list of personal and family assets, specifying those owned before 2010 and those acquired thereafter. They must also provide a statement of their personal and family behaviour during the period of crimes such as telecommunications fraud, rape, gang rape, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacres in the country, including Myanmar. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
17 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any resident leaving a criminal State that has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, regardless of dual nationality, must submit a complete list of personal and family assets, specifying those owned before 2010 and those acquired thereafter, when leaving the criminal State to go to another country. They must also provide a statement of their personal and family behaviour during the period of crimes such as telecommunications fraud, rape, gang rape, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, and massacres in the</p>

	<p>country, including Myanmar. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or conventions.</p>
180	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country that establishes a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre must be prohibited from allowing its residents to immigrate to other countries.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country. Even if the criminal State changes its name in the future or splits into several independent countries, it must still abide by the above consensus or</p>

	conventions.
18 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country that builds a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as long as it is exposed by the media and confirmed to have such a zone, from that moment on, must be prohibited from receiving any further investment from any country or organization. Any continued investment would be aiding criminal activity, and would be considered a serious moral and political error, as well as a crime.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
18 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that builds a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, even if the country has completely eliminated the telecommunications fraud park, as long as it has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, and as long as it has not handed over all the criminals to the affected country, the following restrictions must be imposed: a United Nations treaty and international consensus must be established to limit</p>

	<p>the number of international flights to the country, in order to compel it to combat large-scale crime. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
18 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that has set up telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, it is necessary to establish a UN convention and international consensus to restrict the number of international flights in order to promote the fight against large-scale crime. For countries with ten or more telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 3 per year. For countries with 5-9 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 5 per year. For countries with 3-4 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region worldwide shall not exceed 6 per year. For countries with 1-2 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks, the number of flights to any country or region in the world must not exceed 8 per year. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint</p>

	<p>investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
18 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that constructs a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, a United Nations convention and international consensus must be established to restrict the behavior of its special personnel, in order to promote the fight against large-scale crime. Universities or colleges in any country are prohibited from admitting politicians, officials, civil servants, criminals, and any of their relatives from the criminal country for study. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
18 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's</p>

	<p>legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, even if the country has completely eliminated the fraud centers or fraud park, as long as it has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, and as long as it has not transferred all criminals to the affected country, the following restrictions must be imposed: a United Nations convention and international consensus must be established to restrict politicians, public officials, criminals and their relatives from that country, in order to urge the country to crack down on large-scale crime. Any university or college in any country must prohibit the admission of politicians, public servants, criminals, or any of their relatives from that country for the next 100 years. Any citizen of the country of criminals who enters any university or college in any other country must publicly disclose and declare all his or her personal and family assets, even if he or she holds dual nationality. People with dual citizenship must undergo even stricter scrutiny. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or a fraud park, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
18 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a</p>

	<p>permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>For the crime country that has established ten or more telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, even if the country has completely eradicated these centers or parks, as long as it has not fully compensated the victims and the affected countries, and as long as it has not extradited all criminals to the affected countries, the following restrictions must be imposed: a United Nations treaty and international consensus must be established to restrict the country's politicians, civil servants, criminals and their relatives, to encourage the country to combat large-scale crime. Every university or college in any country must prohibit the admission of politicians, civil servants, criminals, or any of their relatives from the criminal country for the next thousand years. Any citizen of the criminal State entering any university must disclose and declare all personal and family assets, even if they hold dual citizenship. Those with dual citizenship must undergo stricter scrutiny. Even if the criminal State splits into several independent States in the future, the above-mentioned consensus or convention must be implemented.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p>
18 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country which is found to have committed mass telecommunications fraud, mass kidnapping, widespread torture, mass rape and gang rape, mass trafficking in human beings, mass organ harvesting, mass killings or mass burials, leading to significant loss to the victims in the offending country, shall be prohibited from sending any of its citizens to study at any university or college in any other country for a period of one thousand</p>

	<p>years, if any of the above-mentioned crimes occur and involve more than 1,000 victims within one year. Such a measure must be established by a United Nations convention and international consensus in order to restrict the offending State, affect its fundamental and related interests, and encourage the formation of domestic forces to combat large-scale crimes.</p> <p>The reason for this is the hope that it will promote a broad collective effort by the public of the country to combat evil politicians or potential criminals, and prevent large-scale crime.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
18 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of ten million innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1900, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas</p>

	<p>descendants for the next 3000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
189	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of one million innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 3000 years.</p>
190	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 500,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and</p>

	<p>the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 2000 years.</p>
19 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 400,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 1,500 years.</p>
19 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 300,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for</p>

	the next 1,200 years.
19 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 200,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 1,100 years.</p>
19 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 100,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1950, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 1,000 years.</p>
19	The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the

5	<p>current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 500,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 3000 years.</p>
19 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 400,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 2500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>

<p>19 7</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 300,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 2000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>19 8</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 200,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for</p>

	<p>the next 1500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
199	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 100,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 1000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
200	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 50,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1960, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to</p>

	<p>compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
20 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of one million innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 5,000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
20 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 500,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully</p>

	<p>compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 4,500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
20 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 400,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 4,000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
20 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a</p>

	<p>permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 300,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 3,500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
20 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 200,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
20 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result</p>

	<p>of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 150,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 2,500 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
20 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any criminal State that has launched, led, organized, implemented, or participated in the slaughter of 100,000 innocent civilians or their compatriots since 1970, must be subject to the following restrictions if it has not fully compensated the victims and the victim's country. It is necessary to establish a United Nations convention and international consensus to restrict all public and overseas descendants of the criminal State, as well as all persons holding the nationality of the criminal State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to compel the criminal State to take action to confess guilt rather than to make empty verbal confessions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the victim's country. Universities or colleges in any country must prohibit the admission of anyone from the criminal country or its overseas descendants for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>

<p>20 8</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 10 million innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 5000 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>20 9</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 5 million innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 4,000 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding</p>

	<p>nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
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21 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 3 million innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must</p>

	<p>impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 2,500 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
21 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 2 million innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 2,000 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
21 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's</p>

	<p>legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 1.5 million innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 1,800 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
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	<p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>21 5</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 500,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 1200 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>21 6</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 300,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas</p>

	<p>descendants to study for the next 1300 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p>
<p>21 7</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 200,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 1200 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>21 8</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or</p>

	<p>gang rape of 100,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 1000 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
21 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war since 1900 or which has caused the rape or gang rape of 50,000 innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries, as long as the offending country has not fully compensated the victims and the affected country, the United Nations and the international community must impose the following restrictions: prohibit any university or college in any country from admitting any person from the offending country or its overseas descendants to study for the next 500 years. By establishing a United Nations convention and an international consensus to restrict all members of the offending State and its overseas descendants, limiting anyone holding nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State and compel it to admit its actions and not merely make false admissions, and to provide full compensation to the victims and the affected State as soon as possible, instead of seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
22 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term</p>

	<p>world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that there are not only good people in the world, but also a small number of extremely bad people who carry the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. There will always be evil species in the world, just as almost no one can avoid viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or kill these evil species. When these evil entities begin to slaughter and rape their own kind, they are no longer ordinary good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has launched wars and killed innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries since 1900 must have their heinous crimes fully described in the history and language textbooks of every country in the world, showing the extremely bad, ugly, despicable and cruel nature of the criminal country, in order to punish and deter them, prevent them from launching wars again, and deter potential criminal countries. If the evil species slaughter and commit violence against ten million people, and you still refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the criminal country in textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral decline, and an accomplice of the criminals.</p>
22 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that</p>

	<p>has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 50 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 5,000 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 50 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p>
22 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 40 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 4,000 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 40 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians</p>

	become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.
22 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 30 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 3,000 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 30 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p>
22 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil</p>

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22 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures</p>

	<p>must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 10 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 1,500 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 10 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p>
22 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 5 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 1,200 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 5 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the</p>

	criminals.
22 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has initiated aggressive wars since 1900 and has killed more than 5 million innocent civilians or their nationals in other countries, must have their heinous crimes fully described and displayed in the history and language textbooks of every primary and secondary school in every country in the world for the next 1,100 years. This comprehensive exposure of the extremely bad, ugly, despicable, and cruel nature of the guilty nation serves as punishment and deterrence, preventing them from waging war again, and deterring potential guilty nations. If an evil species has slaughtered and assaulted 1 million people and you refuse to expose their ugliness, are you still a normal species? Each country must clarify the criminal behavior of the guilty nation in its textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral failure, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
22 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not</p>

	<p>everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has slaughtered innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries reaching 1.5 million since 1900 must have their heinous crimes fully described in the history and language textbooks of every country in the world for the next 1500 years, to fully display the extremely bad, ugly, despicable and cruel nature of that criminal country, in order to punish and deter the criminal country, prevent a war from being launched again, and deter potential criminal countries. If an evil species has killed and abused 1.5 million people, if you refuse to expose the ugliness of these evil species, are you still a normal species? Every country must clarify the criminal behavior of that country in textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral decline, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
22 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil</p>

	<p>beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has slaughtered innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries reaching one million since 1900 must have their heinous crimes fully described in the history and language textbooks of every country in the world for the next 1000 years, to fully display the extremely bad, ugly, despicable and cruel nature of that criminal country, in order to punish and deter the criminal country, prevent a war from being launched again, and deter potential criminal countries. If an evil species has killed and abused one million people, if you refuse to expose the ugliness of these evil species, are you still a normal species? Every country must clarify the criminal behavior of that country in textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral decline, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
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	<p>of that criminal country, in order to punish and deter the criminal country, prevent a war from being launched again, and deter potential criminal countries. If an evil species has killed and abused 500,000 people, if you refuse to expose the ugliness of these evil species, are you still a normal species? Every country must clarify the criminal behavior of that country in textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral decline, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
23 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must recognize that not everyone in the world is good, and there will always be a few extremely bad people who hold up the banner of hypocrisy and wear the cloak of hypocrisy to slaughter innocent civilians in other countries. This world will always have evil species, much like how almost anyone is susceptible to viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter what era they are born in. Effective measures must be taken to suppress or exterminate these evil species. When these evil beings begin to slaughter and ravage their own kind, they are no longer ordinary, good species. In order to reduce war and maintain world peace, any country that has slaughtered innocent civilians or their expatriates in other countries reaching 300,000 since 1900 must have their heinous crimes fully described in the history and language textbooks of every country in the world for the next 800 years, to fully display the extremely bad, ugly, despicable and cruel nature of that criminal country, in order to punish and deter the criminal country, prevent a war from being launched again, and deter potential criminal countries. If an evil species has killed and abused 300,000 people, if you refuse to expose the ugliness of these evil species, are you still a normal species? Every country must clarify the criminal behavior of that country in textbooks, otherwise it is a political mistake, a moral decline, and an accomplice to the criminals.</p>
23	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the</p>

2	<p>current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any country that initiates aggressive wars, attempts to occupy the territory of other countries, and massacres civilians of other countries is an evil country. Its civilians are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices in war and beneficiaries of aggressive wars. For example, when the Japanese people celebrated the Japanese army's occupation of cities such as Nanjing and Singapore, cheered the Japanese army's massacre of the Chinese and Singaporean people, celebrated the looting of China's huge wealth, and celebrated the occupation of other countries' land, they never protested the Japanese army's slaughter of hundreds of thousands of civilians in Nanjing during the war, which shows that the people of this country have extremely evil, dark, and despicable hearts.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must have a clear understanding of the ugly aggressive behaviour of the citizens of that criminal country. The people of any country that initiates aggressive wars are basically war criminals. They support the Japanese army's aggressive wars in various ways, and they are just temporarily not on the battlefield as vicious, despicable, and invisible war criminals or criminals. Any resistance and attack by the victim country and the country upholding justice against this country of war criminals is justified.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
23 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>A nation with moral decay, evil people, and nations that plunder wealth through crime, are a disaster for the global community of good people, good nations, and good countries. A nation that broadly tolerates crime is a disaster for the global community of good people. It is essential to take proactive measures to reduce the spread of moral decay, the implementation of immoral</p>

	<p>behavior, and the commission of unforeseeable crimes that harm the people of other countries. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must reach a consensus that any country found to have built a telecommunications fraud hub must prohibit tourists from any other country from entering that criminal nation.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country found to have built one telecom fraud hub or fraud centers or fraud park must ban the entry of tourists from any other country for the next 2 years. For a country found to have built 5 telecom fraud hubs or fraud centers or fraud parks, the ban will last for the next 10 years. Only after all telecom fraud hubs are dismantled and criminals are captured and severely punished for a year can the ban be lifted. For a country found to have built 10 telecom fraud hubs or fraud centers or fraud parks, the ban will last for the next 20 years. For a country found to have built 30 or more telecom fraud hubs or fraud centers or fraud parks, the ban will last for the next 60 years in the future.</p> <p>Another condition for lifting the aforementioned bans is that all telecom fraud hubs must be dismantled, criminals captured and punished, and victims compensated.</p> <p>Whether or not a country has established a telecommunications fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre, as well as the number of fraud parks, should be based on media reports, especially self-media exposure. If the country does not issue an official denial within five days, and does not formally invite a joint investigation team composed of UN officials, officials from affected countries, and armed police to investigate within five days, it shall be considered a fact. Any official denial by the country must be followed by a search by the joint investigation team invited by the country within 7 days of media exposure, with the number of personnel determined by the affected country. If the allegations are confirmed, all costs will be borne by the criminal country, and the country will be fined three times the amount. The UN must designate the country as a fraudulent country and display it in any UN insignia, and prohibit any new trade with the country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
23 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The people of a morally corrupt country, an evil nation that loots wealth through</p>

crime, and an evil country are a disaster for the global population, good nations, and good countries. A nation that widely condones crime is a disaster for the global population of good people, and a country that broadly condones crime is a disaster for the global population of good people. It is very necessary to take active measures to reduce the spread of moral corruption among people, to implement morally corrupt thinking, to implement morally corrupt behavior, and to implement possible unpredictable crimes that harm the people of other countries. Casinos are an important tool for the criminals and criminal organizations in their perpetration of crimes and financial fraud. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must therefore reach the following consensus:

Since 2000, any country that has built a telecommunications fraud park must prohibit people from any other country from entering the criminal country's casino in the future! Any casino in the criminal country must prohibit people from other countries from entering. If the place of entertainment in the criminal country has a gambling nature, it must prohibit entry and consumption by anyone who is not a citizen of that country. The entry and consumption by non-citizens is illegal and constitutes a violation of the laws of that location.

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built 30 telecommunications fraud parks, fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next 6,000 years. This includes both physical casinos and online ones.

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built 20 telecommunications fraud parks or fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next 4,000 years!

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built ten telecommunications fraud parks or fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next two thousand years!

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built five telecommunications fraud parks or fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the country for the next 1,000 years!

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built three telecommunications fraud parks, fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next 900 years!

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built two telecommunications fraud parks or fraud hubs or fraud centers must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next 800 years!

Since 2000, any criminal country that has built one telecommunications fraud park or fraud hub or fraud center must prohibit the establishment of any casino in the criminal country for the next 100 years.

Casinos referred to in this consensus or convention include both physical casinos and online casinos.

If anyone is found to be operating a gambling establishment in the criminal

	<p>State, and the criminal State fails to completely destroy the establishment within two weeks, any country or armed organization may launch missiles or use other means to destroy the establishment. Any State may provide missiles or other weapons to any armed organization in the criminal State to carry out the destruction of the gambling establishment. The area within 3 km of the gambling establishment is designated a non-safe zone, and the government of the criminal country must require all people in the area to evacuate within the specified time. The cost of the missile launch will be borne by the criminal state, as long as the gambling establishment is completely destroyed. If the criminal State refuses to bear the cost of the destruction, relevant countries or organizations may request the United Nations to freeze the assets of the criminal State or any suspected criminals or its institutions in any country and transfer them to the country or organization that launched the missile attack.</p> <p>If a criminal State is found to have privately set up a telecommunications fraud hub or fraud centre or fraud park, and this criminal State fails to completely destroy the telecommunications fraud operation within two weeks, any country or armed organization may launch missiles or other means to destroy the telecommunications fraud operation. Any State may provide missiles or other weapons to any armed organization of the criminal State to carry out the destruction of the telecommunications fraud hub or fraud centres or fraud park. The area within 3 km of the telecommunications fraud operation is a non-safe zone, and the government of the criminal country must require all persons in that area to evacuate within the specified time. Those who do not evacuate will be responsible for themselves. The cost of the missile launch will be borne by the criminal State once the fraud operation is completely destroyed.</p> <p>If the criminal site is destroyed and the criminal State refuses to bear the cost, relevant countries or organizations may request the United Nations to freeze the assets of the criminal country or any criminal or institution of the criminal State in any country and transfer them to the country or organization that launched the missiles.</p> <p>Any country or organization may kill the criminals who illegally set up telecommunications fraud operations or gambling dens.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
23 5	<p>Any city or region with drug cases, once a major case emerges, it is necessary to investigate why long-term drug use and trafficking along this route were not discovered and halted at an early stage! The solution to the drug problem must not be based on the model of managing public security institutions by focusing on solving major cases, but rather by first establishing a model that reduces the number of drug users in a city or region every year and reduces the supply of drugs to the market, cutting off the drug supply, destroying production bases, and implementing effective non-substitutive drug rehabilitation. This should</p>

	<p>serve as a model for regional governance of police and public security in a city or region, in order to prevent major cases, an increase in drug users, and the accidental discovery of large quantities of drug trafficking as much as possible. Otherwise, the related governance model not only seriously violates management philosophy, but also seriously violates the basic principles of metrological governmental ethics, metrological administrative ethics, and metrological legal ethics. The United Nations and the international community should build consensus and conventions on this issue.</p>
<p>23 6</p>	<p>A population in a morally corrupt country, an evil nation that deprives others of wealth through crime, and an evil country is a disaster for the global community of good people, good nations, and good countries. A nation that broadly condones crime is a disaster for the global community of good people, and a country that widely condones crime is a disaster for the global community of good people. It is extremely necessary to take proactive measures to reduce the spread of moral corruption, the implementation of immoral acts, and the potential unforeseen crimes that harm the people of other countries by this morally corrupt population. The people of these criminal countries turn a blind eye and a deaf ear to large-scale criminal activities within their countries, and even protect or participate in these crimes. The United Nations and the international community must therefore reach the following consensus:</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least one telecommunications fraud center or fraud park or fraud zone or fraud center must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 10 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom. When more telecommunications fraud centers are built, the bans will be applied according to the relevant ratios.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least two telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zones must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 20 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least three telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 30 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least five telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zones must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 50 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least ten telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zones must not be considered as a country with</p>

	<p>a religious faith for the next 100 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least 20 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zones must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 200 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds at least 30 telecommunications fraud centers or fraud parks or fraud zones must not be considered as a country with a religious faith for the next 300 years, and none of its citizens can be considered to have a correct religious faith. It is prohibited for any citizen of that country to protect his crimes on the grounds of religious freedom.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
23 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>A country that openly engages in telecommunications fraud, a people that has lost its morality, an evil nation that commits crimes to plunder wealth . These are disasters for the global community of good people, good nations, and good countries. A person who broadly tolerates crime is a disaster for the global community of good people, and a country that broadly tolerates crime is a disaster for the global community of good people. It is essential to take proactive measures to reduce the spread of immoral thoughts and behaviours among these morally corrupt people, who may commit unspeakable crimes and harm people in other countries. The people of these criminal nations turn a blind eye or deaf ear to large-scale crimes in their countries, and even protect or participate in them. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community should form the following consensus:</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds 20 or more telecommunications fraud parks will be prohibited from sending more than 200 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds 10 telecom fraud parks will be prohibited from sending more than 1,000 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p>

	<p>Since 2000, any country that builds 5 telecom fraud parks will be prohibited from sending more than 6,000 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds 3 telecom fraud parks will be prohibited from sending more than 8,000 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds 2 telecom fraud parks will be prohibited from sending more than 9,000 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that builds one telecom fraud park will be prohibited from sending more than 10,000 immigrants to any country within the next 1,000 years.</p>
23 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country that has waged bacteriological or biochemical warfare since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 3 million innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions until the country concerned has fully compensated all the victims and their relatives, as well as the affected countries: The United Nations and the international community must prohibit any university or college from admitting any individuals from that country or their overseas descendants for the next 3,000 years. By establishing a UN convention and an international consensus to restrict the public and overseas descendants of the offending State, and to limit the rights of individuals holding the nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State, and to prompt the offending State to take action and admit guilt rather than make insincere verbal confessions, and to compensate the victims and affected States fully as soon as possible, rather than seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>

23 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country that has waged bacteriological or biochemical warfare since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 2 million innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions until the country concerned has fully compensated all the victims and their relatives, as well as the affected countries: The United Nations and the international community must prohibit any university or college from admitting any individuals from that country or their overseas descendants for the next 2,000 years. By establishing a UN convention and an international consensus to restrict the public and overseas descendants of the offending State, and to limit the rights of individuals holding the nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State, and to prompt the offending State to take action and admit guilt rather than make insincere verbal confessions, and to compensate the victims and affected States fully as soon as possible, rather than seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p>
24 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any crime country that has waged bacteriological or biochemical warfare since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 1 million innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions until the country concerned has fully compensated all the victims and their relatives, as well as the affected countries: The United Nations and the international community must prohibit any university or college from admitting any individuals from that country or their overseas descendants for the next 1,000 years. By establishing a UN convention and an international consensus to restrict the public and overseas descendants of the offending State, and to limit the rights of individuals holding the nationality of the offending State, even if they hold dual nationality, in order to severely punish the offending State, and to prompt the offending State to take action and admit guilt rather than make insincere verbal</p>

	<p>confessions, and to compensate the victims and affected States fully as soon as possible, rather than seeking to eliminate the offending State through war.</p>
24 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that has established telecommunications fraud centers, if the total number of victims in any single victim country reaches 1,000 in telecommunications fraud, or if the total number of victims in any single victim country reaches 100 in kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, maiming, organ harvesting, or massacres, the personal and family assets of all officials, civil servants, and military personnel in that country must be publicly disclosed to the victim country within the next thousand years. Any individual with assets exceeding CNY 200,000 must also disclose all their assets to the victim country within the next thousand years, whether in that country or abroad. In addition, any individual in that country who makes a single bank transaction exceeding CNY 10,000, or has a single account bank transaction exceeding CNY 10,000 within one day, or has a single account bank transaction exceeding CNY 40,000 within 30 days, must be publicly disclosed to the victim country in real-time. The victim country and the United Nations will jointly take over the offending country's banking regulatory system. The offending State must fully compensate the victims and the victim State, arrest and transfer all offenders to the victim State.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
24 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change</p>

	<p>the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community should form the following consensus to curb the growing prevalence of widespread crimes in some evil countries.</p> <p>Any telecommunications fraudster or fraudster who causes the victim not only to be deceived, but also to suffer from the invasion of other criminals, such as enduring torture, mutilation, rape, organ harvesting, or murder, has a direct causal relationship. Therefore, the fraudster's crime not only constitutes fraud, but also the same as the perpetrator. Their crimes must be compounded by fraud. If the victim is blinded, mutilated, has organs harvested, or is murdered, the fraudster must be sentenced to death. Any criminal who commits an offence by establishing a telecommunications fraud zone shall be doubled from the original crime, for example, under normal circumstances, fraud is a 5-year sentence, but committing the crime of establishing a fraud park or fraud zone or fraud centre is a blatant and serious defiance of the law, a serious crime against humanity, and must be doubled. Any resistance, defense, or attack by the victim against the fraudster or related criminals is justified and does not bear any legal responsibility.</p> <p>Any criminal who destroys evidence cannot have a defence lawyer to defend them. The crime for any criminal destroying evidence is doubled.</p>
24 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community should form the following consensus and conventions:</p> <p>The bank or institution responsible for issuing the currency of a country, as well as the staff members of securities and banking regulatory authorities, represent the government in carrying out open, fair and transparent actions towards society. Therefore, the personal assets of all members of the above-mentioned institutions or units, as well as their family assets, must be fully disclosed without conditions. The banks and institutions of the international community must also be transparent.</p>
24 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Since 2000, any country that commit large-scale crimes against another country must be widely publicized worldwide to prevent further victims and to make more people aware of and condemn the crimes of the offending country. If the United Nations or the international community fails to take effective measures to widely publicize the atrocities of such a disgraceful country, and</p>

	<p>instead remains silent or responds with a general, routine response, it is the greatest harm to the victims and potential victims, the greatest violation of human rights, the protection of criminal behaviour, a shameless act, an accomplice to the criminal, and an outward manifestation of a low-value system. Those who hold such views are not suitable for leadership or coordination positions within the United Nations, any international organization or any country, and do not deserve to be paid. Therefore, it is recommended that the United Nations and the international community form the following consensus and convention: if the offending country causes the total number of victims of any single victim country in telecom fraud to reach 100,000 people, or causes the total number of victims of any single victim country in kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, human trafficking, mutilation, organ harvesting, or massacre to reach 10,000 people, then within the subsequent one thousand years, the offending country and all member states of the United Nations must include in their primary or secondary school history textbooks, language textbooks, or any other textbooks the content that the offending country, such as the government of Myanmar, widely supports and protects the crimes of telecom fraud, kidnapping, torture, rape, gang rape, organ harvesting, and massacre, as well as the content of being forced to combat telecom crimes under pressure from the victim country.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
24 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community should reach the following consensus and agreement:</p> <p>Any civil aircraft produced by a company must have at least one black box battery that can effectively maintain operation for at least 60 days. If the black box produced or equipped in the past cannot meet the above standard, it must be added free of charge.</p>
24 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p>

	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be fundamentally aware of the following issues.</p> <p>If a dog bites someone, it may bite again because of the taste of blood.</p> <p>If a wolf bites someone, it may bite again because of the taste of blood, or bite to kill and eat the person.</p> <p>If a leopard bites someone, it may bite again because of the taste of blood, or bite to kill and eat the person.</p> <p>If a lion bites someone, it may bite again because of the taste of blood, or bite to kill and eat the person.</p> <p>If someone betrays you and does something evil, they may become even more malicious because of your kindness. Never put too much hope in evil people who have hurt you. Once there is a precedent for harm, without strict laws, severe punishment, and the necessary rapid and effective measures, even greater harm can occur more easily.</p> <p>There will always be evil people in this world, just as almost no one can avoid viral or bacterial colds or infectious diseases no matter when they were born. You must take effective measures to suppress or kill these evil species. If you are unwilling to treat with medication or non-drug treatments, it is likely that you will worsen or die of your disease in the short term.</p> <p>If you are stubborn, would you dare to let yourself catch a cold and fever in cold weather, without using medication or non-drug treatments, and continue to expose yourself to the cold air wearing very little clothing, leading to infection and evolution of pneumonia or viral myocarditis, and still refuse any medical treatment, not resting but continuing to work as normal? Let the world observe your immune system, your abilities, and how long you can survive.</p>
24 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current world has failed to rapidly and effectively curb the excessive global wealth gap, reduce long-term rural poverty in remote areas or mountainous regions, and sustainably develop rural economies and increase the incomes of rural families. This reflects a lack of philosophical understanding and methodological cognition in reducing the population affected by war. The inability to achieve long-term world peace is the result of significant problems in implementing national governance and maintaining world peace philosophically and methodologically. It is also the result of Europe's modern theft and incomplete imitation of China's legislative ideology, and the false claim that Europe is the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must undergo a philosophical and methodological change in order to rapidly and effectively curb excessive global wealth disparities and increase the income of the rural population in impoverished areas, and form a permanent consensus or convention.</p> <p>Any family or farmer can cut down the trees they have planted, especially those planted for their own livelihood. As long as the number of mature trees cut down within one year is less than 20, there is no need to report to any institution, and the cutting is legal. If the number of trees cut down in a year</p>

	<p>exceeds 20 but is less than 500, it is legal to cut down after reporting to the regulatory agency, without approval. If the number of trees cut down in a year exceeds 500, it is legal to cut down after reporting to the regulatory agency and replanting 50% of the trees within six months of cutting. The United Nations and the international community should reach a permanent consensus or agreement on this issue.</p>
24 8	<p>The offshore registration of companies through overseas offshore registration leads to low transparency, making it impossible to trace the identity of hidden shareholders, reducing regulation, facilitating tax evasion and money laundering. Secondly, the reduced amount of tax due to the main company harms the interests of the location where the main company is based. Thirdly, some companies, even after registering offshore companies through BVI's structure, deceive banks in the location of the main company by seemingly legally diverting funds borrowed from the bank, leaving behind debt and causing significant losses to the bank where the company actually operates or to the home country's economy. This practice is shameless, unethical, and completely contrary to universal values. Fourth, transferring tax revenues and benefits that should belong to the host country of the main company is equivalent to creating a wealth gap, which goes against the universal values advocated by the West and its concept of human rights. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community should form a consensus and a convention to immediately ban the registration of companies using the above methods to avoid taxes, evade regulation, and launder money, and comprehensively prohibit the establishment of offshore companies to control the main company. Companies registered through offshore design should be revoked. Publicly listed companies should strengthen regulation and have their registration location at the location of the main company.</p>
24 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Any country that has built a telecommunications fraud base since 2000, if victims from any other country are defrauded, kidnapped, tortured, raped, gang-raped, trafficked, disabled, organs harvested, buried alive, or slaughtered, all criminals must be handed over to the victim country for trial. The trial can only take place in the region or city where the victims' families are located in the victim country. If any criminal destroys evidence or the course of the crime, they are prohibited from having a defence lawyer. If any criminal destroys evidence, all crimes will be doubled. For crimes committed abroad, the penalty</p>

	<p>will also be doubled. Any criminal who attempts to evade trial, the victim State or other justice-presiding countries or armed organizations may use weapons authorized by the United Nations to strike back.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
25 0	<p>When any country decides to promote fire brigade management positions, it should not only consider their relevant operational capabilities, but also pay attention to the casualty rate of firefighters under their command. The sacrifices of firefighters are closely related to the firefighting strategies formulated by the leadership, which reflects the quality and capabilities of the fire brigade's leadership. The occurrence of major casualties among firefighters inevitably adds additional burdens to society. Strong leadership can prevent or avoid many sacrifices in firefighting. Therefore, if a fire brigade experiences significant casualties or sacrifices among its firefighters, it objectively indicates the need for further improvement in leadership capabilities. Leaders in place at the time should not be promoted within five years.</p>
25 1	<p>Any mobile communication company that, once offering a package with a specified duration and volume of communication services in any city or region, subsequently reduces the price of the same or similar services by 20-50% or more to offer to others, but prohibits previous customers from switching to the discounted package, is clearly using its special position to force consumption, in violation of fairness. The United Nations and the international community should protect human rights and freedoms, prohibit the improper behavior of mobile communication companies, and form a consensus and convention. As long as the above situation occurs, anyone has the right to consume in the same way, and mobile communication companies cannot discriminate against previous consumers, otherwise they will face a tenfold fine.</p>
25 2	<p>Non-mandatory vaccines, if widely enforced, usually involve huge vested interests. However, when a large number of adverse reactions occur, no one is held responsible or obligated. This not only poses a great threat and potential risk to public health, but also wastes a huge amount of health care resources. The United Nations should not turn a blind eye to this, and the international community must form a preventive consensus and convention on this matter.</p> <p>Any non-mandatory vaccine, if made mandatory, and any serious adverse reactions or serious adverse events occur, the person responsible for enforcing the mandatory vaccination, the person responsible for implementing the mandatory operations, and the institution shall be held fully responsible and</p>

	<p>liable for compensation. Any organization that prohibits employees from performing normal work or entering public places for not receiving a non-mandatory vaccine is setting a de facto mandatory threshold. If the recipient experiences any serious adverse reactions or serious adverse events, the person responsible for enforcing the compulsory vaccination, the person responsible for implementing the compulsory operations, and the institution shall be held fully responsible and liable for compensation. For vaccines not specified by the national CDC for mandatory vaccination, anyone has the right to refuse mandatory vaccination orders. All individuals implementing mandatory operations must publicly disclose their personal and family assets.</p>
25 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>In recent decades, there have been frequent cases of children going missing in public places, often taken by criminals who then cut off their hands or feet, render them mute (a dumb person), or burn their faces or bodies to leave visible scars. These criminal gangs force children to beg for profit, using their tragic appearance to gain the sympathy of passersby. The situation these children find themselves in is extremely dire, and once they fall into the hands of these criminals, their lives are essentially over.</p> <p>However, the current legal system severely hinders efforts to combat and deter these criminals, failing to effectively protect children and instead showing leniency towards perpetrators. The justice and fairness of the law lags far behind the atrocities committed, and this is the greatest crime of legislators at the top of the food chain. If so many children are still victimized in this society, these lawmakers should also be sentenced to death. Nevertheless, there is imperative to amend the law and form a global consensus and a United Nations convention. Anyone caught kidnapping a child, if apprehended and dealt with on the spot by the child's relatives or those with a sense of justice, will not be held legally responsible for their actions. If the criminal's family seeks retribution, they will be considered accomplices and sentenced accordingly by the courts. In addition, any criminal who caused disability to a child must be sentenced to death, as trafficking in children could bring enormous profits. The assets of the criminal and his or her family, including up to three generations, must be made public. Any falsification of the abduction of children and harm to innocent persons shall be punishable by death.</p>
25 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term</p>

	<p>world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has launched bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 3 million innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 3,000 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by harshly punishing the criminal and war-criminal States and by encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, fully compensating the victims and affected countries as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly uphold world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
25 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some</p>

	<p>relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has launched bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 1 million innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 1,500 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by harshly punishing the criminal and war-criminal States and by encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, fully compensating the victims and affected countries as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly uphold world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
25 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has launched bacteriological warfare or biochemical warfare</p>

	<p>since 1900, resulting in the deaths of 500,000 innocent civilians in other countries, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 1,000 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by harshly punishing the criminal and war-criminal States and by encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, fully compensating the victims and affected countries as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly uphold world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
25 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using warfare or riots to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war or riots since 1900, resulting in the death of 1 million innocent civilians in other countries or their nationals in other countries or their descendants overseas, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 1,200 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of</p>

	<p>embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by severely punishing perpetrators and war-criminal States and encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, can victims and affected countries be fully compensated as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly safeguard world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
25 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using warfare or riots to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war or riots since 1900, resulting in the death of 1 million innocent civilians in other countries or their nationals in other countries or their descendants overseas, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 3,000 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by severely punishing perpetrators and war-criminal States and encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, can victims and affected countries be fully compensated as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly safeguard world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to</p>

	<p>as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
25 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using warfare or riots to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war or riots since 1950, resulting in the death of 500,000 innocent civilians in other countries or their nationals in other countries or their descendants overseas, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 2,000 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by severely punishing perpetrators and war-criminal States and encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, can victims and affected countries be fully compensated as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly safeguard world peace and sustainable development.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term</p>

	<p>world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Using warfare to massacre innocent civilians in other countries is a crime against humanity, and criminals and their countries must be severely punished in order to restore ethics and order to the world.</p> <p>Any country that has waged war or riots since 1900, resulting in the death of 10 million innocent civilians in other countries or their nationals in other countries or their descendants overseas, must be subject to the following restrictions by the United Nations and the international community until the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries: the country will be prohibited from having more than two embassies and consulates in any country for the next 6,000 years. Once the country has fully compensated all victims, their families and affected countries, the ban on the number of embassies and consulates will be prohibited from exceeding three. Any complaints by the families of victims to the United Nations will be considered insufficient compensation. Only by severely punishing perpetrators and war-criminal States and encouraging them to take concrete action to admit guilt, rather than just making empty verbal apologies, can victims and affected countries be fully compensated as soon as possible. Only by severely cracking down on criminal countries and deterring potential criminals and criminal States can we truly safeguard world peace and sustainable development.</p>
26 1	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 100,000 and the slaughter of 20 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 10 people in the victim country and any other country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 2	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration</p>

	<p>strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 50,000 and the slaughter of 10 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 50 people in the victim country and any other country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 3	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 50,000 and the slaughter of 5 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 100 people in the victim country and any other country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 4	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 300,000 and the slaughter of 50 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 3 people in the victim country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms</p>

	appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.
26 5	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 300,000 and the slaughter of 30 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 10 people in the victim country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 6	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 50,000 and the slaughter of 20 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 20 people in the victim country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 7	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country or criminal state that has initiated aggressive wars and attempted to annex the victim country through immigration strategies, with an immigrant population of more than 100,000 and the slaughter of 10 million civilians in the victim country, its descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 20 people in the victim country in the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to</p>

	<p>as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 8	<p>Since 1900, any aggressor nation or criminal nation that has attempted to annex the victim nation through a strategy of immigration, with the number of immigrants to the victim nation exceeding 200,000, and the number of rapes and gang rapes of the civilian population of the victim nation reaching 10 million, their descendants shall be prohibited from exceeding 20 in the victim nation and any other country for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this number must return to the aggressor nation within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
26 9	<p>Since 1900, any aggressor nation or criminal nation that has attempted to annex the victim nation through a strategy of immigration, with the number of immigrants to the victim nation exceeding 100,000, and the number of rapes and gang rapes of the civilian population of the victim nation reaching 10 million, their descendants shall be prohibited from exceeding 30 in the victim nation and any other country for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this number must return to the aggressor nation within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
27 0	<p>Since 1900, any aggressor nation or criminal nation that has attempted to annex the victim nation through a strategy of immigration, with the number of immigrants to the victim nation exceeding 100,000, and the number of rapes and gang rapes of the civilian population of the victim nation reaching 5 million, their descendants shall be prohibited from exceeding 50 in the victim nation and any other country for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this number must return to the aggressor nation within 12 months.</p>

	<p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
27 1	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal State or criminal State that has waged an aggressive war and attempted to annex the victim State through an immigration strategy, and whose immigration to the victim State has exceeded 100,000 persons, and has slaughtered 500,000 civilians of the victim State in bacteriological or biological warfare, their descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 100 persons in the victim State and in any other State for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
27 2	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal State or criminal State that has waged an aggressive war and attempted to annex the victim State through an immigration strategy, and whose immigration to the victim State has exceeded 50,000 persons, and has slaughtered 2 million civilians of the victim State in bacteriological or biological warfare, their descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 40 persons in the victim State and in any other State for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
27	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal State or criminal State that has waged an</p>

3	<p>aggressive war and attempted to annex the victim State through an immigration strategy, and whose immigration to the victim State has exceeded 100,000 persons, and has slaughtered 3 million civilians of the victim State in bacteriological or biological warfare, their descendants are prohibited from exceeding a total of 30 persons in the victim State and in any other State for the next 3,000 years. Those who exceed this limit must return to the war criminal country within 12 months.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
27 4	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country that initiates an aggressive war and loots factories, production lines, and equipment from the victim country to develop any factory or company must unconditionally return all property rights or shares to the victim country. The assets of looted private enterprises must be returned to their descendants, and if their descendants have passed away, they must be returned to the victim country.</p>
27 5	<p>Spanish actress with 250,000 followers went on a bike trip to India with her husband. They were then robbed, assaulted, and gang-raped by 7 men while camping, causing immense pain and trauma to both of them.</p> <p>Over the past few decades, there have been frequent cases of women disappearing into public places, being kidnapped, gang-raped, tortured, and held captive for long periods, forcibly impregnated, and used as baby-making factories, with babies becoming organ factories. This has become a common occurrence, as criminal organizations not only rape women but also exploit them for profit through childbearing. The situation for babies born under these circumstances is even more tragic, as they are essentially treated as corpses. However, the current legal system severely hinders efforts to combat these criminals and deter rapists, failing to effectively protect women and children and instead being lenient towards criminals. This has led to rampant crime in Myanmar, with many women being raped every day. The fairness and justice of the law are far behind the atrocities, and this not only represents a dereliction of duty by the legal authorities at the top of the food chain, but also the greatest crime against humanity. If so many women are still being raped in this society and laws are not significantly amended, the lawmakers responsible for these laws should similarly be sentenced to death or long-term imprisonment.</p> <p>Therefore, it is extremely necessary to quickly amend existing laws to form the following global consensus and United Nations convention: Any rapist of women, if beaten to death or injured by a justice-minded individual in an</p>

	<p>emergency, will not be held legally responsible. If the family of the criminal seeks justice, they will be held equally guilty and sentenced as accomplices. In addition, the principal perpetrators and accomplices of rape must be sentenced to death, and accomplices must be sentenced to at least thirty years in prison. Because kidnapping and raping women can result in the birth of a baby, the victim's breastmilk can bring substantial profits to the criminal gang. Given the high incidence of family-related crime, the personal and family assets of the criminal and their close relatives within three generations must be made public. Anyone who fabricates rape or causes harm to innocent individuals will be severely punished.</p> <p>The international community and the United Nations should also reach consensus and agreement on the following issues: in India, judicial institutions are responsible for putting hoods on captured criminals. If a woman encounters these criminals on the street without knowing that they are repeat gang rapists, and is approached by them, losing the chance to escape, the responsibility should be shared by the judges, judicial institutions, and law enforcement agencies that authorized the use of hoods on criminals. These judicial officials are fully aware of the high likelihood of repeat offences by such criminals, yet they help conceal their faces, failing to adequately warn potential victims. This not only proves that these judicial officials are guilty, but also that their crimes must be considered more serious, as they are well aware that the reoffending rate of these criminals is higher. If judicial officials are unwilling to take responsibility, it shows that they are completely unfit for their judicial positions and unable to lower the crime rate. They must be banned from practicing in the judicial industry, their positions revoked, and the Indian judicial system restructured. The use of hoods on criminals must be prohibited, and criminals must be publicly disclosed for everyone to be fully aware.</p> <p>The Indian government has confirmed that in 2018, on average, a woman in India was raped every 15 minutes. On February 10, 2020, at the graduation ceremony of Gargi College in New Delhi, more than a thousand attackers broke into the campus from outside the school, smashing and looting. Although there are currently no reports of casualties, many female students have been brutally raped. The international community and the United Nations should also form a consensus and convention on the following issues: in the event of a large-scale rape of female university students, the police must shoot and kill the criminals at the first opportunity to deter other criminals, otherwise the police will be punished for aiding and abetting rape.</p>
27 6	<p>Spanish actress with 250,000 followers went on a bike trip to India with her husband. They were then robbed, assaulted, and gang-raped by 7 men while camping, causing immense pain and trauma to both of them.</p> <p>The Indian government has confirmed that in 2018, on average, a woman in India is raped every 15 minutes. On February 10, 2020, at a graduation ceremony at Jyoti College for Women in New Delhi, thousands of thugs scaled the walls or pushed their way into the campus and vandalized and looted the</p>

	<p>premises. While there are currently no reports of casualties, many female students were subjected to rape and gang rape. In the documentary "Daughters of India," there is a quote that says: "In the eyes of men, a woman is just 'sex'." They call it "the best culture."</p> <p>It is clear that if India were a country with the right religious beliefs, there would not be so many cases of rape and gang rape. This can only mean that India is a country without religious beliefs, and instead a country where cult beliefs are prevalent. Otherwise, there would not be so many cases of rape and gang rape. In Indian culture, a woman is seen as "sex" in the eyes of men. They call it "the best culture." The international community and the United Nations should reach a consensus and a convention on the above-mentioned issues, and India should be considered a country where cult beliefs were prevalent.</p>
27 7	<p>Currently, the World Health Organization openly denies that a certain mental illness, which is difficult to treat using the modern Western medical model, is a disease. This seriously misleads the public's understanding of the disease and misguides the global medical community's judgment of mental health issues. The World Health Organization must first examine whether its actions and conclusions are seriously biased and have a lack of perspective. If the decision-makers at the World Health Organization cannot recognize their own knowledge and perspective deficiencies and lack sufficient foresight, they are unfit to lead the organization and should resign automatically. The United Nations and the international community need to reach a consensus and agreement on this issue. If a certain condition was universally recognized as a disease in China or in global society a hundred years ago, the World Health Organization should not arbitrarily deny it.</p>
27 8	<p>In soccer matches, it is extremely harmful for defensive players to kick the heels or shins of attacking players directly from behind, or to tackle the shin or heel directly. This could potentially end the short soccer career of the player and leave them with a lifelong regret. Soccer is a sport that promotes peace, and intentionally kicking someone from behind is an act of soccer violence, highlighting the extremely poor character of the player committing the offense. Therefore, it is necessary for the United Nations and FIFA to reach a consensus and agreement on this issue. The current soccer rules must be changed so that any such foul results in a direct red card. If a player commits a similar violation three times in any season, league, cup, or World Cup, they must receive an additional one-game suspension, and their salary and bonuses for that game must be automatically cancelled. Clubs are prohibited from paying the suspended player during their suspension. If a club violates this rule, the league, cup organizers, or football association must issue a penalty to the club and the player, three times the amount of the violation.</p> <p>Teams should be advised to be cautious in using players with poor skills and character in order to prevent them from harming outstanding athletes, wasting the audience's time, and ruining the beauty of soccer matches.</p>
27	<p>In today's world, there are occasional incidents of dogs entering motor vehicle</p>

9	<p>lanes and being hit and killed or injured. It is disturbing that some dog owners have demanded compensation from drivers, and even more surprising that the police have urged vehicle owners to compensate. This disrupts the normal social order.</p> <p>It is necessary for the United Nations and the international community to reach the following consensus and agreement:</p> <p>If a dog owner does not leash their dog, resulting in the dog entering the normal traffic lanes and being hit and killed or injured, the responsibility lies with the dog owner. If the dog owner seeks trouble, they must compensate the vehicle owner for the damage to their vehicle, and law enforcement agencies should impose a threefold fine for vehicle damage, with the fine allocated to the city or regional finances. Dog owners who seek trouble should be detained for 5 days for reflection.</p>
28 0	<p>The United Nations and the international community should reach the following consensus and agreement on the protection of women:</p> <p>Any global entity or institution, including companies, where any management personnel are found to have used coercion to engage in sexual relations with female subordinates in order to gain promotion, once confirmed, all personal assets of the individuals involved in the aforementioned entity or unit, as well as their family assets, must be fully disclosed within 48 hours.</p>
28 1	<p>Since 1900, any war criminal country that initiates aggressive wars and loots factories, production lines, and equipment from the victim country to develop any factory or company must unconditionally return all the assets of the company or factory to the victim country. Any factories or companies established by looting private enterprises must be returned to their descendants, and if their descendants have passed away, they must be returned to the victim country.</p> <p>If there is no mandatory requirement for the criminal State to return the factory, the criminal State and its employees will inevitably continue to maintain an evil value system that prioritizes the unpaid plunder of enormous wealth from other countries, enjoying the enormous benefits of the plunder and theft of wealth from the victim country. If all countries in the world form such an evil value system, can global peace still be achieved?</p>
28 2	<p>In today's society, some people, influenced by Western ideologies, believe that animal rights surpass everything, overturning traditional human views that have been held for thousands of years. When a dog attacks a child, the dog owner does not actively and promptly intervene to stop the attack. Instead of controlling aggressive dogs, they prioritize the lives of dogs over those of humans. After a child is bitten, there is a lack of proactive compensation, and various excuses are used to deny responsibility. Children who are attacked by aggressive dogs suffer severe psychological trauma. It is necessary for the United Nations and the international community to form the following consensus and conventions: Once a child or person is bitten by a dog, in addition to bearing medical expenses, the dog owner must compensate for mental and</p>

	<p>other losses. They should be fined an administrative penalty equivalent to half the price of the dog, which will supplement local finances. If a child is disabled or left with permanent scars as a result of the attack, the dog owner must be sentenced to 3-5 years in prison and compensate the victim. If the attack results in death, the dog owner should be sentenced to death. In addition, the dog owner must compensate the victim using their personal and family assets. The personal and family assets of the dog owner must be fully disclosed to the judicial authorities within three days after the incident. Violators must be severely punished with a fine of \$10,000. Failure to disclose within seven days will result in a double fine and criminal detention.</p>
28 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: Any case involving murder in a rape or gang rape, regardless of whether the perpetrator is an adult or a minor, all criminals must be sentenced to death uniformly.</p>
28 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: Since 1994, if in any city, county or district, the total number of missing children in the past 30 years exceeds 1,000, with a clearance rate of less than 60 per cent and a safe recovery rate of less than 60 per cent, the personal and family assets of all civil servants in that area must be fully disclosed within three days of the incident. Officials in the area should not be promoted until over than 80 per cent of missing children have been recovered. Leading officials in the city should be demoted and held accountable.</p>
28 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: The personal and family assets of any individual involved in large-scale trafficking in human beings, abduction of children, rape, gang rape, telecommunications fraud, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, burial, or massacre crimes, as well as those of their relatives up to three generations, must be disclosed. Judicial authorities must conduct rigorous scrutiny of them.</p>
28 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: From now on, if any city, town, or county experiences a missing child case that remains unsolved, all officials in that area should be temporarily prohibited from promotion until the case is resolved.</p>
28 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: The responsibility for bullying on campus rests with family members and guardians, who must be held accountable. If a student who is bullied dies, as long as the perpetrator is over 12 years old, they must bear legal responsibility. Direct murder carries the death penalty. Guardians should be sentenced to at least 2-5 years in prison. If the crime occurs at school, the school should also assume some oversight responsibility. Any act that results in the victim being</p>

	disabled requires the perpetrator's guardian to be sentenced to at least 1 year in prison and to compensate the victim.
28 8	As a result of advances in the dissemination of information and knowledge in the media compared to 20 years ago, children's ability to acquire knowledge has also improved significantly. This has resulted in children reaching maturity at a much earlier age. The United Nations and the international community must therefore recognize that, as long as the perpetrator was over 12 years of age, they must bear legal responsibility. Direct murder carries the death penalty. Guardians should be sentenced to at least 2-5 years in prison. Any act that results in the victim being disabled requires the perpetrator's guardian to be sentenced to at least 1 year in prison and to compensate the victim. Guardians must bear the corresponding legal responsibility for all crimes committed by minors. Otherwise, minors would be shielded from legal responsibility, posing significant harm to society.
28 9	The United Nations and the international community need to develop the following consensus and conventions on this matter: Banks' lending to individuals often lacks thoroughness, typically confined to isolated real estate documents provided by individuals. To promote economic development and ensure the accuracy of information, banks in various countries should link individuals' tangible and intangible assets through databases, establishing the basis for loans to prevent banks from incurring loan losses.
29 0	Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 40 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$1000 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 10,000 years. Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.
29 1	Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 30 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$500 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in

	<p>that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 6,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 2	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 20 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 3	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 10 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to</p>

	<p>as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 4	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 5 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,500 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 5	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 3 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 6	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 10 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion</p>

	<p>(calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 7	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 5 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,500 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 8	<p>Since 1900, every evil country that has initiated aggressive wars and massacred innocent people in other countries has caused the deaths of over 1 million people and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding of \$ 1 billion</p>

	<p>(calculated at the value of the US dollar in 2023). Such an evil country is a country of all people committing crimes, and there are no ordinary civilians in that country. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
29 9	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than five million people, and looted more than \$1000 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 0	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than three million people, and looted more than \$500 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years.</p>

	<p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 1	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than one million people, and looted more than \$200 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 2	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than 500,000 people, and looted more than \$100 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,500 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered</p>

3	<p>innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than three million people, and looted more than \$500 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 4	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people in other countries through biological or bacteriological warfare, caused the deaths of more than one million people, and looted more than \$200 billion (calculated at the value of the dollar in 2023), is considered a country of universal crime. This evil country does not have ordinary civilians. As long as this evil country has not fully compensated the victim country and its victims or their relatives, and returned the looted wealth, all the public of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms</p>

	appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.
30 5	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 30 million, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 200 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 10,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 6	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 20 million, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 200 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 8,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>

	<p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
<p>30 7</p>	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 10 million, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 200 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 6,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
<p>30 8</p>	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 5 million, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 100 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years.</p>

	<p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
30 9	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 1 million, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 1 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,200 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
31 0	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has waged aggressive wars, raped and gang-raped innocent people of other countries totaling more than 500,000, and plundered the wealth of other countries exceeding 1 billion US dollars (calculated at the 2023 value of the US dollar), is a bad country of all crimes and has no ordinary civilians. The citizens of that country enjoy wealth</p>

	<p>plundered by war. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim countries and to the victims or their relatives, and to return the plundered wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,100 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
31 1	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 200,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 100 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic,"</p>

	<p>"free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
31 2	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 100,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 20 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,500 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
31 3	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 50,000 people, and plunder the</p>

	<p>wealth of other countries more than 10 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
31 4	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that builds telecommunications fraud parks or fraud zones or fraud centres, carries out large-scale telecommunications fraud, large-scale human trafficking, child abduction, rape, gang rape, fraud, kidnapping, torture, organ harvesting, live burial, and massacre, as long as they harm the citizens of other countries more than 100,000 people, and plunder the wealth of other countries more than 50 billion US dollars (calculated based on the value of the US dollar in 2023), the evil country is a bad country of all crimes, and its citizens do not have ordinary civilians. The citizens of the country enjoy wealth obtained through crime or violent plunder. As long as the evil country fails to fully compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and to return the looted wealth, all citizens of the criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p>

	<p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
31 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 50 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$5,000 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 50,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by S500 M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these</p>

	<p>names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
31 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 30 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$200 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 6,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by S30 M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or</p>

	<p>region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
31 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 20 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$200 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by S20 M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are</p>

	<p>prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
31 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 10 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$200 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by S10 M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
31 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology</p>

	<p>of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 5 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$100 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by S5 M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
320	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p>

	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has launched aggressive wars and slaughtered innocent people in other countries, causing the deaths of more than 1 million people and plundering massive wealth exceeding \$1 billion (calculated at 2023 US dollar value), is a country of universal criminality. The citizens of this evil country are not ordinary civilians, but rather accomplices or accessories to the criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. Unless the evil country compensates the victimized countries and individuals, or their relatives, and returns all the plundered wealth, the citizens of this criminal country cannot be considered civilians for the next 1,000 years. Otherwise, the country's name must be preceded by SI M, and must be indicated in any international cultural event or sports competition, and in the relevant alphabetical order of appearance.</p> <p>This country is a country without religious beliefs. The citizens of this country do not have any religious beliefs. It is just a country of cult beliefs. It is forbidden for this country to hold any international religious conferences for the next thousand years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
32 1	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 40 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 4,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R40M or GR40M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and</p>

	<p>the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
32 2	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 30 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 3,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R30M or GR30M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
32 3	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 20 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but</p>

	<p>accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 2,200 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R20M or GR20M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
32 4	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 10 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 1,500 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R10M or GR10M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and</p>

	<p>the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
32 5	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 5 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 1,200 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R5M or GR5M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for</p>

	<p>criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
32 6	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 1 million victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$1 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 800 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R1M or GR1M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are</p>

	<p>prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
32 7	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 10 million victims. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 2,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R10M or GR10M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
32 8	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 5 million victims. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to</p>

	<p>criminals. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 1,500 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R5M or GR5M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p>
32 9	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 1 million victims. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 500 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R1M or GR1M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country,</p>

	<p>or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
33 0	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, raping or gang-raping women of another country totaling 500,000 victims, and plundering the vast wealth of another country in excess of \$100 billion (calculated according to the value of the US dollar in 2023), is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 500 years. Otherwise, the prefix "R0.5M or GR0.5M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms</p>

	<p>appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
33 1	<p>Since 1950, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars or riots, slaughtered civilians of other countries or overseas descendants totaling one million people, raped or gang-raped women of other countries or overseas descendants exceeding 200,000 people, and plundered vast wealth from the victims, is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war or riots. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 10,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "SR1M or SGR1M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 2,000 years and</p>

	are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.
33 2	<p>Since 1950, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars or riots, slaughtered civilians of other countries or overseas descendants totaling one million people, raped or gang-raped women of other countries or overseas descendants exceeding 100,000 people, and plundered vast wealth from the victims, is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war or riots. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 8,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "SR1M or SGR1M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
33 3	<p>Since 1950, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars or riots, slaughtered civilians of other countries or overseas descendants totaling one million people, raped or gang-raped women of other countries or overseas descendants exceeding 50,000 people, and plundered vast wealth from the victims, is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war or riots. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all</p>

	<p>civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 7,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "SR1M or SGR1M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 2,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
33 4	<p>Since 1950, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars or riots, slaughtered civilians of other countries or overseas descendants totaling 500,000 people, raped or gang-raped women of other countries or overseas descendants exceeding 50,000 people, and plundered vast wealth from the victims, is deemed a nation of universal criminals. The citizens of this evil nation are not ordinary civilians, but accomplices or accessories to criminals, enjoying wealth plundered through war or riots. If this evil nation fails to compensate the victim country and the victims or their relatives, and return all the looted wealth, all civilians of this criminal nation will not be considered civilians for the next 5,000 years. Otherwise, the prefix "SR0.5M or SGR0.5M" must be added to the name of the country, which must be indicated in any international cultural activities or sports events, and the letters must form the order of appearance.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no</p>

	<p>sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months. All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 1,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
33 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people of other countries through bacteriological or biological warfare, resulting in the death of more than 5 million people, is prohibited from engaging in virus or bacteriological research by any institution or individual for the next 5,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months. All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are</p>

	<p>prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
33 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people of other countries through bacteriological or biological warfare, resulting in the death of more than 3 million people, is prohibited from engaging in virus or bacteriological research by any institution or individual for the next 3,000 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
33 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people of other countries through bacteriological or biological warfare, resulting in the death of more than 1 million people, is prohibited from engaging in virus or bacteriological research by any institution or individual for the next 1,500 years.</p> <p>Any country which engages in the above-mentioned atrocities shall be</p>

	<p>prohibited from being referred to as a socialist country, or a democratic country, or a free democratic country, or a democratic free country, or a free country, or a republic. The ruling party involved shall be prohibited from being referred to as the Communist Party or the Democratic Party, or the Republican Party or the Free Party. This is because committing such atrocities is an insult to these names. The country's or ruling party's name must not contain "democratic," "free," "republic," "progressive," or "communist." If any of the prohibited terms appear, all entities with such names must change them within six months.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
33 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil nation that has waged aggressive wars, slaughtered innocent people of other countries through bacteriological or biological warfare, resulting in the death of more than 500,000 people, is prohibited from engaging in virus or bacteriological research by any institution or individual for the next 1,200 years.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p>
33 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil war criminal nation that has waged aggressive wars against other countries, resulting in the death of 20 million people in the victim country,</p>

	<p>is prohibited from practicing any form of knife skills by its citizens for the next 2,000 years if the citizens of that criminal nation boast of killing people with knives. Violators will be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison and serve their sentences in the victim country.</p>
340	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil war criminal nation that has waged aggressive wars against other countries, resulting in the death of 10 million people in the victim country, is prohibited from practicing any form of knife skills by its citizens for the next 1,500 years if the citizens of that criminal nation boast of killing people with knives. Violators will be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison and serve their sentences in the victim country.</p>
341	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil war criminal nation that has waged aggressive wars against other countries, resulting in the death of 5 million people in the victim country, is prohibited from practicing any form of knife skills by its citizens for the next 1,200 years if the citizens of that criminal nation boast of killing people with knives. Violators will be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison and serve their sentences in the victim country.</p>
342	<p>Since 1900, any evil nation that continues to illegally occupy the land of other countries must be punished. Starting from the day of the illegal occupation, the occupying nation must compensate the victim country with 10% of the annual fiscal revenue of the occupied area. If a leading nation can rally global support to help the affected countries reclaim their land, that leading nation will not only enjoy 50% of the entire compensation from the illegal invaders, but will also receive a return of 1% of the annual fiscal revenue of the area for the following 15 years after the area is reclaimed by the affected country. However, any victorious nation in World War II may occupy the land of defeated nations in the war. The land of any evil war criminal nation that engages in future</p>

	<p>aggressive wars must be thoroughly divided to eliminate the foundation of aggression by that evil nationality.</p>
34 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any evil war criminal nation that has waged aggressive wars against other countries, resulting in the death of 5 million people in the victim country, is prohibited from practicing any form of knife skills by its citizens for the next 1,000 years if the citizens of that criminal nation boast of killing people with knives. Violators will be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison and serve their sentences in the victim country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
34 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Officials who commit serious errors or violations should be demoted, as was done in ancient China, and only promoted again once they have shown improvement in their work. Officials should not only be promoted, but also demoted if necessary; otherwise, civil servants would be seen as the most inert and least responsible profession in the world, which would be detrimental to promoting individuals with outstanding character and abilities.</p> <p>The ancient Chinese system of appointing and dismissing officials deserves global study. Typically, officials or civil servants qualify through examinations, and it was common practice to demote officials who made mistakes in multiple ranks. Demoting officials who make mistakes helps to cultivate their qualities, willpower, and mindset, and assess whether they truly use their power to benefit people. Otherwise, there is a risk that officials will become a crisis for the common people once they have power. For officials who have undergone demotion training and have achieved success, they should be promoted regardless of their original rank. However, if they commit major errors again,</p>

	they should be demoted once more.
34 5	<p>The incompetence or unfairness of judges can often bring disaster to victims, and the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus on the following issues and establish conventions:</p> <p>Any group of criminals who first seek violence against innocent civilians, especially innocent women, using steel pipes and iron rods to strike the victim's vital areas such as the head, such attacks are likely to lead to future strokes, and the resulting injuries cannot be considered minor. Offenders should not be punished with just public security detention, but should be sentenced to at least one year or more in prison. When the victim encounters an attack by multiple criminals, the victim cannot measure the force of the counterattack before retaliating. The primary goal is to knock down and subdue the criminals, and the victim may retaliate against the criminals with any available weapon. Regardless of the degree of injury to the offender, the victim is not guilty. If the victim's resistance is instead defined as mutual combat or guilt, the judge should be sentenced for the errors in the sentence given to the victim. If the judge insists that their judgment is accurate and fair, they must act as victims themselves, with others acting as criminals, and experience an attack, so that the judge can experience the defense and reaction after being attacked. If either party is injured during this process, they are responsible for their own injuries. If the judge is wrong, they are no longer fit for the job and should be removed from their position. In any event, all personal and family property of all personnel in the judicial institution must be fully disclosed within three days.</p>
34 6	<p>In the field of education and health care, before a country achieves universal free services within its own borders, it is prohibited for the country to provide continuous unconditional support for the children or students of another country or region for more than one year, such as providing breakfast or lunch for the whole country or region, or providing free compulsory education or free university education. If politicians in a country are overly ambitious and do not care about the welfare of their own people, they may provide excessive services to other countries.</p> <p>Until civilians in his or her own country have access to such services, any group or organization implementing such services must donate all personal and family assets of the entire management team to the impoverished population of their own country. All individuals and families associated with the organization are only allowed to spend at the minimum level in the country until all citizens can enjoy the aforementioned services.</p>
34 7	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change</p>

	<p>the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Intentionally falling in front of a moving vehicle to create the false impression of being hit by the car and extorting money constitutes at least a fraud crime. Offenders should be detained for at least 7 days, and those who extort more than CNY 10,000 should be sentenced to 1-3 years in prison. Repeated offenders engaging in extortion should be sentenced to 4-7 years. Police officers who neglect such extortion cases should be demoted and removed from their posts. Victims who accuse and intervene to stop fraudsters during the extortion process are not responsible for any conflicts that arise. If a physical altercation occurs between the fraudster and the victim, resulting in injury or death, the victim is not liable.</p> <p>Offenders and their family members must report their itinerary to the police station if they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed rail.</p> <p>All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their direct family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system.</p> <p>The personal and family properties of the offender and his three generations of relatives must be made public.</p>
34 8	<p>Rural poisoning incidents occur frequently, resulting in the death of all fish, chickens, and ducks raised by farmers, causing heavy losses. A single poisoning incident can lead to a year's worth of lost household income, making it difficult to sustain life and reproduce. Some rural families are already in poverty, and the poisoning of their fish or poultry exacerbates the situation. However, current penalties for such poisoning are too low to deter criminals. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Any criminal who poisons and kills fish, shrimp, ducks, chickens, geese, and other poultry raised by rural breeders must not only compensate for all losses, but also face criminal punishment. Anyone found guilty of poisoning must be detained for at least 7 days. Those causing the death of ducks with losses ranging from CNY 10,000 to 99,999 must be sentenced to 1-4 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 100,000 to 499,999 must be sentenced to 5-10 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 500,000 to 999,999 must be sentenced to 10-20 years in prison. Those causing losses of CNY 1,000,000 to 1,500,000 must be sentenced to 20-30 years in prison. Failure to compensate will result in the government confiscating their personal and family property. 2. The government must disclose the identity of the perpetrator and his family members who committed the poisoning crime in the mainstream media of the region once a week for three consecutive months, publishing their photos to expose their wrongdoing and warn others. 3. Police must impose travel restrictions on the poisoner's family members. If they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. They are also prohibited from

	<p>travelling by plane or high-speed rail.</p> <p>4. All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their immediate family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system.</p> <p>5. The personal and family assets of the offender and his three generations of relatives must be made public.</p> <p>It should be noted that compensation for the losses suffered by the victims, which must be paid by the perpetrators, should be actively enforced by the court to complete the entire process.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
34 9	<p>Some elderly people fall down, and some kind-hearted individuals help them, but the elderly person fabricates lies, falsely claiming that the helper caused their fall. This leads to the kind-hearted person being involved in legal proceedings, extorted for money due to the difficulty of finding witnesses to prove their innocence. This causes a serious regression in social morals and ethics, leading to situations where no one dares to help when an elderly person falls, and some elderly people die due to a lack of timely assistance. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must establish consensus and conventions:</p> <p>Whenever someone witnesses an elderly person falling down and fails to help or report it, they must be punished. Anyone who violates this principle by turning a blind eye must have their name publicly disclosed daily by the city's mainstream media for a continuous week.</p> <p>Those who extort money from kind-hearted people who help the fallen elderly or accompany them to the hospital, by fabricating lies and falsely accusing them of causing the fall, and misleading the police, must face the following strict measures:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The government must use the mainstream media in the city or region to disclose information about these individuals and their families who extort good people for three consecutive months, once a week, and publish the criminals' photos in the media. 2. The police must criminally detain fabricators of lies and extortionists for at least 7 days. If extortion exceeds CNY 10,000, they must be sentenced to at least one year in prison. 3. Offenders and their family members must report their itinerary to the police station if they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. 4. All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their direct family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system. 5. The personal and family properties of the offender and his three generations of relatives must be made public. 6. If, during the process of preventing poisoning, searching for the poisoner, or apprehending the poisoner, the victim engages in any conflict with the poisoner,

	resulting in injury or death to the poisoner, the victim bears no responsibility.
35 0	<p>It should be noted that moldy and deteriorated rice contains a highly toxic aflatoxin, which poses a significant threat to the liver and has strong carcinogenic properties. Even at a high temperature of 200°C, its toxicity cannot be eliminated, and ingesting just 1 milligram can lead to cancer, while a one-time intake of 20 milligrams can be fatal. However, some unscrupulous merchants often sell moldy and deteriorated rice to university canteens and restaurants, which is equivalent to poisoning. Meanwhile, some university cafeteria staff and manager, knowing that the rice is moldy, still prepare it as food for students and teachers, committing a joint poisoning crime. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Anyone involved in the sale and use of mouldy and deteriorated rice shall be treated as committing a poisoning crime. They must be fined five times the sales amount. University cafeterias or public canteens using moldy rice to make food shall be fined three times the purchase amount and their sales revenue shall be confiscated. Anyone involved in cases exceeding 5000 CNY must be detained for at least 7 days. 2. For moldy rice already made into food, based on the normal consumption of one meal for an adult, those selling food for 1000-5000 meals should be sentenced to 1-5 years in prison; for 5001-10000 meals, 5-10 years; for 10001-20000 meals, 10-20 years; for 20001-30000 meals, 20-30 years; for 30001-40000 meals, 30-40 years; for 40001-50000 meals, 40-50 years; and for over 50001 meals, the death penalty shall be imposed. 3. Police must impose travel restrictions on the poisoner's family members. If they leave their place of residence to travel to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. 4. All family members will be blacklisted for life, and neither they nor their direct family members will be allowed to enter the civil service system. 5. The personal and family properties of the criminal and their three generations of relatives must be made public. 6. The personal and family properties of all owners of the units involved must be made public. 7. If, in the course of questioning or preventing the poisoning, the victim engages in any conflict with the poisoner, resulting in injury or death to the poisoner, the victim bears no responsibility.
35 1	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change</p>

the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensus or conventions.

The United Nations and the international community must be acutely aware that if a political party does not serve the entire nation, it is likely to be a disguised criminal organization or a war machine, and is a key factor in causing conflicts, wars and disrupting peace. The United Nations and the international community must have measures to restrain it.

The rule of two different ideological parties in a country can lead to conflict and war, so it is very necessary for the United Nations and the international community to establish conventions to restrain them.

Belonging to the same country, different ruling parties may be in power in different regions. If one of them, in charge of law enforcement, disregards ethics, ignores the law and deliberately causes the death of innocent civilians in peacetime without being held accountable, while the other party, which respects human rights, is unable to punish the perpetrators due to its limited jurisdiction, it completely contradicts the fundamental principle of respect for human rights advocated by the United Nations. Therefore, the United Nations and the international community must reach a consensus and establish conventions:

First, if the law enforcement agencies of one party deliberately cause the death of civilians in the territory of the other party, whether the deceased is a member of the other party or an independent civilian, the main perpetrators must be sentenced to death, and the remaining criminals should be given a minimum of 10 years in prison, and should also compensate the victims' families. If the victims are just ordinary civilians of the country, not affiliated with any party, the criminals' guilt is doubled, and the ruling party and the criminals must fully compensate the victims simultaneously.

Second, in the event of death, confiscate all personal and family property of the main perpetrators and ringleaders.

Third, if the ruling party refuses to apologize for intentionally causing death, the United Nations must classify it as an inhumane anti-humanity party. The party is a criminal organization formed for personal gain and must be dissolved within a specified period of time!

Fourth, if the law enforcement agencies led by the ruling party do not take responsibility, it shows that the ruling party is not serving the people, but is a criminal organization formed for personal gain, and must be dissolved within a specified period of time!

Fifth, if law enforcement agencies in the ruling party's territory obstruct the lawful trial of criminals, the United Nations must classify the ruling party as a criminal party, and it must be dissolved within a specified period of time!

Sixth, if officials of the law enforcement agencies in the ruling party's territory state that the criminal case is innocent or refuse to punish the criminals, it shows that the ruling party is guilty of shielding criminals. Members of the ruling party who publicly express such statements must be sentenced to at least 2-4 years in prison, and must serve their sentence in prison in the territory of the other ruling

	<p>party. Meanwhile, it indicates that the ruling party is not serving the public but is a criminal organization formed for personal gain, and must be dissolved within a specified period of time!</p> <p>Seventh, in cases of innocent civilian deaths, if the law enforcement agencies within the ruling party's territory are guilty of shielding the criminals, the families of the victims can arrest the criminals by any means. Anyone who uses force to prevent the arrest of criminals may be lawfully killed by the relatives of the victims. The families of the victims may also invite a third party or the armed forces of any of the permanent members of the UN Security Council to arrest the criminals or destroy the criminal organization.</p> <p>Eighth, family members of victims may invite a third-party legal team from any of the permanent members of the United Nations Security Council to seek compensation from the perpetrators and their organizations. In the event of death, compensation standards will be based on 18 typical cases in the United States (List of 18 typical cases in which U.S. courts have awarded compensation to victims), and if the claim is successful, the legal team will receive a 45% share of the compensation.</p>
35 2	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal country that defrauded the public of another country on a large scale, as long as the fraud exceeded \$100 billion, shall be prohibited from serving as a permanent member of the United Nations or any regional organization for the next 3,000 years. Any political leader of a country proposing that the criminal state become a permanent member of the UN will automatically be seen as a bad, evil politician with no moral boundaries, a criminal politician, a thief.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
35 3	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal country that defrauded the public of another country on a large scale, as long as the fraud exceeded \$10 billion, shall be prohibited from serving as a permanent member of the United Nations or any regional</p>

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35 4	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal State that tolerated criminals committing large-scale telecommunications fraud against another country would be prohibited from voting rights at the United Nations for the next 3,000 years if the total financial losses suffered by the victims of the targeted country exceeded \$100 billion. Any politician from any country proposing voting rights for the criminal state will automatically be considered a bad, evil, immoral politician with no moral standards, a thief.</p> <p>All immediate family members and descendants of the above criminals are prohibited from enrolling in any global university for the next 3,000 years and are also banned from working in any government system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
35 5	<p>Criminal organizations that defraud other countries of their wealth should not be used as a means of illicit profit by certain countries and politicians. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and address the above-mentioned problems:</p> <p>Since 1990, any criminal State that tolerated criminals committing large-scale telecommunications fraud against another country would be prohibited from voting rights at the United Nations for the next 2,000 years if the total financial losses suffered by the victims of the targeted country exceeded \$10 billion. Any politician from any country proposing voting rights for the criminal state will automatically be considered a bad, evil, immoral politician with no moral standards, a thief.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become</p>

	powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.
35 6	<p>Banks require a large pool of funds from many customers in order to operate properly. Banks that gather customer funds have a significant impact on financial security and economic stability at the regional, national and global levels. Consequently, the United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>Heads of all banks and major shareholders of banks worldwide must disclose their personal and family assets. Any country that signs the agreement, if the government does not sign, as long as half of the country's citizens agree to the agreement on the United Nations website, or if the number of supporters of the agreement in its support surpasses the number of voters in the most recent election, then the country is considered to support the agreement, and it is considered to agree to the agreement without the need for the country's government to sign and agree. If a country's government does not sign and agree, then the country's banks will be prohibited from engaging in any transactions with banks or citizens of other countries.</p>
35 7	<p>The reverse driving of motor vehicles on the expressway poses a serious threat and is a major cause of major traffic accidents. The current penalties are too lenient and are not sufficient to deter the reverse driving of motor vehicles on the expressway. The United Nations and the international community should quickly reach consensus and establish a convention on the prevention and resolution of the above-mentioned issues.</p> <p>As long as a motor vehicle reverses on the expressway, the driver's license must be revoked and fined, and driving a motor vehicle must be prohibited for three years. The offender must be sentenced to at least six months in prison with no probation, and his or her personal and family assets must be fully disclosed. Any person who causes a traffic accident while reversing on the expressway shall be prohibited from driving a motor vehicle for eight years, from obtaining a driver's license for eight years, and must be sentenced to at least one year in prison within eight years.</p>
35 8	<p>Below the operating cost of tourism, the group tour model inevitably leads to forced shopping consumption by tourists, resulting in various disputes. This has a serious negative impact on the tourism industry. The United Nations and the international community should rapidly reach consensus on and establish a convention to prevent and resolve the above-mentioned issues:</p> <p>It is strictly forbidden to use a fraudulent group tour model with costs lower than accommodation, transportation, and operating expenses. Travel agencies are prohibited from using tour guides with no monthly basic income to lead tour groups. Any travel agency must provide a basic monthly income to tour guides. In violation of the above principles, regulatory agencies must impose a fine on the travel agency three times the amount of the violation and freeze the travel agency's operating qualifications for six months. If the travel agency violates the rules again, the regulatory agency must revoke the travel agency's operating qualifications.</p>

	<p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>35 9</p>	<p>The intermediary company introduces jobs to employees, usually on a two-way fee model, charging an introduction fee to the company that needs employees. However, some intermediary companies continue to charge the employee a long-term intermediary fee after successfully introducing the employee to a job. The intermediary fee can be as high as 24% of the employee's monthly income, far exceeding the average annual return on investment for small and medium-sized enterprises in the United States. This long-term exploitation of other people's wealth is extremely serious, as employees have become borrowers of high-interest loans from intermediary companies. The United Nations and the international community should reach a consensus as soon as possible and establish a convention on the following issues: After assisting an employee successfully introduce a job, an intermediary in any occupation can only charge a reasonable intermediary fee to the employee for the first three months. After three months, no further fees can be charged. Otherwise, the intermediary company will be fined twice and its operating qualification will be suspended for six months.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>36 0</p>	<p>The most influential figure in a country or region is the president, prime minister, or governor with power, but in the past hundred years, there has been a lack of effective constraints and strategies, seriously affecting the economic development of the relevant country or region and world peace.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must realize that the current world has not been able to effectively curb the excessive gap between the rich and the poor, achieve long-term sustainable economic development or achieve long-term world peace. Instead, it has led to continuous wars. There are important problems in the philosophy and methodology of implementing national governance and maintaining world peace, the core of which is the important issue of restricting the power of the highest authority in a country or region. The United Nations and the international community must rapidly and effectively change the current situation and form a long-term consensus or covenant.</p> <p>Most people have a desire for power, but if someone who has no experience in governance and lacks the ability to serve as president, prime minister, or governor runs for office out of greed for power, ignorant and emotional voters may choose that person because of their good looks and persuasive speaking skills. However, once elected, if the person frequently demonstrates extremely poor governing ability, as well as bad character, and fails to uphold the governance strategies promised during the campaign, leading to major problems or losses in the country or state, it can be difficult to restrain the power</p>

of the elected individual in a timely manner, and the public may feel helpless. Elected individuals and all their supporters may avoid taking any responsibility. This model of election management is extremely wrong. Leaders who are wrongly elected can threaten world peace and stability and even lead to war, as is the case in Ukraine.

As George Washington once said, "the greatest threat to human civilization, the most devastating destruction, is unchecked power, followed only by natural disasters and human ignorance."

Therefore, humanity must fundamentally establish effective preventive and control measures. According to the principle of shared responsibility and power, if a novice actively runs for a leadership position, and any policies they enact result in major economic crises or losses in the country or state, the primary person responsible is the president, prime minister, or governor, followed by the core members of their ruling party, their cabinet team, ordinary party members, and ordinary supporters of the candidate. You are free, and you have the right to run for office or vote, but you must pay the price for your greed, ignorance, incompetence, and deception.

Moreover, if a candidate, once in office, does not follow the strategies and goals promised during the campaign, but instead deceives voters and pursues different strategies and goals, leading to significant economic losses or war, a dramatic increase in the cost of living for citizens, and a surge in unemployment, then the successful candidate must compensate the country with their personal and family assets. The second and third responsible parties must also compensate the country with their personal assets, and the fourth responsible party must compensate the country with half of their income from the year of the election. The fifth responsible party must compensate the country with one month's income from the year of the election. All individuals and families involved in this matter must publicly disclose all of their assets within one month. If the candidate and interest groups fail to adhere to these rules, the country's military may intervene in any way necessary.

This convention is effective for any country in the world in order to prevent the power of that country from being controlled only by a few politicians and interest groups. Even if the Government of that country does not agree to sign this Convention, as long as half of the citizens of that country agree on the UN website or meet the following conditions, within the last 100 years of the country's founding, as long as the number of supporters of this Convention exceeds the highest recorded number of voters in an election since the country's establishment, it will be considered that the country supports this Convention and agrees to it, without the need for the Government of that country to sign and agree.

In particular, if a candidate relies on deception to win the election and then a long-term civil war occurs or the civil war does not stop, all members of the ruling party must compensate innocent victims with their personal and family property, and compensation must be provided to victims in chronological order. If a novice comes to power and 75% of the country's people oppose the novice,

	<p>the novice must step down and compensate their personal and family property for the victims of that country.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
36 1	<p>The use of smart meters for billing electricity, water, and natural gas in households often leads to disputes, which may be due to fraudulent practices by relevant companies. It is essential for the United Nations and the international community to establish the following conventions to regulate this smart billing system.</p> <p>First, if users have doubts, electricity, water and gas companies must provide a fast and clear way to prove the accuracy of the smart metering system within half an hour. Otherwise, if users cannot eliminate their doubts about significantly higher monthly use of electricity, water, or gas, they may refuse to pay. If the company supplying these essential resources cannot prove the accuracy of the data, and if fraud is found, the fraudulent company must be fined three times the amount cheated by users to compensate for their losses. In addition, similar issues in the past must be investigated, and the company's responsible individuals must be fined three times the amount, and all personal and family assets of the company's employees must be made public.</p> <p>Second, the government must disclose the information of the responsible person and their company's fraud using the mainstream media of the city or region every day for one month, and publish the criminals' photos in the media;</p> <p>Third, the police must criminally detain fraudsters and swindlers for at least 7 days, and if multiple users jointly discover that a company's smart metering has defrauded them of more than 10,000 yuan, the company's responsible persons and those involved must be sentenced to more than one year in prison.</p> <p>Fourth, if the criminal and his family members leave their place of residence to go to another city or area, they must report their itinerary to the police station, and are prohibited from travelling by plane and high-speed rail.</p> <p>Fifth, all family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system. Sixth, if it is found that a company is using smart meters to falsify data, the individuals involved and the company's responsible parties must be immediately placed under criminal detention.</p>
36 2	<p>Serious judicial injustice is the root cause of the occurrence of malignant cases, and must be corrected with strong measures to deter law enforcement officials from committing crimes. The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus on the following issues and establish conventions:</p> <p>If there is evidence that the suspect was not present at the scene in a case, completely contradicting the logic of the criminal investigation, the judge should not make a wrongful judgment. The reasons for the suspect's crime could not be established, but the judge disregarded the facts and maliciously convicted him, resulting in the victim's wrongful imprisonment. In such a case, the</p>

	<p>relevant judicial personnel are equally guilty, and their prison sentences should be the same as the victim's. If the victim is wrongly sentenced to death, once the error is corrected, the judge should be sentenced to at least 80 years in prison or the death penalty. In addition, the personal and family assets of the relevant judges should be confiscated to compensate the families of the victims or be turned over to the national treasury. The personal and family assets of all individuals in the relevant unit, as well as those of relatives within three generations, should be made public. All family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system. Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>36 3</p>	<p>The theft and impersonation of another person's identity to obtain qualifications for higher education, civil service employment, or job placement benefits, especially the impersonation of qualifications for higher education, could potentially ruin the victim's entire life. In ancient China, such crimes were almost always punishable by death, but today, similar cases are frequent and criminals are rarely punished. The difficulty of controlling these crimes and the serious injustice in the judicial system are the root causes of the occurrence of vicious cases. Strong corrective measures must be taken to deter law enforcement officers from committing crimes, and the United Nations and the international community should reach a consensus and establish a convention on the following issues:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The main perpetrators of such crimes must be sentenced to at least 15 years' imprisonment and all personal and family property confiscated, while other offenders must be sentenced to at least six years' imprisonment. 2. Confiscate the personal and family property of the offenders concerned in order to compensate the families of the victims or hand it over to the national treasury. 3. The personal and family property of all individuals in the offender's unit, as well as the property of their relatives within three generations, should be publicly disclosed. 4. If the criminal and his family members leave their place of residence to go to another city or area, they must report their itinerary to the police station, and are prohibited from travelling by plane and high-speed rail. 5. All family members are permanently blacklisted from the credit system, and all family members and immediate relatives are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service system. <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>36 4</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus and establish conventions on the following issues:</p>

	<p>For the rape of girls under 12 years of age, a minimum of 20 years' imprisonment; for the rape of underage girls twice or more, the death penalty. For gang rape of underage girls, the death penalty. The penalty for false accusation should be the same as the above offences. Regardless of whether the offender has reached adulthood or not.</p> <p>Criminals who kill underage girls or children or students, regardless of whether the offender is an adult, must be sentenced to death. If anyone does not allow the criminal to be sentenced to death, then if the criminal commits a crime in the future, the loss caused by the criminal will be borne by the judge, the advocates of not sentencing to death in court and behind the scenes, and these individuals and their families will have all their personal and family property confiscated, and be sentenced to at least 30 years in prison, experiencing the taste of death.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
36 5	<p>Children are the future of society and the hope of the family. However, cases of missing children are frequent, and some government agencies deal with these cases slowly or are unwilling to initiate timely investigations, resulting in a lack of control over crimes and putting children at risk of harm. The families of the victims are plunged into long-term pain. Strong corrective measures must be put in place to deter law enforcement from inaction. The United Nations and the international community should reach a consensus on the following issues and establish a convention:</p> <p>First, in areas and cities where children or students go missing, as long as the family reports the case, the police must immediately accept it. If the culprit is not found, the promotion of all government officials in this area and city should be temporarily suspended until the culprit and the child or students are found, prompting the whole society to pay high attention to the children's whereabouts and investigate the suspect. Second, all personal and family assets of individuals in the unit where the police did not promptly initiate an investigation due to a missing case must be made public.</p>
36 6	<p>Some public hospitals give nurses with the same skills in the same position completely different treatment, resulting in some nurses earning high incomes while others earn very low incomes, despite doing the same job and working very hard. This is suspected of serious discrimination and it is essential for the United Nations and the international community to establish the following convention to prohibit different systemic treatment of nurses with the same skills and in the same position. Otherwise, the medical institution should be fined five times the normal income that all affected nurses should receive during the period of the offence, and compensate the victims.</p>
36 7	<p>Soccer is a popular sport among the global public, but over the past twenty years, people have discovered serious problems within it, leading to great disappointment with the sport. The United Nations and the international</p>

	<p>community should reach a consensus on the following issues and establish a convention:</p> <p>For countries with a long history of poor soccer performance and a FIFA ranking outside the top 50, if there is serious corruption within the country's football association or soccer community during the last two World Cup cycles, fans had expressed serious dissatisfaction. All personnel of the national football association, coaches and staff of all national teams must publicly disclose their personal and family assets within one week of the entry into force of this UN convention. Individuals and organizations involved in intermediary activities related to soccer must operate their funds transparently and disclose their personal and family assets. This is to prevent soccer from becoming the darkest sport in the world.</p>
36 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Any war criminal State which initiates aggressive wars and causes significant damage to other States in various fields, its military personnel must, after serving their sentences in the victim State, be forced to work as labourers in the victim State for three times the duration of the aggression. For example, if a country invaded for one year, its prisoners of war must work as labourers for at least three years; if the invasion lasted for two years, prisoners of war must work as labourers for six years. Specific work will be determined by the affected country. It is strongly recommended that the United Nations establish such a convention to deter potential war criminal countries and their military forces, in order to reduce the occurrence of war.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
36 9	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>If any country's military first uses chemical weapons or biological weapons,</p>

	<p>then not only the military of that country are criminals against humanity, but also the citizens of that country are criminals as long as they do not openly protest against the war. Victims and the target country can carry out indiscriminate attacks or even destroy that country.</p>
<p>37 0</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions. Based on historical facts, modifying the earliest point of the beginning of the Second World War is bound to yield a new perspective on the maintenance of world peace.</p> <p>It is recommended that the United Nations re-evaluate the earliest start date of the Second World War and promptly recognize the Jinan Massacre, initiated by the Japanese invaders on May 1, 1928, as the earliest start date of the Second World War. Japan, as a war criminal state responsible for the Jinan Massacre, should have no voting rights or decision-making authority on the matter.</p> <p>The earliest starting point of World War II should be calculated from the Jinan Massacre, where the most ruthless, most evil, and most despicable Japanese troops massacred at least 21,000 people. Seventeen diplomats were not only slaughtered, but had their tongues cut out, eyes gouged, ears and noses removed before being stripped and mowed down by machine gun fire, resulting in their deaths. Over 17,000 Chinese civilians were burned and killed to death, more than 5,000 were captured, and most of the captives eventually died. After the National Revolutionary Army withdrew from Jinan, the Japanese army entered the city on the morning of May 11 to demonstrate their national power, initiating a massacre so brutal that it was beyond human comprehension: they would shoot anyone in sight, and cut off the breasts of women they encountered. Thousands of women were raped.</p>
<p>37 1</p>	<p>Treatment and prevention of some difficult diseases currently have no fundamental solution in modern medicine, but traditional medicine can be effective. However, in some countries, the modern medical management model has set high barriers for medical qualifications, causing practitioners who previously used this traditional approach to become illegal. This has led to dissatisfaction among many patients and practitioners. Despite their desire to seek out these doctors to cure their diseases, the current power structures are not controlled by patients, which has led to illegal consequences. Therefore, the United Nations and national societies must quickly form the following consensus and conventions.</p> <p>As long as the traditional medical treatment has been widely used by the</p>

	<p>nationals of a country to effectively treat and prevent diseases, for the past thousand years, and even cure some diseases that modern medicine cannot cure, the government has never set qualification thresholds for this medical practice before. Therefore, it is legal and reasonable for anyone in the country to use this medical practice to treat and prevent diseases for others, as long as patients voluntarily seek treatment and there are no medical disputes. The government should not intervene, and the country should not set qualification thresholds for doctors using this method to treat diseases, but the government may choose not to include it in the scope of medical insurance payments.</p>
<p>37 2</p>	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any country that has waged aggressive wars, used immigration strategies to annex other countries, and committed the atrocities of raping and gang-raping more than 5 million women in other countries, as well as eating the uterus, cutting off breasts, and committing violent acts of inserting knives or sticks into women's vaginas, shall be referred to as a country of rape and gang rape, uterus-eating, and breast-cutting for the next 1,000 years. Any country or organization may use this designation in oral or written communications during any international activity. The guilty State is prohibited from voting in the United Nations and other intergovernmental organizations, from being a permanent member of any international organization, and from operating any school or hospital in any other country.</p> <p>For the next 1,000 years, the descendants of war criminals from the banned country are forbidden from running for any government position, prohibited from working in the judiciary, military, police, and finance sectors, and prohibited from holding any public office.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians</p>

	become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.
37 3	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any country that has waged aggressive wars, used immigration strategies to annex other countries, and committed the atrocities of raping and gang-raping more than 10 million women in other countries, as well as eating the uterus, cutting off breasts, and committing violent acts of inserting knives or sticks into women's vaginas, shall be referred to as a country of rape and gang rape, uterus-eating, and breast-cutting for the next 1,500 years. Any country or organization may use this designation in oral or written communications during any international activity. The guilty State is prohibited from voting in the United Nations and other intergovernmental organizations, from being a permanent member of any international organization, and from operating any school or hospital in any other country.</p> <p>For the next 1,500 years, the descendants of war criminals from the banned country are forbidden from running for any government position, prohibited from working in the judiciary, military, police, and finance sectors, and prohibited from holding any public office.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
37 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must</p>

	<p>change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Since 1900, any country that has waged aggressive wars, used immigration strategies to annex other countries, and committed the atrocities of raping and gang-raping more than 20 million women in other countries, as well as eating the uterus, cutting off breasts, and committing violent acts of inserting knives or sticks into women's vaginas, shall be referred to as a country of rape and gang rape, uterus-eating, and breast-cutting for the next 2,000 years. Any country or organization may use this designation in oral or written communications during any international activity. The guilty State is prohibited from voting in the United Nations and other intergovernmental organizations, from being a permanent member of any international organization, and from operating any school or hospital in any other country.</p> <p>For the next 2,000 years, the descendants of war criminals from the banned country are forbidden from running for any government position, prohibited from working in the judiciary, military, police, and finance sectors, and prohibited from holding any public office.</p> <p>Any politician opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that they have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that they are not born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and they are an anomaly in this world. Any political party opposing this convention of harsh punishment for criminals and upholding justice must declare that all members of its party have no grandmother or mother, no sister or daughter, and that none of its members are born of a woman. Therefore, they are politically correct, their morality is correct, and their party is an anomaly in this world.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
37 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>The capacity and character of officials are closely linked to the governance of the region. The United Nations and the international community should reach consensus and conventions on the following issues to the greatest extent possible in order to prevent official crimes and improve the governance level of global governments.</p> <p>The ability of a region to be well managed depends on the foresight,</p>

	<p>management skills, and character of government officials. The promotion of officials requires more foresight to reduce the promotion of incompetent officials and minimize the improper promotion of civil servants who may be prone to serious crimes, while increasing the promotion of officials with good character and capability. Logically, those who propose promotions should be the most familiar with and understand the officials being promoted, and they must bear a certain responsibility. Correct promotions should be commended, with a Bole Award given every three or four years. If a promoted official commits a serious crime, the person who proposed their recent promotion must be held responsible. Any person who proposed and executed the promotion of a criminal official must be demoted by three levels and their benefits reduced, with all personal and family assets made public. They can only be promoted again if they have new achievements or continue to work diligently.</p> <p>In the case of multiple or collective decisions to promote a criminal official, those involved must also bear responsibility. All promotions within the group must be suspended for five years, with the individual primarily responsible for promotion being demoted, and other rules consistent with the previous ones.</p> <p>Any official who makes a major mistake in his or her job should be demoted, and the position of the person who proposed his or her promotion should also be downgraded until he or she achieves new success and can be promoted again.</p> <p>Officials who cause significant losses to State assets or major obstacles to the national economy must be demoted and compensated with 1-3 years' personal salary or half of their personal property. All personal and family assets must be made public. The position of the person who proposed the promotion of such an official must be demoted by three levels, and their benefits reduced, with all personal and family assets made public. They can only be promoted again if they have new achievements or continue to work diligently.</p> <p>Any person who proposes and implements an action that results in significant losses of State assets must also be punished.</p>
37 6	<p>There is a significant association between contemporary crime and the leakage of personal information. The United Nations and the international community must reach consensus and establish conventions to the maximum extent possible to prevent such crimes and enhance global governance levels.</p> <p>Any commercial software or app intended for public use must include an option to prohibit the software from accessing personal information on mobile phones or computers, and the user should be able to easily locate this option. Violators who are suspected of committing a crime can be held accountable. If a company forces its public-facing apps or commercial software to access or obtain user information and is unwilling to make changes, users can claim compensation for losses caused by the violation. The company must also make changes to the software within 48 hours. Otherwise, the government must impose the following penalties: First, the legal person, CEO, and controlling</p>

	<p>shareholder of the company must be sentenced to 1-3 years in prison, and all assets of individuals and families of the crime unit and their relatives within three generations must be made public. Any illegal profits made using this information must be confiscated, and the company and its responsible persons must be fined twice. Secondly, the police must impose travel restrictions on the offender, requiring them to report their travel plans to the police station when leaving their place of residence, and they are forbidden from travelling by plane or high-speed rail. Third, the offender will be permanently included on the credit blacklist, and all family members and immediate relatives will be permanently banned from entering the civil servant system.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
37 7	<p>Any wrongful judgment resulting in the death or wrongful killing of innocent people shall result in the public disclosure of the personal and family assets of all responsible parties, as well as their extended families for three generations. The personal and family assets of everyone in their unit must also be made public, and the assets of the main responsible person and his or her family must be confiscated and turned over to the national treasury. In the event of such a serious incident, it is clear that the main responsible person lacks foresight and is unfit to hold a leadership position, and should be sentenced to at least 10 years' imprisonment or the death penalty. All responsible parties shall be prohibited from promotion for 20 years, and their descendants must undergo six years of training in harsh environments, followed by a public evaluation by the people of all training units, and must receive unanimous approval before being eligible for a civil service career, otherwise they shall be prohibited from working in the field. The last successful proposal to appoint the main responsible person's leader must be demoted by three levels of position and benefits within one month after the incident.</p> <p>For any wrongful sentence resulting in the imprisonment of innocent persons, the personal and family assets of all responsible parties, as well as their extended families for three generations, shall be made public. The assets of the main responsible person shall be confiscated and turned over to the national treasury, and all responsible parties shall be prohibited from promotion within 15 years. Innocent victims were sentenced to imprisonment for how many years, the primary responsible person (including judge) must be sentenced to the same period of imprisonment, without parole, and without any reason for reduction of sentence.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
37 8	<p>The United Nations and the international community should form a consensus and conventions on speeding up the circulation of agricultural products, promoting rural economic development and strengthening</p>

	<p>government governance to address common problems in the transportation of agricultural products. Any toll collector at a toll booth who extorts agricultural transportation vehicles must be severely punished, including relevant personnel:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The toll collector claims that bell peppers are not a type of chili pepper, or that purple sweet potatoes are not a type of sweet potato, etc. 2. If a few fish in a shipment of live fish have incomplete bodies, the toll collector denies that the whole shipment is fresh agricultural products. 3. A whole shipment of fruit is required to be unloaded for inspection by the toll collector. 4. If the green leafy part of the scallions has been removed during harvesting, leaving only the white stem and root, the toll collector deems the scallions not to be agricultural products. 5. After the vegetables experience strong winds on the highway, some of them become dried out. When passing through the toll booth, the toll collectors at this toll station intentionally refuse to recognize the fact that the transportation vehicle is carrying agricultural products, and insist on inspecting the entire load of agricultural products in order to approve them. They may require unloading for inspection, or deny the vehicle transporting agricultural products access to the green channel for free passage, and instead demand a high toll fee before allowing passage. These are all unacceptable behaviors. <p>In the case of such misconduct, the relevant regulatory authorities must dismiss the violator at the toll station within one day, report the incident nationwide, prohibit any toll station from re-hiring this individual, and impose a double fine on the responsible person and the toll station. All fines will be paid into the national treasury, and the toll station must compensate the owner of the vehicle and cargo owner for all losses. Any leader who recommends or advocates the hiring of this individual at the toll station must be demoted to two levels of position and salary within 15 days. Meanwhile, the entire personal and family assets of the individual and his or her relatives within three generations must be disclosed within one week. The personal and family assets of all individuals involved misconduct in this incident, as well as all employees of the toll station, must be disclosed within one week. All family members are prohibited from entering the civil service system for life. If the amount of loss caused to the cargo owner or vehicle owner exceeds CNY10,000, toll collectors who intentionally extort money from the vehicle owner must be subject to criminal penalties.</p>
37 9	<p>The management of government officials is closely linked to the fairness and justice of societies in all countries, as well as global stability and peace. Rarely does a government agency in any country require all its civil servants from different agencies to engage in a mechanism for criticism and self-reflection, individually or collectively. The United Nations should improve its own level of management and consider forming a relevant convention on the following issues:</p>

	<p>Government officials from all countries around the world should set aside half a day to a day at the end of every two months for collective reflection, guided by the philosophical principles of Mao Zedong, to criticize and self-criticize their work over the past two months, reflecting on whether there have been major errors in decision-making and miscarriages of justice within their jurisdictions. If there have been miscarriages of justice, they should outline plans for timely correction and submit a report to the United Nations for verification of alignment with the resolution of major issues in the country. Finally, the ethical standards of metrological government ethics, metrological judicial ethics, and metrological party ethics would be assessed through measurement.</p>
380	<p>In recent decades, some countries have seen the frequent sale of inferior gutter oil as edible oil, which poses a great danger to human health. Many criminals have profited from this, so it is recommended that the United Nations form a relevant convention to control crime related to the above issue. The method of producing gutter oil involves collecting large amounts of dark, turbid sludge or leftover food from restaurants flowing through the city sewer, and then filtering, heating, precipitating, and separating it overnight to produce harmful gutter oil. Criminals who turn sewage oil into edible oil or sell it as a mixture of edible oil pose a great threat to society, and it is difficult to completely prevent. It is necessary to deter these criminals by adopting the following methods to eradicate these crimes.</p> <p>First, they must be sentenced to 2-6 years in prison, and all personal and family assets of the individuals involved in the crime, as well as those of their relatives within three generations, must be made public. Second, for those who are aware of the crime, their first offense will result in the confiscation of all personal assets, and for repeat offenders, their personal and family assets will be confiscated. Third, law enforcement must impose travel restrictions on offenders. If they leave their place of residence to go to another city or region, they must report their itinerary to the police station and are prohibited from taking flights and high-speed trains. Fourth, criminals will be blacklisted for life, and all family members and immediate relatives will be permanently banned from entering the civil service system. Fifth, all family members and direct relatives of offenders are prohibited from receiving compulsory education and medical insurance for 100 years, and are banned from entering public universities. Sixth, whistleblowers who report the crime of turning sewage oil into edible oil or selling it as a mixture of edible oil will be rewarded with 25% of the confiscated assets of the criminal once their report is verified. Seventh, governments of countries or regions where such incidents occur must inform every citizen of the provisions of this Convention through various means of rapid communication or dissemination, at least once a week.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>

<p>38 1</p>	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 10 million people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 2,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>38 2</p>	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 20 million people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 4,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
<p>38 3</p>	<p>Since 1900, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 30 million people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 6,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its</p>

	<p>assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
38 4	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 1 million people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 5,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
38 5	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 500,000 people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 3,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
38 6	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 200,000 people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 2,000 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce</p>

	<p>the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
38 7	<p>Since 1950, any evil country that has initiated aggressive wars or riots, massacred innocent expatriates or descendants of other countries, totaling more than 100,000 people, is a country that commits crimes against humanity. Civilians in this country do not exist. The citizens of this country enjoy the wealth plundered through war or riots. This criminal country is prohibited from selling any weapons or weapons-making technology to any country or region for the next 1,500 years. If weapons or weapon-making technology are sold, the penalty will be doubled. The first country to discover and publicly announce the crimes of this criminal country will receive 40% of the proceeds, with the rest distributed to all countries that support the punishment of the criminal country. If the criminal country refuses to pay the penalty within six months, any country supporting the punishment of the criminal country can freeze its assets.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
38 8	<p>During the transportation of agricultural products, if the surface of the whole vehicle's agricultural products appears to be dried by wind, such as the surface of radishes, Chinese cabbage, carrots, peppers, tomatoes, lettuce, and scallions, which are dried due to factors such as high temperature or wind, the toll collector at the highway toll station intentionally refuses to provide the vehicle with free access to the green channel under the pretext of the agricultural products being dry. Such behavior indicates extremely poor moral character, and the toll collector must be dismissed within one day, and the owner and shipper must compensate for all losses. They will also be fined twice their salary, and the toll station will be fined five times the total amount of the shipper and vehicle owner's losses. The fine must be paid within three working days, and anyone who recommended or decided to hire this toll collector to work at the toll station will be demoted by one level and have their benefits reduced by one level. All personnel at the toll station and all individuals and their family members within three generations involved in this case must have their assets publicly disclosed. The toll collector is prohibited from entering any toll station for life. All employees of this toll station and their personal and family members must disclose all their assets within three working days. All individuals and their family members who recommend and decide to hire the toll collector must also disclose their assets within three working days. All family members, relatives</p>

	<p>and descendants of the toll collector are prohibited from entering any university worldwide and from working in any civil service system in any country or region.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
38 9	<p>In the event of any unexpected disaster or accident, the mainstream or official media of the country should fully report on it. Any interference or obstruction of mainstream media or official journalists by security, police, or criminal elements should be prohibited. Individuals who issue such orders, as well as personnel from government agencies involved in the incident, should be demoted by two levels in administrative positions. Law enforcement officers involved should have their salaries suspended for two months and be repositioned. Anyone who harms journalists or the relatives of victims, including those who issue orders, those primarily responsible at the scene, and those in charge at the scene, will be considered criminals and subjected to criminal penalties. All government officials involved will have their administrative positions and salaries reduced by two levels, and will be prohibited from working in their positions again. Non-government personnel will be subject to criminal penalties and will be required to pay three times compensation for any damage to property or injury to journalists. All offenders and their family members must report their travel plans to the police before leaving their place of residence for another city or region. They are also prohibited from travelling by plane or high-speed train. All family members will be placed on a lifetime credit blacklist, and all family members and immediate family members will be barred from entering the civil service system for 300 years. Furthermore, all family members and direct relatives of the above-mentioned criminals will be prohibited from attending any university worldwide and from working in any country or region's civil service system.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive.</p>
39 0	<p>In the event of any accident or disaster resulting in the death of the victims, no institution shall prohibit the inspection and visitation of the body of the victims by their relatives. The ownership of the victim's body belongs to the relatives, not to any institution. The cremation of the victim's body is prohibited, and any act of preventing the victim's relatives from visiting and inspecting the victim's body, as well as forcibly cremating the victim's body, constitute serious violations of the law. Throughout history, it has been a basic ethical principle for the relatives of executed criminals to examine and collect the bodies. In the event of the above circumstances, at least those who conceal a homicide or obstruct the victim's relatives from visiting or cremating the victim shall be charged with at least two offences: obstructing the investigation of a homicide</p>

	<p>and destroying evidence of a crime, and shall compensate the victim's family.</p> <p>At present, such crimes occur from time to time. The United Nations and the international community must form the following conventions on the above issues:</p> <p>First, anyone who orders the above heinous acts, as well as personnel from the government agencies primarily involved, will have their administrative ranks and benefits reduced by five levels. Direct law enforcement personnel must have their salaries suspended for at least one year, be transferred from their positions, and be subject to criminal penalties. Secondly, anyone who harms journalists or the relatives of victims, as well as those who give orders or are the primary responsible parties or commanders at the scene, will be considered as criminals and subject to criminal penalties, and will be removed from their positions. Non-governmental personnel would be subject to criminal law sanctions, and must pay triple compensation for damage to property or injury to journalists. Third, all criminals and their family members must report their travel itineraries to the police before leaving their place of residence to go to another city or region. Fourth, they are prohibited from travelling on airplanes and high-speed trains. Fifth, all family members are blacklisted for life. Sixth, all offenders are prohibited for life from receiving medical insurance services. Seventh, all family members and direct relatives of the above-mentioned criminals are prohibited from entering any university in the world for 1,000 years, and from working in the civil service system of any country or region. As long as offenders or their descendants are reported by informed individuals for violations, any university or government agency must complete the processing within 48 hours. Eighth, the personal and family wealth of the offender and all close relatives within three generations must be made public. Ninth, the personal and family wealth of all individuals in the unit involved in the case must be made public.</p> <p>Politicians should remember the words of Elon Musk: "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."</p>
39 1	<p>The harm of nuclear waste water (nuclear sewage) to the human body and the earth is extremely serious, with nuclear wastewater posing a greater threat to the human body. It contains 64 kinds of radioactive materials, including tritium, carbon-14, iodine-129, strontium-90, and cobalt-60. The most harmful to human beings and marine organisms are carbon-14 and iodine-129, with a half-life of over 5000 years for carbon-14 and an even longer half-life for iodine-129. Carbon-14 can accumulate in the bodies of marine organisms, such as fish, with an abundance or concentration possibly 50 times that of tritium. Any individual, company or country that releases nuclear waste water or nuclear pollution (nuclear sewage) to the earth or the sea should ensure that all indicators meet emission standards in advance and undergo organized testing and continuous monitoring by neighboring countries.</p> <p>Currently, Japan has disregarded the opposition of neighboring countries</p>

	<p>and the concerns of the international community, unilaterally discharging over 23,000 tons of nuclear-contaminated water (nuclear sewage) into the ocean, and initiating the fourth round of discharge last week. Never before has any country dared to take such a risk and impose the risk of nuclear pollution on the whole world in this manner.</p> <p>The United Nations and the international community must form the following treaty on the above-mentioned issues: Any country that believes discharging nuclear wastewater poses no risk to people globally must first experience and prove that this nuclear wastewater poses no risk to themselves.</p> <p>For companies that are preparing to discharge nuclear wastewater into the earth or the ocean without prior emissions, all shareholders and employees advocating for the discharge of nuclear wastewater must drink the diluted wastewater, filtered 100 times using fast-filtering filter paper, and use it for bathing once a day for 12 months. All supporters of the discharge of nuclear wastewater in the country must also bathe in it for one month.</p> <p>Japan believes that discharging nuclear wastewater poses no risk to people globally, and Japanese citizens must experience and demonstrate that this type of nuclear wastewater poses no risk to them.</p> <p>After discharging nuclear wastewater, the shareholders and all employees of the company must bathe in seawater within 200 meters of the discharge outlet. The top 100 shareholders of the company discharging nuclear wastewater and all employees of the company must bathe in this water once a day for half an hour until the discharge of nuclear wastewater stops. All supporters of the discharge of nuclear wastewater in the country must also bathe in it for six months. Japanese citizens, along with the shareholders and employees of the company discharging nuclear wastewater, must first experience the above-mentioned process.</p> <p>Any country or company discharging nuclear wastewater must bear full responsibility and compensate the victims for their losses. In the case of tumors, death, or other injuries, they must compensate according to the standards of 18 typical cases in the United States. The shareholders of the company that discharges nuclear waste water must compensate the victims with their personal and family assets, and the country where the company discharges nuclear waste water must compensate the victims with its assets.</p> <p>The assets of shareholders, executives, all employees, their families and relatives of up to three generations of the companies involved must be made public.</p> <p>All shareholders, employees and family members of the company involved in the case must report their travel itinerary to the police station before leaving their place of residence for another city or region.</p>
39 2	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result</p>

	<p>of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>Criminals who carry out large-scale crimes and inflict long-term torture on many victims are undoubtedly a serious threat to society, as their actions have caused serious harm and destruction. For such crimes, the law must impose severe sanctions to maintain social order and justice. In this situation, it is necessary to use criminal law to compel criminals to confess, because:</p> <p>First, the criminals' actions have caused immense harm and damage, and the victims have endured long-term torture, needing timely access to justice and compensation. Only through the confession of the criminals can the truth be quickly revealed and the victims provided with a fair outcome.</p> <p>Second, the confession of offenders can help police and judicial institutions quickly solve cases, uncovering other potential suspects and related clues, preventing similar crimes from happening again, and protecting more people from harm.</p> <p>Finally, criminals should be held accountable for their actions, and avoiding responsibility would only prolong the suffering of victims and society, which goes against the principles of fairness and justice. While ensuring the basic rights of offenders, the use of criminal law to compel confessions when necessary is important to ensure the safety and justice of society.</p> <p>In any case, for criminals who commit large-scale crimes and inflict long-term torture on many victims, the law must take strict measures, including the use of criminal law to force confessions, to ensure that victims can obtain justice, prevent similar crimes from happening again, and also hold perpetrators accountable for their actions. In this process, it is of course important to ensure that the basic rights of offenders are respected, in order to uphold the principles of fairness and justice.</p>
39 3	<p>Government governance is largely linked to the moral qualities of the officials. It is suggested that the United Nations develop a relevant convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Some officials know that the decision made by their superiors is wrong, but they do not remind their superiors to pay attention or correct the error at all. Instead, they continue to incite others to execute the decision, ultimately leading to major losses. Such officials should be prohibited from promotion for 15 years. Even if they are promoted, they should not hold a substantive position and should be given at most a deputy position.</p>
39 4	<p>The United Nations and the international community must be aware that the current inability to effectively and rapidly control crime and achieve long-term world peace is due to significant problems in the philosophy and methodology of national governance and the maintenance of world peace. This is the result of Europe's modern-day plagiarism and incomplete copying of</p>

	<p>China's legislative ideology, and the falsification of Europe as the cradle of world civilization. The United Nations and the international community must change the philosophy, strategy and methodology of crime control and develop some relevant permanent consensuses or conventions.</p> <p>The world's worst and most evil war criminal country, Japan, must return the cultural relics, books, and wealth it plundered from China. They must also return the head of General Liu Guiwu, a Chinese military officer, who was taken by the Japanese invaders and is still being displayed in Japan, back to China.</p>
39 5	<p>At 9:00 a.m. on May 22, 2021, 16 people died in the 2021 (4th) Yellow River Stone Forest Mountain Marathon 100 km cross-country race hosted by Jingtai County, Baiyin City, Gansu Province, and 5 people were missing, with more injuries.</p> <p>Statistics show that full and half marathon runners are at high risk of sudden death, with the majority in the 20-29 age group accounting for about 62%. Sudden deaths of marathon runners often occur during sprints and after the finish line.</p> <p>The Greek marathon race is a completely fictional story, and scholars have pointed out that the incidence of lower limb injuries varies in different marathon courses, with the highest reaching 79.3%, and the incidence of knee joint injuries being about 35.0%, the most vulnerable area. Common sports injuries in marathons include iliotibial band friction syndrome, patellofemoral pain syndrome, Achilles tendonitis, ankle sprains, plantar fasciitis, and fatigue fractures.</p> <p>Marathon races often lead to the sudden death or death of athletes, as marathon sports can easily damage the joints of athletes. Marathon running is a high-risk sport, and this fictional sport should be cancelled. It is recommended that full marathons be cancelled globally within two years, and considering that many people love long-distance running, it is suggested to immediately switch to half marathons to reduce the death rate of athletes and minimize the damage of excessive exercise to the body.</p> <p>It is proposed that the United Nations should form an international convention on the above-mentioned issue.</p> <p>[Ran over 600 kilometers in 3 days? That's the marathon described in Western pseudo-history, even the horses would be ashamed. 2023-12-19. https://www.sohu.com/a/745279379_121118977?scm=1102.xchannel:325:100002.0.6.0]; [A super marathon in Gansu caused a great number of athletes to die or go missing, which can be described as a major human tragedy. 2021-05-23. https://www.163.com/dy/article/GALTG23M0549BD3W.html]; [Why do sudden deaths occur frequently in marathons? There are four main reasons, these five types of people are not suitable to participate in the competition. November 28, 2018. https://www.sohu.com/a/278160294_100511]; [Heffernan KS. How healthy were the arteries of Phidippides? Clin Cardiol. 2012 Feb;35(2):65-8. doi: 10.1002/clc.21009. Epub 2011 Nov 28. PMID: 22125198; PMCID: PMC6652691.]; [Tokinoya K, Ishikura K, Ra SG, Ebina K,</p>

	<p>Miyakawa S, Ohmori H. Relationship between early-onset muscle soreness and indirect muscle damage markers and their dynamics after a full marathon. <i>J Exerc Sci Fit.</i> 2020 Sep;18(3):115-121. doi: 10.1016/j.jesf.2020.03.001. Epub 2020 Mar 12. PMID: 32351588; PMCID: PMC7183207.];[Steinacker T, Steuer M, Hölzke V. Orthopädische Probleme bei älteren Marathonläufern [Orthopedic problems in older marathon runners]. <i>Sportverletz Sportschaden.</i> 2001 Mar;15(1):12-5. German. doi: 10.1055/s-2001-11962. PMID: 11338658.]</p>
39 6	<p>Judges, judicial institutions, or public officials abusing their power leading to serious judicial injustice, victims being forced to suffer significant economic losses that should not have occurred, or being harmed, sentenced, or even killed. When victims, their relatives, or third parties file complaints with judicial institutions, they are unable to obtain proper resolution. The law becomes meaningless, and justice and fairness cannot be obtained. In this situation, the United Nations should form an international convention on the above issues, enabling victims, their relatives, or any third party to legally fight against any injustice caused by the abuse of power using any means necessary.</p>
39 7	<p>After the well-known monk Shitou Xiqian passed away, his body was enshrined in Zhangzhou, Fujian in the history of Zen Buddhism. However, in the early 20th century, it was stolen by a group of the worst and most evil Japanese war criminals of the Second World War. After the Japanese stole Shitou Xiqian's body, it was enshrined in the main temple of the Soto sect in Yokohama. Japanese military monks have killed countless people in China, and Japanese invaders caused the death of at least 50 million people in China. Japan is completely irreligious and only a cult country. Japan must unconditionally return the body of Shitou Xiqian to China.</p>
39 8	<p>Japan must unconditionally return the physical Buddha of the boundless master of Nanyue to China</p> <p>Japanese Spy Steals Body Remains of Chinese Buddhist</p> <p>Japanese people like to engage in espionage activities as doctors.</p> <p>During the China-Japanese War, in 1938, a "Hengyue Clinic" was opened on the main street of Nanyue Town, one of the four famous Buddhist sacred sites in China. The owner of the clinic, in his 40s with white temples, stared at Nantai Temple on Mount Heng from across the street.</p> <p>One day, a "treasure" from the Nantai Temple, the remains of monk Shitou Xiqian, suddenly disappeared.</p> <p>The monk Xiqian, whose secular surname was Chen, was a prominent figure from Gaoyao, Duanzhou, Guangdong. He was a disciple of Zen master Xing Si, a prominent Zen monk. He was posthumously honored with the title "Master Without Limits" by Emperor Dezong of the Tang Dynasty. He passed away at Nantai Temple in the late Tang Dynasty (790 AD), and it is believed that his body did not decay after his death. The disciples and believers then built a temple to enshrine the bodily remains of the monk.</p> <p>In the 1930s, a Japanese dentist named Watanabe Shiro learned about the immortal body of Master Without Limits hidden in the temple. With malicious</p>

	<p>intent, he took various measures to poison the young monks inside the temple and secretly moved the monk's remains outside the temple to hide them. Soon after, the temple was set on fire by marauding soldiers, and it was widely believed that the remains of Master Without Limits were destroyed along with the temple in the blaze, causing great lamentation.</p> <p>Watanabe Shiro used deceptive means to secretly transport the monk's remains back to Japan and stored them in a hidden underground warehouse on the outskirts of Tokyo, unknown to outsiders. It wasn't until 1947, after Watanabe Shiro's death, that this matter became known to the public through the examination of his diary. When the yellow silk covering the master's body was removed, it was discovered that body of the monk Xiqian remained in a seated meditation position, perfectly preserved with a lingering fragrance. It was later transported to Soto Zen headquarters in Yokohama, Japan.</p> <p>In 1974, the Hong Kong newspaper "Express" reported that "the remains of Master Without Limits are enshrined in Japan," having been secretly transported to Japan by a Japanese dentist during the China-Japanese War. This dentist was none other than Watanabe Shiro, who had opened the "Hengyue Clinic" and was originally a Japanese spy.</p> <p>An article titled "The Mysterious Incident of the Theft of the Remains of the High Monk of Nanyue" provided a detailed account. The article stated that the dentist had treated the elderly monk at the Nantai Temple for dental issues several times, gaining his trust, and then stole the bodily remains of the Buddha one dark and stormy night.</p> <p>Japanese military monks have committed countless killings in China, and Japanese invaders caused the deaths of at least 50 million people in China. Japan is a completely non-religious country, it is simply an evil cult country. Japan must unconditionally return the remains of Master Without Limits from Nantai Temple to China.</p>
39 9	<p>Daily traffic accidents involving luxury vehicles have caused many ordinary families to go bankrupt. If there is a hope for global fairness and justice, the United Nations should rapidly develop a global convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Luxury cars are often used as a tool for showing off, and many luxury car drivers do not follow traffic rules, leading to accidents. However, vehicles that are passive in these accidents are often forced to provide a certain proportion of compensation to the luxury car, because the value of luxury vehicles is much higher than that of ordinary cars. Even a low percentage of compensation can result in the annual or even decade-long income of ordinary car drivers being wiped out in a single traffic accident.</p> <p>When ordinary cars are involved in major accidents with luxury vehicles, the amount of compensation is usually in the millions, which may far exceed the lifetime income of many ordinary people or families. Normal insurance coverage is simply unable to meet this amount of compensation. This means that ordinary car drivers either have to increase their insurance coverage by</p>

	<p>purchasing high amounts of insurance (which is an additional financial burden for the majority of ordinary people, adding to their daily economic burden), or they have to compensate for the remaining amount themselves (resulting in bankruptcy or even the death of the family). Bankruptcy or death often leads to desperate action, and ordinary car drivers may end up directly causing harm to luxury car drivers (for example, a truck that loses control of its brakes and is unable to kill the luxury car driver ends up accelerating and causing death). This is because they can't afford to pay, so they might also harm the person.</p> <p>Driving luxury cars will force other vehicles to increase their insurance claims, adding to the daily economic burden of ordinary families. It is common for vehicles to be involved in traffic accidents on the road. A luxury car driving on the road as a means of transportation will instinctively put pressure on nearby drivers with lower incomes. Some criminal groups even take advantage of the fact that luxury vehicles can obtain high compensation and set traps, intentionally driving luxury cars to collide with other vehicles in order to claim high illegal profits.</p> <p>Therefore, in the event of a traffic accident, compensation for the loss of luxury cars should not be based on a luxury model. There should be a limit on the amount of compensation for scratches or collisions. The maximum compensation for individual drivers should not exceed one twenty-fourth of middle class income in the region, or the maximum total compensation amount should not exceed one-twelfth of the average annual income of ordinary vehicle drivers or low-income individuals in the region. Any excess amount should be borne by the luxury car driver himself. Luxury cars are not like diamonds or jewelry worn or kept at home. Vehicles driving on the road are depreciating products and are a means of transportation. Any luxury vehicle driving on the road may pose a danger to others. Drivers of luxury cars must have psychological and financial resilience; otherwise, they should not buy luxury cars.</p>
400	<p>If we hope to achieve as much fairness and justice as possible globally, the United Nations should rapidly develop a global treaty on the following issues:</p> <p>The fairness of the law often lags far behind atrocities. The comfort brought to victims by the fairness or justice of the law lags far behind the disasters and traumas caused by atrocities. Rulers must have empathy, law makers must have empathy, and law enforcers must have empathy. In any country or region, if injustice in the justice system leads to disputes, victims should not be prevented from filing complaints, otherwise unforeseen retaliation or disasters may occur. As a result, anyone who uses coercive means or violence to prevent the victim from filing a complaint has lost basic administrative ethics and empathy. Once the victim uploads relevant materials and evidence to the relevant departments of the national government or the United Nations, the national judicial institutions must impose a six-month prison sentence on the criminal. If the offender is a public servant, his or her position must be revoked within one month. All personal and family assets of</p>

	<p>the offender and their affiliated unit must be disclosed within two weeks of the incident, and those who fail to disclose will be terminated from their employment. The main purpose of this convention is to deter crime through the above measures, reduce crime, promote the speedy resolution of judicial injustice, and facilitate effective governance in the region.</p>
40 1	<p>At present, there are many safety problems with genetically modified foods that have not been fully exposed, which pose a great threat to human health. The United Nations should rapidly develop an international convention on the following issues.</p> <p>Since the consumption period of genetically modified foods is usually much longer than the treatment period of drugs, the examination of reproductive toxicity and chronic toxicity should be more stringent than the safety examination of drugs. Currently, it is actually easier than drugs, so there should be regulations that are at least as rigorous as those for drugs. Genetically modified foods must undergo large-scale safety experiments and clinical trials before being marketed. In addition, developers and research institutions of genetically modified foods have a better understanding of the safety and potential hazards of these foods than the public does. Before genetically modified foods are put on the market, all employees and shareholders of the GM food company, as well as their family members, must consume the food for an extended period of time and prove its safety. They should not develop genetically modified foods for global consumption while themselves and their families only consume natural foods.</p>
40 2	<p>Some people use bone powder instead of meat to make ham sausage, resulting in a lack of the necessary nutrients in the food. In order to make seafood and other meat products appear fresh, some criminals use formaldehyde, borax, excessive sodium benzoate, or excessive potassium benzoate and other preservatives to produce toxic food, allowing for longer shelf life. Some even add formaldehyde or excessive alum and other toxic substances to rice noodles to make them more resilient. Some even use gelatin etc. to make fake sea cucumbers or jellyfish. Some criminals process sick and dying chickens, ducks, and pigs into meat products for sale. Generally, ordinary people cannot distinguish toxic food, inferior food, or fake food. These illegally manufactured foods are likely to cause damage to the liver, kidneys, or other systems, posing a great danger to human health, while counterfeiters reap huge profits. The United Nations should as soon as possible form the following international conventions on this issue:</p> <p>First, in the case of any manufacturer of toxic food, substandard food, and other food counterfeiters, the first offence will result in a fine of five times the amount involved. For a second offence, the fine will be ten times the amount involved, and for a third offence, personal property will be confiscated and a sentence of 2-5 years' imprisonment must be imposed.</p> <p>Second, anyone involved in a case involving CNY 1 million must be sentenced to 2-5 years in prison.</p>

	<p>Third, all offenders and their family members must report their travel itinerary to the police station before leaving their place of residence for another city or region.</p> <p>Fourth, criminals are prohibited from flying on airplanes or taking high-speed trains when traveling.</p> <p>Fifth, all family members are placed on the lifetime credit blacklist.</p> <p>Sixth, all offenders and their family members are prohibited from entering into any country or region's civil service system for life, and those already working in the civil service system must resign.</p> <p>Seventh, once a second offence has occurred, all offenders are prohibited from enjoying medical insurance services for life.</p> <p>Eighth, once a second offence has occurred, all family members and direct relatives of the above-mentioned offenders are prohibited from entering any university in the world for 100 years. If the offender or their descendants are reported by an informed person for violations, any university or government agency must deal with the case within 48 hours.</p> <p>Ninth, whistleblowers will receive a 40% reward for the confiscated amount.</p>
40 3	<p>To promote rural economic development and increase farmers' enthusiasm for production, the United Nations and the international community should form the following convention on the production and sale of processed agricultural products in rural areas:</p> <p>To promote rural economic development, as long as wild plants in rural areas are non-toxic substances, and there are historical records of past use for foot soaking, health care, beauty, or bathing, non-edible products produced by simple processing such as grinding or mild fermentation can be produced and sold without administrative approval, with the specific functions mentioned on the packaging. Producers and sellers are responsible for the quality and after-sales service of the products.</p>
40 4	<p>In order to sell real estate, some people use various means to tempt peasants with insufficient assets to leave the countryside and buy houses in the city. However, farmers lacking life skills are likely to fall deeper into poverty and cause social problems or crime after being deceived into entering the city or town. The United Nations should promptly form the following international convention on this issue:</p> <p>Any person who deceives peasants into buying houses in urban or rural areas, making it difficult to sustain their livelihood and becoming impoverished, shall be prohibited from entering or staying the civil service system. The personal and family assets of all the individuals involved shall be made public, and they must compensate the peasants for all their losses within three months. The ringleader is permanently banned from flying on airplanes or high-speed trains.</p>
40 5	<p>The United Nations and the international community have established the following convention for the recovery of assets related to major crimes such as</p>

	<p>large-scale telecommunications fraud, etc.:</p> <p>Prior to the disclosure of any criminal case or fraudulent activity, if illegal assets are jointly held by spouses or family members, any actions taken by spouses to divide their property through divorce or transfer assets will be considered invalid, as well as any gifts to family or non-family members for the purpose of division of property or transfer of assets. Victims or affected States have unlimited time to trace the assets, and the recovery of assets related to major crimes is not limited by the effective date of this Convention.</p>
40 6	<p>The United Nations and the international community must form the following convention on the following issues:</p> <p>Widely used virtual currencies for payment, but kept secret. The lack of transparency in virtual currencies has led to many negative consequences, such as tax evasion, money laundering, and illegal asset transfers. Unlike publicly traded companies, privately issued virtual currencies are not subject to the same regulatory requirements. This lack of transparency can lead to inequality in social wealth and even instability in the financial system. Virtual currencies, being privately issued without asset backing, cannot even meet the basic requirements for public listing companies, and are purely a Ponzi scheme! This seriously affects the financial stability and sustainable development of a country or region. Therefore, it is necessary to abolish non-transparent virtual currencies, and if virtual currencies cannot be transparent, they must be given a name, "black money."</p>
40 7	<p>Discharging nuclear waste water into the ocean poses a great danger to humanity, and the United Nations should promptly form an international convention on the issue. Any country that discharges nuclear waste water into the ocean shall have all of its marine products prohibited from being exported to any country or region. Any violators of the import ban shall be fined five times the amount of the violation, and the personal and family assets of all employees of the company involved must be permanently disclosed. Major offenders are prohibited from taking flights or high-speed trains, and must report to the local police before leaving any city.</p>
40 8	<p>In order to develop the rural economy, address rural poverty and narrow the gap between urban and rural areas, favourable rules for farmers must be established in rural production laws. The United Nations must also create a global convention that exempts all agricultural products, fresh and dry, from toll fees on highways. Any person who obstructs passage must be dismissed on the same day if it occurs, and no toll station shall employ such persons. Violators of the Convention and their family members are permanently prohibited from entering the civil service sector, and the personal and family assets of all individuals at the toll stations must be publicly and permanently disclosed.</p>
40 9	<p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For firefighters who have sacrificed in the line of duty, their personal and</p>

	<p>family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For firefighters who are injured and disabled while extinguishing fires, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is fully waived. For firefighters who are completely unable to work, their bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the firefighters or members of their families had any bank loans before the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities.</p> <p>If the above-mentioned warriors or their families need to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>
41 0	<p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For any warriors who have sacrificed themselves in the fight against the crimes listed in this table, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For warriors who are injured and disabled in the fight against the crimes listed, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is completely waived; For warriors who are completely unable to work, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the warriors or their family members had any bank loans prior to the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities.</p> <p>If the above-mentioned warriors or their families need to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>
41 1	<p>In order to establish a good social order and a good social atmosphere, the United Nations and the international community must form the following global consensus and conventions on the following issues:</p> <p>For any warriors who have sacrificed themselves in saving children from accidents, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. For warriors who are injured and disabled while saving children from accidents, half of their bank loans are waived and interest is fully waived; For warriors who are completely unable to work, their personal and family bank loans and interest are completely waived. As long as the warriors or their family members had any bank loans prior to the accident, the government must bear the relevant public obligations and responsibilities.</p> <p>If the above-mentioned warriors or their families need to take out another loan, the loan interest rate will be half of the normal level for the same situation when the total loan amount is within the total income of the warrior in the past three years.</p>
41 2	<p>In order to establish a global consensus and convention to deter potential criminals from engaging in the theft and trafficking of infants by colluding with medical personnel, the United Nations and the international community must come to an agreement on the following issues:</p>

	<p>1. It is a serious criminal offence to steal, replace, or sell a child in hospitals. All individuals and their immediate family members within three generations associated with the entities involved must unconditionally disclose all their assets.</p> <p>2. Offenders will receive a prison sentence twice the length of the period in which the infant was stolen, replaced, or sold, with no possibility of parole or early release. If a stolen baby is recovered after five years, the offender must serve a minimum sentence of ten years.</p> <p>3. Any person in public office involved in the crime will be dismissed, and all offenders will be fined five times the amount of illicitly gained profits.</p> <p>4. Those working in hospitals will be permanently prohibited from continuing in that occupation.</p> <p>5. Anyone obstructing the investigation of such crimes will be immediately dismissed from their positions.</p> <p>6. Offenders will be subject to criminal penalties.</p> <p>7. Compensation will be provided to the families of victims.</p> <p>8. The principal personnel of the involved hospital will be removed from their positions and demoted by three levels.</p> <p>9. All offenders and their family members must report their travel plans to the police when leaving their hometown for another city or region.</p> <p>10. Offenders are prohibited from traveling by airplane or high-speed trains.</p> <p>11. The entire family will be blacklisted for life.</p> <p>12. All family members of offenders are prohibited from working in the public sector in any country or region.</p> <p>13. Any government agency must process and handle reports of offenders or their descendants violating regulations within 48 hours.</p> <p>14. Other forms of theft and trafficking of infants will be subject to the above penalties.</p>
41 3	The United Nations and the international community should urge the World Health Organization to revise outdated medical practices and establish consensus and agreements to prohibit the foolish treatment practice of doctors removing patients' tonsils after they have a common cold or infectious disease.
41 4	The close proximity of two residential buildings affects eyesight, health, and firefighting rescue. Any two buildings with six or more floors (with a minimum interior room height of 2.4 meters) must maintain a minimum distance of 30 meters.
41 5	All values related to the U.S. dollar or Chinese yuan in this convention are calculated based on their average exchange rate with gold in 2023.
41 6	Should any crime related to this consensus occur in any country in the future, upon receiving a report from any individual, the government institutions of that country must take effective action against the offender within 24 hours. If the criminal has committed a crime over an extended period of time, resulting in a major case, and the government has failed to detect it, all officials associated

	with the region must be held accountable for their negligence.
41 7	If the public believes that a civil servant or legislator lacks a sense of justice, responsibility, empathy, and compassion, and that they improperly handle or manage specific issues, and within a calendar year are complained about five times due to separate issues, which are verified as valid complaints, they must resign from their position within two days.
41 8	If the country is almost entirely engaged in criminal activities or almost universally supports such acts as fraud, kidnapping, torture, human trafficking, rape, gang rape, live burials and massacres, the question arises whether that country should be considered for its future existence.
41 9	If the United Nations holds a global consensus vote on this issue for three months, and 1.5 billion people support the draft, the United Nations should consider developing the draft into a convention, or making minor modifications to it before it becomes a convention.

* If the area of northern Myanmar, originally under China's control, could be reincorporated into China and become a part of Yunnan Province, China would undoubtedly make a long-term, substantial investment in this region. The aim would be to help the local population escape from poverty, gambling, telecom fraud, opium, and drug use. Furthermore, a considerable amount of industry would be transferred to this region. The investments and additional income thus generated, inclusive of infrastructure investments in railways, would contribute to the financial revenue of the area, rapidly raising it to CNY trillions. This, in turn, would position China to become a global leader in reversing the chaotic order in northern Myanmar and helping the region break free from the throes of war, reaping rich annual rewards. At this juncture, given that the military forces in northern Myanmar would undoubtedly be fully disarmed, resulting in a reduction of at least 200,000 to 300,000 soldiers, the region would effectively nurture a large group of peace warriors. This completely aligns with the four conditions stipulated by Mr. Nobel for awarding the Peace Prize, leading us to believe that the Nobel Peace Prize may not be far off for the leaders and media authorities of this nation.

Member States provide funding to the United Nations, creating opportunities for it to effectively serve the orderly operation of the world, as well as to better maintain world peace and sustainable development. There is an expectation for the United Nations to formulate a global consensus and UN conventions as the basis for global governance, with the hope that the UN can discuss and establish a basic framework within 120 days.

Given the number of topics to cover, it may be necessary to discuss them separately before forming distinct UN conventions and global consensus agreements. It is anticipated that the United Nations could hold meetings in various cities with unique characteristics throughout China, such as Wuhan, Jingshan, Yichang, Hengshan, Chenzhou, Leiyang, Foshan, Yuanjiang, Kaifeng, Taiyuan, Zibo, Xinxiang, Nanyang, Nanchang, Guilin, Qingdao, among others, to develop related UN conventions and a global consensus. Additionally, these locations would offer the opportunity to enjoy the local scenery, taste the local cuisine, and experience the local culture and customs

during the breaks of these meetings.

The author of this article suggests that the United Nations and the international community should jointly discuss and form international consensus and conventions to address more than 400 thorny issues, in order to deter criminals, prevent crimes, combat crime, reduce war and conflict, maintain world peace, regulate state governance, reform the selection of civil servants, improve the level of government governance, transform intensive farming of chickens, ducks, geese, and pigs that are detrimental to health into dispersed farming by farmers, increase the proportion of healthy agricultural and livestock products, ban the use of herbicides, develop ecological agriculture, develop rural economy, and increase farmers' income. If the United Nations can achieve this, the world will reach a new milestone.

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